

Deliverable 3.5

The water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit – Final release

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Summary

WP3 aims at developing and deploying a series of water-smart applications, to be demonstrated at six Living Labs (LLs). The different solutions developed and demonstrated in T3.2-T3.7 are conceptually assembled into 2 coherent toolkits, a) the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit and b) the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit. The current report documents the final release of the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit, which is comprised of the following eight tools: UWOT #22, regional demand-supply matching GIS tool #23, reclaimed water distribution network water quality model #24, water-energy-phosphorous balance planning module #25, QMRA+ #26, risk assessment for urban water reuse module #27, short-term demand forecasting tool #28 and SuTRa #31 and complements the other toolkit. The final release of the toolkit aims at updating the readers about the latest developments of tools focusing on tool description, attributes and information around pre-existing background, developments and advancements within the project, navigation and primary functionalities, interoperability, indicative applications and synergistic benefits and how to access each tool and test data. Additionally, D3.5 dives deeper in the application of tools to the LLs by introducing initially the water-smartness challenges and ambition of the LLs, presents the selected technologies and products and explains the integrative use, conceptual links, data flows and pilot interactions. Further, it describes the pre-processing stage and setup process before documenting the results and lessons learned from tools and technologies' application to the LLs. Building on results from the cases, the toolkit attempts to provide a more holistic and complementary picture of how water-smartness can be enhanced while highlighting complementarity and replicability aspects of tools.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOP	Advanced Oxidation Processes
API	Application Programming Interface
ARPAV	Agenzia regionale per la protezione ambientale Veneto
ASR	Aquifer Storage and Recovery
BOD	Biological Oxygen Demand
BOHB	Bayesian optimization with Hyperband
BS	Baseline Scenario
BSD	Berkeley Source Distribution
BWS	B-WaterSmart
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures
CARD	Controlled Agricultural Recharge and Drainage
CCRO	Closed Circuit Reverse Osmosis
CDF	Cumulative Distribution Function
CE	Circular Economy
CLC	CORINE Land Cover
CML	Camara Municipal de Lisboa
CO	Confidential
CoP	Community of Practice
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRC	Climate Ready Certificate
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
CSV	Comma-separated values
DALY	Disability Adjusted Life Years

DAP	Data Application Products
DBMS	Database Management System
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DE	Digital Enabler
DPR	Direct Potable Reuse
DSS	Decision Support System
DW	Distilled Water
DWD	Deutscher Wetterdienst
DWTP	Drinking Water Treatment Plant
Dx.x	Deliverable
EC-JRC	European Commission - Joint Research Centre
EEA	European Environment Agency
EEC	European Economic Community
EEPA	European Enterprise Promotion Awards
EI	Expected Impact
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
FIWARE GE	FIWARE Generic Enabler
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GDPR	General data protection regulation
GHG	Greenhouse gases
GIS	Geographical Information System

GPU	Graphics processing unit
GUI	Graphical User Interface
GW	Greywater
GWR	Greywater Recycling
HD	Hard Drive
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IdM	Identity Management
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IoT	Internet of Things
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technology
IWA	International Water Association
JRC	Joint Research Centre.
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Cost
LL(s)	Living Lab(s)
LNEC	Laboratorio Nacional de Engenharia Civil
MAR	Managed Aquifer Recharge
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MS	Milestone
MSL	Machine Learning

NA	Not Available / Not applicable
NGO	Non-governmental organization
NGSI-LD	Next Generation Service Interfaces – Linked Data
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens
O3/RO	Ozone/reverse osmosis
OOWV	Oldenburgisch-Ostfriesischer Wasserverband
OPC	Open Platform Communications
OPEX	Operating Expenses
OS	Operating System
PC	Personal Computer
PDF	Portable Document Format
PET	Potential Evapotranspiration
PIF	Progetto Integrato Fusina
PLC	Programmable logic controller
PO	Project Officer
PU	Public
QCRA	Quantitative Cost Risk Analysis
QMRA	Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment
R&D	Research and Development
RAM	Random-Access Memory
RDSMG	Regional demand-supply matching GIS tool
REST	Representational State Transfer
RO	Reverse osmosis
RR	Resource Recovery
RW	Rainwater

RWDS	Reclaimed water distribution system
RWH	Rainwater Harvesting
SDFT	Short-term demand forecasting tool
SDM	System Dynamic Modelling
SM	Sewer Mining
SO	Strategic Objective
SSD	Solid-State Drive
SuTRa	Subsurface Transport and Removal
tbd	To Be Decided
TP	Technology Product
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
Tx.x	Task
UI	User's Interface
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
URN	Uniform Resource Name
UWC	Urban Water Cycle
UWOT	Urban Water Optioneering Tool
WC	Water closet
WE	Water Europe
WEM	Water Europe Marketplace
WEP	Water-Energy-Phosphorus
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WHG	Wasserhaushaltsgesetz
WiCE	Water in the Circular Economy
WM	Washing Machine
WP	Work Package

WPC	Water Production Centre
WPx	Work Package
WQ	Water quality
WRRF	Water resource recovery facility
WS	Water Smart
WSGI	Web Server Gateway Interface
WW	Wastewater
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant
XML	Extensible markup language

Executive summary

The BWS project aims to accelerate the transformation to water-smart economies and societies in coastal Europe and beyond. To achieve this, the project is delivering (among others) smart data applications for more efficient and safe allocation and use of resources (water, energy, nutrients) while building on FIWARE technology that will enable interoperability and cross-sectoral exchange. The latter is considered as a key element for systemic change. While working on this purpose, WP3 “Water-Smart applications and data” focused on the development and deployment of a series of water-smart applications, to be demonstrated at the six Living Labs (LLs) of the BWS project, namely Alicante (ES), Bodø (NO), Flanders (BE), Lisbon (PT), East Frisia (DE) and Venice (IT). Research partners and innovative solution providers worked with the LLs representatives, i.e., the problem owners participating in the project, having high ambitions to address water-related challenges and opportunities, in order to deliver tools and Information and Communications Technology (ICT) solutions (combined with technologies). The tools target to enhance water-smartness in (waste) water reuse, recovery of energy and materials, management of water systems and infrastructure, monitoring, negotiation and decision support, water cycle modelling and assessment, risk assessment and management, water demand analysis and natural resources’ management. This deliverable (D3.5) reports the final release of the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit and presents the 8 solutions (Table 1) developed in the related tasks (T3.2 – T3.7) in close collaboration with the Living Labs.

With the goal to develop, customize and demonstrate data applications for transparent management and interoperability, WP3 developed and proposed an interoperability approach in T3.1 building on FIWARE technology and its open specifications to increase the transferability of the water-smart applications. Tasks T3.2 – T3.7 develop and demonstrate advanced analytics, models and tools for challenges identified through individual LLs and customize some of them to be compatible with FIWARE. While co-developing and implementing tools that demonstrate the advantages of the project’s interoperability approach and putting together BWS solutions from a number of tools that address similar problems at different scales, two sets of solutions emerged that form the two ICT solutions toolkits of the project (Table 1). The numbering of the tools (i.e. ‘#xx’) is the same as in the Grant Agreement of the project, Annex 1 part B section 1.3.5 Table 5 and is consistently used through all documents prepared by B-WaterSmart that make reference to the tools.

- ***The monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit*** which aims at improving water smartness by supporting the steps of context awareness, decision making, management, monitoring, and certification. The toolkit is comprised of 10 tools:
 - The Water Reuse Strategic Platform (#16) which has been built upon the Digital Enabler (#32),
 - The Sludge Management Platform (#19) which has been also built upon the Digital Enabler (#32),
 - The Environment for Decision Support and Alternative Course Selection (#17),
 - The Re-Actor (#18),
 - The Urban Water Cycle (UWC) Observatory (#20),
 - The Stormwater Reuse Management System (#21),
 - The Nessie System (#29),
 - The Environmental Dashboard (#30) and
 - The Climate-Readiness Certification tool (#33).

- **The water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit**, comes to supplement the above-mentioned toolkit. It is focused on advanced analytics for providing detailed evidence in support of decision-making. This is achieved by providing the tools to conduct simulations, predictions, demand/supply match-making and other quantitative analyses. This second toolkit is comprised of 8 tools:
 - The Urban Water Optioneering Tool (UWOT) (#22),
 - The Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS tool (#23),
 - The Reclaimed Water Distribution Network Water Quality Model (#24),
 - The Water-Energy-Phosphorous Balance Planning Module (#25),
 - The QMRA+ tool (#26),
 - The Risk Assessment for Urban Water Reuse Module (#27),
 - The Short-Term Demand Forecasting Tool (#28)
 - The SuTRa tool (#31)¹.

The two toolkits conceptually assemble the different solutions, developed and eventually demonstrated in T3.2 to 3.7, into two coherent solutions that provide added value with respect to the water related challenges of the case studies, serving at the same time as an umbrella helping to clarify a potential combined use of the different tools.

Table 1: The two BWS ICT solutions toolkits and the tools that assemble them. The name of the city that follows corresponds to relevant Living Labs, where the tool is applied.

The monitoring, negotiation, and decision support solutions toolkit	The water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit
1. Water-reuse strategic platform (#16) – Venice	1. UWOT (#22) – Flanders & East Frisia
2. Sludge management platform (#19) – Venice	2. Regional demand-supply matching GIS tool (#23) – East Frisia
3. Digital Enabler (#32) – Venice	3. Short-term demand forecasting tool (#28) – East Frisia
4. Re-Actor (#18) – Alicante	4. QMRA+ for water reuse and agriculture (#26) – Flanders
5. Environment for decision support and alternative course selection - BASEFORM (#17) – Lisbon	5. SuTRa (#31) – Flanders
6. UWC observatory (#20) – Lisbon	6. Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model - BASEFORM (#24) – Lisbon
7. Climate-readiness certification tool (#33) – Lisbon	7. Water-energy-phosphorous balance planning module - BASEFORM (#25) – Lisbon
8. Stormwater reuse management system (#21) – Flanders	8. Risk Assessment for urban water reuse module - BASEFORM (#27) – Lisbon
9. Nessie System (#29) – Bodø	
10. Environmental Dashboard (#30) – Bodø	

¹ SuTRa tool was originally called "ASR pro" tool. The name of the tool has been changed to 'SuTRa' to better reflect the broader application potential.

As noted earlier, D3.5 reports the final release of the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit and the tools that comprise it. The current report has been prepared in parallel with D3.4 “The monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit – Final release” in order to ensure that the work in the related tasks is aligned and the information/results are presented in a consistent way. Another reason for doing that is to highlight the complementarity of both toolkits and propose synergistic ways in which the tools could be used to provide a more holistic and complementary picture of water-smartness at the water cycle scale, while building on results from the cases (including findings from technologies’ implementations in WP2, when relevant). The general sections of D3.4/D3.5 (i.e., Chapter 1- Chapter 4) are common for the two toolkits in order to set the base for the readers while ensuring that each toolkit report is autonomous, complements the other and assists readers in their navigation through the available contents. Similarly, the concluding section of the document includes some parts that are repeated in both reports. These are related to final considerations that document the conceptual links among all tools and describe how the 18 solutions of both toolkits are related to the water related challenges and the steps of the urban water cycle.

The final release deliverable of the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit (as well as the one of the other toolkit) aims at introducing the readers to the tools per se and to the final developments as well as to the actual application of tools to the case studies.

The following features of tools are addressed in the first part of the report (Chapter 5) and follow a common pattern across different tools:

- Description of tools and their attributes (Section 5.x.1),
- Pre-existing background (context) (Section 5.x.2),
- Developments/advancements made within the project (Section 5.x.3),
- Navigation and primary functionalities (Section 5.x.4),
- Interoperability options covering also FIWARE compatibility when supported (Section 5.x.5),
- Indicative applications and synergistic benefits (Section 5.x.6),
- Accessing tool and test data (Section 5.x.7).

With regard to the application of tools to the case studies, which is documented in the second part of this report (Chapter 6), the information is structured under each LL and includes the following sections:

- Key Water Smart (WS) challenges (as the ones documented in Section 2), ambition and case study description,
- Application of tools and methods by providing information on:
 - the selected tools and technologies of the pilot,
 - the integrative use of tools, pilot interaction and data flows,
 - the pre-processing stage and input data
 - Setup process and application
 - Results
- Initial lessons extracted at the LL level,
- Summary table which provides concise information on the tools and technologies applications in order to be used for the population of the Water Europe Marketplace (WEM) and the dissemination of the LL work to a wider audience. The WEM, which is a versatile platform for networking, business development, discovering and sharing knowledge, and exhibiting achievement in the areas of Water, Energy, and Materials, was originally created as part of the NextGen project and evolved through the BWS and ULTIMATE projects into the Water

Europe Marketplace, currently curated by Water Europe. The platform is accessible via the URL following URL.

<https://mp.watereurope.eu/>

For the case of Lisbon, the above parts of the LL section are duplicated in D3.4 and D3.5 since the 6 tools demonstrated in the LL are split in the two toolkit reports. With this approach, the application of tools is presented in a consistent way, as well as the overall picture of the LL work which involves integration and close interaction of the applied solutions.

D3.5 also attempts to extract findings with regard to the interoperability, transferability and the replicability of the tools and the toolkit overall which are documented in the concluding section.

The tools of the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit are applied in 3 out of 6 LLs and are noted in the proceeding table (Table 2).

Table 2: Ambitions and challenges of the 3 LLs where the tools of the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit are applied.

Living Lab	Ambition	Challenge	Tools
Flanders	To become more water-smart	High drinking water demand due to dense population; high irrigation water demand for agriculture; groundwater overexploitation; water quality deterioration; water scarcity due to droughts and climate change.	#22, #26, #31 (#21 reported in D3.4)
East Frisia		Increasing water demand by industry and agriculture; untapped efficiency potential in water resources allocation	#22, #23, #28
Lisbon		Distance form freshwater sources; need to increase urban green areas; climate change; growing population and economy.	#24, #25, #27 (#17, 20, 33 reported in D3.4)

Note: the challenges included in the table are the ones defined in GA and documented in the M18 scientific progress report, under the LL section (1.3.2 to 1.3.7).

Regarding the interoperability options of tools, and as noted in MS17 “Draft input received from T3.2-3.7 for D3.2 and D3.3; 1/3 of WP3 apps FIWARE compliant” a third of WP3 apps is foreseen to be FIWARE compliant at the end of their BWS development phase. In more detail, WP3 delivers 19 applications (18 from T3.2-T3.7 - reported in the toolkits’ deliverables D3.4/D3.5 and 1 from T3.9 - based on information found in D3.1) out of which 7 are FIWARE compliant. The last-mentioned tool is the water-smartness dashboard (#34) currently under development under T3.9 “Develop and deploy the water-smartness dashboard” and to be applied in all BWS case studies. The related deliverables

of the water-smartness dashboard are D3.6 (early release) / D3.7 (final release). The other six tools developed in T3.2-T3.7 and are FIWARE compatible are the following:

1. Water-reuse strategic platform (#16)
2. Sludge management platform (#19)
3. Short-term demand forecasting tool (#28)
4. Nessie System (#29)
5. Environmental Dashboard (#30)
6. Digital Enabler (#32)

The tools have been reported in the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit (D3.4), with exception of the short-term demand forecasting tool (#28), which is part of the current report (D3.5).

Replicability of the digital solutions in other cities/regions is ensured by different actions and results that T3.8 pursued while interacting with the rest of the project. The developed BWS FIWARE approach with its interoperability guidelines (implementation guidelines, FIWARE and interoperability maturity levels) developed in T3.1 helped developers to conceive and realize tools that are easily integrated with third party systems using open and standard APIs, thus boosting replicability. As described above, WP3 will have delivered 7 FIWARE compatible solutions by the end of the project. Synergies with other WPs, i.e., WP2, WP1, WP7 also supports replicability of solutions. This was achieved by a) intensifying discussions and exchange of experience among technology/tool developers in joint WP2/WP3 meetings, b) organising the training activities (at least 3 different training activities have taken place so far with the rest being planned during the last year of the project, c) distributing materials and recordings (foreseen under WP1) which were communicated inside and outside of the project through peer networks and WP7 dissemination channels and, finally, d) documenting the lessons learned that have been extracted so far from the application of the tools to the LLs in the final version of both toolkits. The findings from the LLs are communicated through the public toolkits' deliverables (D3.2 – D3.5) but also via the WEM under the case study sections and the related factsheets. This is achieved by extracting information from the current report and using it for the population of the WEM. Further a new Milestone (MS32) is suggested to be added in M45 which foresees that final key results and lessons learned from the LLs are available in the WEM.

As noted earlier, WEM is a versatile platform for networking, business development, discovering and sharing knowledge, and exhibiting achievement in the areas of Water, Energy, and Materials. It was originally created as part of the NextGen project and evolved through the BWS and ULTIMATE projects into the WEM, currently curated by Water Europe. Detailed information regarding this product can be found in D7.1 “B-WaterSmart Knowledge portal 'live' with initial upgrades”, where it is documented whereas the link to access the web application is the following:

<https://mp.watereurope.eu/>

1 Introduction

This report, along with D3.4, is the final release of deliverables which document the work done within the tasks T3.2 – T3.7 under which the development, deployment and demonstration of a series of water-smart applications are foreseen in the six Living Labs (LLs), according to the Grant Agreement (GA). Task 3.8, building on the afore-mentioned work attempts to conceptually assemble the different solutions developed and eventually demonstrated in T3.2 to T3.7 into two coherent toolkits that provide added value with respect to the water related challenges of the case studies, serving at the same time as an umbrella to orchestrate and align the LLs around the deployment of tools. Under the lead of T3.8, tool owners in collaboration with the problem owners initially contributed to MS20 “Final input received from T3.2-T3.7 for D3.4 and D3.5” by delivering 6 individual input reports at M34 (end of June), one for each task, which served as the starting point for the development of the final release of both toolkits. The same approach was followed at an earlier stage of the project when draft input reports were received for MS17 (M23) and used to deliver the early release of the toolkits (D3.2/D3.3) in M25. At that point, the focus was on the documentation of the early developments of tools, whereas MS20 and the final release of toolkits aim at providing details on the latest developments of tools and their applications to the 6 LLs.

For the development of D3.2/D3.3/D3.4/D3.5, the leading teams, namely ENG, ICCS and KWR worked in parallel and in close cooperation, in order to ensure that information and results are aligned and presented in a consistent way. The ultimate purpose of T3.8 is to highlight the complementarity of both toolkits and propose synergistic ways in which the tools developed could be used to provide a holistic picture of water-smartness at the water cycle scale. With that as a goal, the D3.5 report is structured as follows.

Chapter 2 and chapter 3 set the base around the water challenges and limitations, encountered in water management and Circular Economy (CE) and are the same for both toolkits reports (D3.4/D3.5). Similarly, the section that follows (Chapter 4), is repeated in both reports, and explains how both toolkits complement each other, contribute to a more holistic assessment, and support the increase of water-smartness. It needs to be highlighted that necessary adjustments were made in order to ensure that each toolkit report is autonomous, but at the same time they complement each other and assist readers in navigating them through the available contents. Chapter 5 of this report, which practically forms one of the main bodies of this deliverable, documents in a consistent way the features of the 8 tools that form the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit. Tool descriptions have been originally prepared for the purpose of MS20 (as foreseen in GA) by the tool owners and problem owners in T3.2-T3.7 and were revised to accommodate the needs of D3.4/D3.5 (i.e., final release of toolkits). Chapters 6 to 8, which complement tools’ description in Chapter 5, have been allocated to the Flanders, East Frisia and Lisbon LL respectively and document the actual application and use of tools in the different case studies. Given that the Lisbon case tools are distributed across both toolkits, the content for the Lisbon LL is replicated in the D3.4 and D3.5 reports. This is done to ensure continuity and to clearly illustrate the advantages derived from the combined use of these tools. With regard to the LL sections (Chapters 6 to 8), those set the basis of the LL work by briefly describing the case studies, the key water-smartness challenges and ambitions and listing the selected tools and technologies applied in their pilots. The integrative use of tools is also included in such sections (and that is the reason for including contents in both reports for the case of Lisbon), while making any necessary connection with the WP2 technologies (when relevant). The sections that follow provide details on the pre-processing stage and input data, the set-up process, the results produced, and the

early findings and lessons learned. The concluding sub-section in chapters 6, 7 and 8 include a summary table where concise information is provided at LL level from the application of the different solutions while making references to WP2 technologies, when relevant. The information of D3.4/D3.5 is used for the creation of the early factsheets of the LLs in the WEM which is suggested to be updated with additional results and lessons learned at a later step of the project (M45) via online forms (available in the WEM).

Chapter 9, building on the autonomous LLs work, concentrates and highlights conclusions at the toolkit level while summarising key information for the 8 tools that form the water cycle modelling and assessment solution toolkit.

Regarding the appendix of this report, Annex A (Section 12) explains the Technology Readiness Level, as considered in the current deliverable, and used in Chapter 5 for defining TRL of each tool, whereas Annex B (Section 13) presents the template tables that were used to collect structured information for the tools and their applications to the case studies. As part of the synergies across work packages, the information gathered in tabular format regarding tools (as part of MS17 and the early release of toolkits D3.2/D3.3) was used to populate the Water Europe Marketplace of T7.1 with tools' information. After D3.4/D3.5 submission, the same approach will be followed, and the content and summary tables of the LLs will be used to formulate the first version of case study factsheet. Finally, Annex C (Section 14) provides a summary table of the different tools described in deliverables D3.4/D3.5. This is done for facilitating the readers to easily associate tool numbers to the appropriate name and basic information.

2 Water challenges and limitations

Engineers, practitioners, decision makers and different types of stakeholders related to water systems face a diverse set of conditions and challenges. Three of the global water challenges that are related to water security, as highlighted by UNESCO (Makarigakis and Jimenez-Cisneros, 2019) are a) water availability, b) water quality and c) water related hazards. As stated in the same source, pressures on water availability can be attributed to population and economic growth, agriculture, water scarcity and/or climate variability and change.

Overpopulation as well as improvements in living standards create constantly increasing water needs. These needs put pressure on available water resources, resulting in imbalance between water supply and demand and leading to water shortage conditions in cities (Foti et al., 2012; Brown et al., 2019). Urbanization (i.e., the tendency of the population to be concentrated into urban areas) leads to the transformation of once natural landscapes to urban lands and as a result the available freshwater resources are being limited (Okello et al., 2015). According to Thomas and Durham (2003), population growth particularly limits the amount of water available per person, because an increase in per capita water consumption driven by development will intensify water demand, straining the local water supply. To meet the increasing water demands, many cities extensively use groundwater as a supplement to the available surface water. Therefore, additional pressure is caused due to groundwater overexploitation and quality deterioration. As the supply of water must be assured for all and meet the basic needs despite (any) regional imbalances in water resources availability, water supply management is necessary in order to distribute it among different categories of users (Arsiso et al., 2017). Indicatively, Figure 1 depicts the relationship between global population and water withdrawal from 1950 to 2010.

Figure 1: Global Population and Water Withdrawal 1900–2010 (Zisopoulou and Panagoulia, 2021).

Water resources are also vulnerable as they are exposed to climate change (Ellen and Jay, 2008; Raskin et al., 1992; Rochdane et al., 2012). Recent research shows that climate change causes the increase in temperature, variability and changes in precipitation patterns (Rochdane et al., 2012). Changes in the frequency and intensity of precipitation may have a significant impact on stream flow and the volume of water stored in reservoirs. As a result, increased occurrence of floods or droughts take place and affect the quality and quantity of water resources at local and regional level (Arsiso et al., 2017). The projected impacts of climate change on freshwater flows are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Projected impacts of climate change on freshwater flows (IPCC, 2007).

Changes in water resources have significant socio-economic impacts. Low water supply and droughts affect many sectors, such as agriculture, forestry, energy and drinking water provision. Irrigated agriculture, hydropower generation, use of cooling water and other activities related to water use are susceptible to changed flow regimes and reduced annual water availability (EEA, 2010).

The challenges referred to above are exacerbated by the mismanagement of available water resources. Groundwater is too significant to not be properly managed in the face of a changing climate and land use. Policy makers, environmental managers, and urban planners, who are concerned with the future availability of water supplies and the sustainability of water use, need to incorporate changes in groundwater management into broader environmental change scenarios (Okello et al, 2015). They need to find sustainable solutions for moderating the impact of climate change and urban development and focus on alternative water sources to face the existing and future pressures (Eriyagama et al., 2010; Kirsten and Mark, 2011).

Figure 3 describes the major water related pressures in a graphic form and arranges them under the three global water challenges highlighted by UNESCO (Makarigakis and Jimenez-Cisneros, 2019). Population and economic growth, agriculture, water scarcity, regional imbalance in water availability and climate change put pressure on water resources availability. Water quality, on the other hand, can be attributed to microbial and toxic pollution, sedimentation, salinization and eutrophication, among others. Lastly, droughts and floods are the most known water related hazards. It is highlighted that this is not an extensive list of water related pressures and elaboration on each one of them falls outside the scope of this deliverable.

Figure 3: Water challenges and pressures.

The above water related challenges place pressure on natural resources, which make the need of shifting from the traditional linear model (take-use-dispose) to a circular economy of vital importance (Govindan and Hasanagic, 2018). The principles of CE are founded on the fact that “today’s waste becomes tomorrow’s resources that yield economic, social and environmental benefits” (Mandy Mbavarira and Grimm, 2021). The fact that societies gain benefits from something considered waste, the reduction in energy consumption, the large number of alternative technologies, the constant availability of wastewater, the decrease in pressure on natural resources and the shift towards greener technologies and processes are some of the strengths and opportunities of circular economy in the wastewater sector highlighted by Guerra- Rodríguez et al. (2020).

Nevertheless, there are barriers in applying technologies as part of a circular economy. According to Govindan and Hasanagic (2018), such barriers are related to a) the high upfront costs, which are

prohibitive for investors and companies who value profits more than environmental impacts, b) the lack of governmental laws and policies which could support the shift towards a circular economy, c) the need to solve technological challenges in the products development in order to enable products to be designed with environmentally friendly technology, and d) the people's low awareness of the principles of circular economy. Little experience of CE in large-scale implementations and general distrust towards the use of reclaimed water are also considered as barriers in the implementation of circular economy (Guerra-Rodríguez et al., 2020). Mandy Mbavarira and Grimm (2021) support the view (based on a review of literature and input from expert interviews) that some of the key barriers of CE opportunities in the water industry are outdated legislation, health and safety risks (which hamper social acceptance), fluctuating fertilizer quality that cannot always be guaranteed with varying concentrations in wastewater which in turn hampers market acceptance. Social acceptance and strong psychological effect in society against direct waste recycling also delay the adoption of CE solutions. Other barriers highlighted by the same authors are the expensive technologies e.g., on monitoring infrastructure and water attributes and the requirement of a high-level of IT readiness and capability for handling big data which increases water organisations overheads. The prioritization of investments which often are in favour of centralised infrastructure rather than complete decentralised systems and the fact that CE remains a complex concept and less something that can be practically adopted cause additional delays in the transition from linear to circular systems. The same authors conclude that digitalization supports CE and can help societies optimise the circularity gains (Mandy Mbavarira and Grimm, 2021). Towards the same direction, Lee et al.(2015) argue that in order to cope with water related challenges, access to water-related data and information is fundamental in order to build sophisticated strategies for water management.

By considering these limitations in CE and in water infrastructure, smart water solutions and tools seem to lead the way towards new water management approaches that will help to increase the efficiency of all elements in the water network (Lee et al., 2015) while supporting the adoption of circular economy technologies. Benefits that come along with this shift towards circularity, while utilizing digitalisation, include reduction of energy, unnecessary water loses and resources exploitation, better monitoring and reporting in quality, quantity and reuse of water, better preparation for water hazards, significant support in decision making and rise of stakeholders' and citizens engagement and awareness towards more sustainable behaviours which value and embrace circular economy opportunities (Mandy Mbavarira and Grimm, 2021).

3 The urban water cycle and the cycle of technology implementation

The major components and pathways of the urban water cycle (UWC) are highly affected by urbanisation and human interventions (Figure 4). Human interventions mostly originate from the need to provide water services to the urban population, including water supply, stormwater drainage and wastewater collection and management/disposal (Marsalek et al., 2014). The same applies to rural areas too. The three major water services have been highlighted in blue, yellow and green respectively in the below graph (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Urban water cycle – main components and pathways (source: (Marsalek et al., 2014)).

The engineered methods alter the hydrologic cycle and form the urban water cycle, which is primarily consisted of eight main steps as depicted in Figure 5 i.e., source, treatment, distribution, storage, use, collection, treatment and discharge, within which the water “travels” from source and eventually is discharged back to the environment. Within those steps, the water practitioners need to be equipped with state-of-the-art technologies and tools to design systems in a robust way to meet water related challenges.

Figure 5: The main steps of the urban water cycle.

As explained by Makropoulos et al. (2008), “the traditional approach is to consider the infrastructure that delivers potable water separately from the infrastructure that disposes of wastewater and separately to the provision of drainage for stormwater. There is growing need to re-evaluate this approach in order to seek ways to, inter alia, minimise the environmental impact of urban areas on supply sources and receiving waters.” Based on that traditional concept, conventional water management systems are built in a linear model which includes the three main steps of a) producing (potable) water, b) using it and c) disposing, as quickly as possible (Bouziotas et al., 2020). On the contrary, circular water systems and models (Figure 6), prioritise reduction of wastewater, removal of pollutants from water and waste water, reuse of waste water, recycling of water, recovery of resources as nutrients and energy and rethinking of water and wastewater to save and conserve water and to optimise water use, in all the relevant sectors (Morseletto et al., 2022; Smol et al., 2020). This new, circular path of water and wastewater, which comes to substitute the conventional linear management model (Bouziotas et al., 2019a), is an integral part of a CE, “where the value of products, materials and resources is maintained in the economy for as long as possible, and the generation of waste is minimised” (EU Commission, 2015). But as any other water/wastewater management model, it needs systemic innovation through a combination of new hardware technology, concepts and software solutions for the whole cycle of technology implementation: from optimal planning, what-if scenarios modelling, negotiations and decision making to monitoring, control and long-term performance assessment (Figure 7).

Figure 6: Circular economy model for water and wastewater management.

While working under uncertainty and trying to deliver sustainable, robust and adaptive systems, robust decision-making and dynamic adaptive policy pathway approaches (Haasnoot et al., 2013; Walker et al., 2013) have been suggested by some researchers in the literature, in order to achieve economic, environmental and societal objectives. Primary steps considered in such approaches are: understand the current situation and conduct problem analysis (for future conditions too), investigate and evaluate actions to reach desired goals, develop contingency plans, implement corrective actions and monitor the actions/plans implemented (Haasnoot et al., 2013).

In order to work towards delivering sustainable, robust and adaptive systems, new advanced software solutions coupled with CE technologies and concepts across a diverse set of conditions and under water challenges need to be exploited by the different stakeholders and decision makers within all steps of the technology implementation route (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Steps in technology implementation.

4 The B-Water Smart ICT solutions toolkits

Challenges related to water described in sections 2 and 3 call for continuous and substantial innovations to avoid wasting such a precious resource due to inefficient management of its lifecycle. It is thus fundamental to improve decision-making and action planning by leveraging the large amount of data available, despite the fact that such data is actually scattered, non-standardized and generally of low quality.

The water sector is undergoing a gradual digital transformation that is affecting the entire water lifecycle, from water sourcing and storage, to distribution, use, treatment and reuse. The level of maturity that the digitalization process has reached throughout the water lifecycle varies from case to case, from simply incorporating sensors into operational procedures to capture relevant data, visualize trends and raise alerts about anomalous trends or events, to sophisticated and data-science-based approaches, data analyses that leverage state-of-the-art Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques, producing predictions/simulations, and supporting automated and optimized operations on the field.

When thinking about digital maturity, it is important to highlight that data-based tools alone can only add a layer of technology that allows for better data collection and increased monitoring. It is their combined and structured use that enables a process of transformation towards the vision of water smartness, where more resilient and sustainable water services are deployed and information is turned from Information technology (IT) applications into data-driven decisions, that help optimize resources (through circularity), minimize climate impacts, and enhance health and safety.

The aim of the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit (in combination with the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit) is to provide a set of complementary tools for enabling and enhancing efficiency for the fundamental steps that have to be followed by subjects that aim to improve their water smartness.

The complementarity of the tools is defined using a high-level process, which is a reference procedural framework for using the toolkits (see Figure 8). The following description defines the reference process that somebody may follow to improve water smartness through the use of digital tools. As a general note, the process is represented as a cycle because water smartness is not a goal (with a finish line), but a trend that has to be improved iteratively.

Figure 8: High-level process for iteratively improving water smartness through digital tools.

The process is composed of two main loops. The main loop includes the fundamental steps that have to be followed to improve water smartness:

- **Context awareness:** the first, strategic step for planning any kind of change process is understanding the state of the system using data-based evidence. Data and information have to be shared among relevant stakeholders as much as possible in order to highlight threats and opportunities, good practices and critical situations. This is the step where the current “as-is” situation is depicted in order to allow decision makers to share a common view of the system and be able to recognize the gaps and the priorities of actions.
- **Decision making:** this step builds on the information collected in the previous one for delivering actual strategic decisions on what to do for improving water smartness. This includes decisions on new investments in technologies or infrastructures, new regulations for fostering CE and Resource Recovery (RR), risk-aware alternative comparisons, etc.
- **Management/monitoring:** implemented actions have to be managed at operational level and their impacts have to be monitored on a regular basis to ensure that decisions are leading to the expected results in terms of water smartness.
- **Certification:** in some cases, the achievements of the change process can be certified with respect to some reference standard. This step is optional but represents a key added value

for those subjects that have a structured and well-defined management plan for their water smartness, ensuring great visibility and credibility of their efforts.

The second loop is focused on advanced analytics for providing detailed evidence in support of the decision-making step. This is a separate loop (nested in the main one) because it may require several iterations, refinements and data exploitations to achieve the necessary results in terms of predictions, simulations, demand/supply match-making and other analysis.

The main loop is supported by **the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit**, whereas the specialized loop for advanced analysis is supported by **the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit**.

Aspects such as management changes or other horizontal matters not strictly related to water smartness are not considered in the reference process.

Table 3 below maps the role of different tools in both toolkits within the steps of the process and provides a brief description of their supporting functionalities.

Table 3: The impact of tools from both toolkits on the steps for improving water smartness.

Step	Tool	Description (how the tool supports this step)
Context awareness	Water reuse strategic platform (#16), enabled by Digital Enabler (#32)	Both platforms can be used for collecting and making available to the relevant stakeholders the heterogeneous information that is scattered across the territory about treated water and sludge and about their potential reuse. This includes any data available in a structured or unstructured format such as: quality and quantity of the product (sludge or water), producers, treatment plants and destinations; characteristics of the territory related to climate, urbanization, industrial plants, cultivated lands, state of soil, regulations at different levels, with information about barriers and drivers. Contextual information is presented through integrated visualizations in a coherent way in order to enable a more effective and data-driven decision process, allowing users to better understand the state of the territory in terms of issues and opportunities for reusing and valorising the available product.
	Sludge management platform (#19), enabled by Digital Enabler (#32)	
	UWC observatory (#20)	The Urban Water Cycle Observatory of Lisbon has the aim to systematise, collect and facilitate access to data on the city water cycle. The system provides access to context data through two different channels: i) open data about urban water and wastewater (main water flows, consumption disaggregation, amount of treated wastewater and reused water production) is provided to citizens and city stakeholders through publicly accessible infographics; ii) entities that have in place a remote water metering can access visualisations about aggregated consumptions and costs per typology of water use, water consumption evolution and individual consumption analysis, leading to an insightful water management, supported by data analytics and automatic performance reports.
	Environmental dashboard (#30)	The Environmental dashboard aims at presenting aggregated data sources (water meters, demographic

Step	Tool	Description (how the tool supports this step)
		data sets) in maps and graphs for providing a picture of water consumption in the different districts of a city.
Advanced analysis	UWOT (#22)	UWOT allows users (water planners, developers and relevant consultants) to compare different water management technologies (including water saving, recycling, treatment and drainage) at different scales. The tool simulates the urban water cycle by modelling individual water uses and technologies and aggregating their combined effects at development scale. UWOT provides a range of technology combinations, which are ranked according to user-based criteria. This allows the user to determine which combination of technologies will be most appropriate or beneficial for their new development.
	Regional demand-supply matching GIS tool (#23)	This is a GIS tool designed for visualizing and processing open-source information on natural water availability and sectorial consumption. Information can be used to identify i) possible consumption hotspots and areas of water shortage, ii) alternative water resources or areas with available water sources and iii) water drain from one region to another region. Based on the analysis, the impacts of alternative water availability scenarios on water demand can be displayed.
	Short-term demand forecasting tool (#28)	The tool is intended to generate water demand forecasts for the next 24 hours. The user can interact with the graphical user interface to train machine learning models and use them to generate and visualize demand forecasts. Furthermore, the user is able to aggregate forecasts for multiple smart meters to achieve the desired spatial resolution.
	QMRA+ for water reuse and agriculture (#26)	Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment (QMRA) is a methodology that can be applied to assess risks of water (re)use and thus support decisions. The QMRA+ tool enables users to estimate the microbial health risk of using various water sources, including reuse of wastewater. A treatment system can be designed by selecting treatment steps from a wide array of possible treatment technologies, resulting in a product water quality. The application can assess the exposure of humans to this product water and the pathogens it may contain.
	SuTra (#31)	SuTRa calculates the subsurface removal of microbial organisms over a distance and with time using an analytical approach. The aim is to allow for a quick assessment of subsurface removal of microbial organisms after subsurface storage.
	Water-energy- phosphorous balance planning module (#25)	This tool is a matchmaking environment where sources and demand points are combined. The supply and demand alternative combinations are assessed through a range of user-selected metrics (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content) over a targeted period.
	Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model (#24)	This tool provides a simulation model for mapping and quantifying risk in reclaimed water distribution networks.
	Risk Assessment for urban water reuse module (#27)	This tool is a human and environmental risk framework dedicated to water demand planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal and water utility contexts.

Step	Tool	Description (how the tool supports this step)
		The tool assesses supply/demand combinations, based on a range of current risk standards and regulations. It works as a risk-related gatekeeper that must be cleared for any supply/demand combination to be considered for assessment in tool #17.
Decision making	Environment for decision support and alternative course selection (#17)	This tool supports water demand planners and decision-makers in urban management to select the best water source combinations to satisfy specific non-potable uses and to prioritize planning options in the governance of water sources and water uses in an urban setting. The tool provides the means to compare supply/demand matchmaking alternatives produced by tool #25 and potentially qualified by tools #24 and #27.
	Re-Actor (#18)	The RE-ACTOR tool aims at supporting water utilities, planners, and decision makers in the evaluation of new investments and actions related to water reuse and water treatment. The tool allows to simulate alternative scenarios in a territory to explore potential impacts related different actuations, such as new processes in a WWTP, installation of renewable technologies or new reclaimed water distribution infrastructure to supply new users with reclaimed water.
Management/ monitoring	Stormwater reuse management system (#21)	The stormwater reuse management system will allow the combination of operational management of a stormwater tank and a connected subirrigation system for groundwater recharge and direct irrigation with the overall objective of reducing water scarcity in spaces or close to urbanised areas. The system includes innovative control concepts to actively manage existing rainwater infrastructures to unlock new applications for otherwise lost rainwater (e.g., agriculture, watering local parks and lawns, industry).
	Nessie system (#29)	The Nessie platform is an information system, able to acquire, process and store, and in general to manage, high-resolution data from IoT agents, such as sensors and smart meters, coupled with analytics and visualisation capabilities to present the information to the end-users. Beyond simple monitoring, possible advanced capabilities for the management of water consumption that could be built upon the tool are: i) the detection of leakages and bursts, ii) the comparison with past consumption data of the household, iii) the comparison with the water consumption of other households with similar socio-demographic characteristics, iv) the analysis of total consumption per appliance, v) the forecast of future consumptions and bills.
Certification	Climate-readiness certification tool (#33)	The climate-readiness certification tool is conceived to support householders, urban planners, the building industry, municipalities, urban planners and Climate Ready Certificates auditors in calculating and emitting the Climate-Ready Certificate (CRC, merging in one certificate the water efficiency, the water-energy nexus performance and the climate adaptation evaluation of households, buildings and neighbourhoods.

The water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit, which is documented in the current report, is comprised of eight tools, which are listed in Table 4 below, along with the LL in which they are applied. Detailed information on each tool is provided in section 5 that follows.

Table 4: Tools of the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit.

#No.	WP3 Tool (leading partners)	Living Lab using the tool
22	UWOT (ICCS/KWR)	Flanders/East Frisia
23	Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS tool (IWW)	East Frisia
24	Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model (BASEFORM)	Lisbon
25	Water-energy-P balance planning module (BASEFORM)	Lisbon
26	QMRA+ (KWR)	Flanders
27	RA-Reuse (BASEFORM)	Lisbon
28	Short-Term Demand Forecasting Tool (IWW)	East Frisia
31	SuTRa (KWR) (former ASR-pro tool)	Flanders

5 The water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit

5.1 Urban Water Optioneering Tool (#22) and water system analysis

5.1.1 Tool description and attributes

The Urban Water Optioneering Tool (UWOT) is a simulation-based Decision Support System (DSS), of the metabolism modelling type, able to simulate the complete urban water cycle by modelling individual water uses and technologies/options (including water saving, recycling, treatment and drainage) for managing them, aggregating them and assessing their combined effects at multiple scales, starting from the household level and progressing up until the neighbourhood, regional and entire city level (Makropoulos, 2017). It provides a range of technology combinations, which are ranked according to user-based criteria. This allows the user to determine which combination of technologies will be most appropriate or beneficial for their new development. UWOT follows a bottom-up, signal-based systems analysis approach that starts from individual components (i.e., in-house appliances, units that use water and generate wastewater or runoff) and proceeds to the generation, transmission, aggregation and transformation of water demand signals that start from the household level and propagate towards the source of water demands, i.e., the central drinking water network (Rozos and Makropoulos, 2013). This demand-oriented conceptualization (see also Figure 9) places household and neighbourhood demand as the starting point of every study and enables UWOT to simulate the whole urban water system from tap to source (Rozos and Makropoulos, 2013). UWOT is able to simulate both standard urban water flows, i.e. potable water, wastewater and runoff, modelled as signals, as well as integrated interventions at household and neighbourhood level, which target these flows in order to create feedback loops that cover household demand; other types of flows that can be modelled through appropriate components are green roofs, blue-green urban areas (Rozos et al., 2013), peri-urban areas, irrigated zones, generic pervious or impervious areas etc. Table 5 presents UWOT's attributes and concise descriptions and will be used for the update of the detailed page of the tool in the Water Europe Marketplace of T7.1, if needed. The detailed page of the tool can be accessed via the following URL: <https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/25>

Figure 9: Modelling the urban water cycle from tap to source using UWOT (Bouziotas et al., 2019)

Table 5: UWOT's attributes and description.

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	A software supporting the Circular Economy. A service, offered as part of a Circular Economy enabling portfolio.
Name	Urban Water Optioneering Tool (#22)
Description	UWOT is a decision-support tool that allows users to compare different water management technologies (including water saving, recycling, treatment and drainage) at different scales. The tool simulates the urban water cycle by modelling individual water uses and technologies and aggregates their combined effects at development scale. UWOT provides a range of technology combinations, which are ranked according to user-based criteria. This allows the user to determine which combination of technologies will be most appropriate or beneficial for their new development.
Abbreviation	UWOT
URL	https://www.watershare.eu/tool/urban-water-optioneering-tool/ ; https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/25 https://uwmh.civil.ntua.gr/products/86-uwot.html
Costs	Software is available for research purposes free of charge upon request on a time limited license. For commercial purposes there are commercial agreement options.
Target audience	UWOT is primarily targeted at water planners, developers and relevant consultants and is designed to be used during: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early and conceptual stage of development, for preliminary design and comparison of different options • Master planning stages of development, to have a holistic system view for the baseline and future (masterplan) scenarios
Actors, roles and interactions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water utilities provide data concerning (waste) water supply and quality characteristics of the inflow (e.g., BOD) • Municipalities provide data related to water demand (for example, for irrigation needs of an examined park) or other information about the area of their responsibility (for example, the area of an examined park)
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bottom-up, component based urban water circle model. • Multiple components, multiple technologies (Drinking water, Wasterwater/Greywater, Rainwater/Runoff) • Able to simulate flows on a daily/hourly time step, in scenarios that span years to decades. • Able to assist smartness in water, by modelling a range of decentralized, distributed interventions: Rainwater harvesting, greywater recycling blue-green areas, smart appliances and estimate water quantity and quality. • Able to assimilate (time-series, parameter) data from multiple sources. • Able to construct scenarios based on socio-economic assumptions. • Supports spatial scales from appliance level and up, house/neighbourhood/city. • Provides links with water and energy, water, and nutrients
TRL	Level 7
Technical requirements	Available as stand-alone software (.exe) in MS Windows environments. Hardware Requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • x86-64 CPU, preferably >= 8GB RAM and 256GB HD Software Requirements:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OS: Windows 10, 8.1, 7, 2008R2, Thin PC as well as Windows Server 2016, 2012, and 2012R2 Dependencies: Microsoft Visual C++ 2010 x64 Redistributable
Environment	Microsoft Windows
Version	v4
Initial release	2008
License type	Software is available for research purposes free of charge upon request on a time limited license. For commercial purposes there are commercial agreement options.
Programming language/technologies used	C, python
Open interface	None
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	Tool has a dedicated GUI to edit and save projects.
Supported spatial scales	Household, neighbourhood, city, region
Supported temporal scales	Hourly, daily and (in aggregation) monthly and annual
Water Use Types	Urban, industrial, rural and agriculture
Compatibility with FIWARE	The tool is not compatible with FIWARE.
Organisations	ICCS/NTUA
Contact details	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Christos Makropoulos (cmakro@mail.ntua.gr) Dimitrios Bouziotas (bouziot@mail.ntua.gr) Stavroula Manouri (stavroula.manouri@gmail.com)
Data Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Christos Makropoulos (cmakro@mail.ntua.gr) Dimitrios Bouziotas (bouziot@mail.ntua.gr) Stavroula Manouri (stavroula.manouri@gmail.com)
Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resource for Circular Economy Water recovery technologies for water reuse Wastewater treatment technologies for water reuse Rainwater harvesting systems. Surface water and infiltration systems Groundwater systems Urban Water buffer
Tags	Circularity, circular economy, climate change, efficiency, energy, innovations, performance, rainwater harvesting, re-use, recycling, sewer mining, sustainability, water management, wastewater, water reuse, wastewater treatment technologies, water storage and recovery

Images	
Caption/Source	Modelling the urban water cycle from tap to source using UWOT (adapted from Makropoulos C. (2017))
Publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bouziotas, D.; van Duuren, D.; van Alphen, H.-J.; Frijns, J.; Nikolopoulos, D.; Makropoulos, C. (2019). Towards Circular Water Neighborhoods: Simulation-Based Decision Support for Integrated Decentralized Urban Water Systems. <i>Water</i> 2019, 11, 1227. https://doi.org/10.3390/w11061227 • Rozos, E., C. Makropoulos, and C. Maksimovic (2013). Rethinking urban areas: an example of an integrated blue-green approach, <i>Water Science and Technology: Water Supply</i>, 13 (6), 1534-1542, https://doi.org/10.2166/ws.2013.140 • Rozos, E., and C. Makropoulos (2013). Source to tap urban water cycle modelling, <i>Environmental Modelling and Software</i>, 41, 139-150, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2012.11.015, Elsevier • Rozos, E., and C. Makropoulos (2012). Assessing the combined benefits of water recycling technologies by modelling the total urban water cycle, <i>Urban Water Journal</i>, 9 (1), https://doi.org/10.1080/1573062X.2011.630096 • Rozos, E., C. Makropoulos, and D. Butler (2010). Design robustness of local water-recycling schemes, <i>Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management - ASCE</i>, 136 (5), 531-538. • Makropoulos, C. (2017). Thinking platforms for smarter urban water systems: fusing technical and socio-economic models and tools. Geological Society, London, Special Publications, 408(1), 201–219. https://doi.org/10.1144/SP408.4 • Makropoulos, C. K., Natsis, K., Liu, S., Mittas, K., and D. Butler (2008). Decision support for sustainable option selection in integrated urban water management, <i>Environ. Modell. Software</i> 23(12), 1448-1460 • Butler, D., Memon, F.A., Makropoulos, C., Southall, A. and Clarke, L. (2010). WaND – Guidance on water cycle management for new developments. C690 CIRIA, London

Within the water system, everything is connected. Interventions within the water system, such as the ones investigated within this project, can affect and be affected by other system components. Water systems analysis can provide information on the interaction between the intervention and the water system and may even aid in decisions regarding that technology.

Specifically for the case of Flanders, two methods that supplement each other are used for the water system analysis. Firstly, UWOT is applied to support pilots in Flanders, with further developments within BWS, followed by a regional water systems analysis that provides broader context at the provincial/catchment scale. The urban water cycle model UWOT is applied in the case of Flanders to support the generalisation and upscaling of the regional pilots and specifically on the regional (local) scale in support of two cases: (a) exploring aspects of the storage basin and water production system

in the city of Woumen, (b) modelling an upscaling of the stormwater retention pond in the area of Mechelen.

Besides the UWOT application, the analysis is expanded by a regional water system analysis (from now on: Regional Analysis) using system dynamics modelling (SDM). This analysis method is under development in a parallel project within the 'Water in the Circular Economy' (WiCE) research program of the Dutch and Flemish drinking water utilities. SDM is used by KWR to analyse regional water flows and to assess the (interacting) effects of interventions and changing circumstances (such as climate change). For this purpose, a generic SDM model is developed and applied to several case studies.

As the tool is still under development and part of an ongoing project, it is not yet publicly available or extensively documented. The models are developed, however, within the publicly available SDM software Vensim (<http://www.vensim.com>), which is free to use for academic and educational purposes. The purpose of the Regional Analysis tool is to assist in the exploration of interactions within regional water systems. Within BWS, it was applied for regional flow analysis, in which interventions (storage, transport and treatment of water) were implemented. Basic understanding of SDM is required to properly use the tool; the proposed end-users are thus experts in the field of water resources management. The Regional Analysis with SDM was complementary to the UWOT study and was assisted by the UWOT data output and findings.

For the East Frisia LL, UWOT tool (#22) is used to simulate the water flows (water demand and supply points) for a test area and to investigate alternative scenarios based on different climatic and demand change conditions or with the implementation of partially decentralised technologies in the area of interest. The outcome of UWOT tool is then incorporated into the Regional Demand-Supply Matching Tool.

5.1.2 Pre-existing background

UWOT has been previously developed and tested in water cycle modelling applications on different spatial scales for a diverse range of cases and demonstrated water management technologies. The range of applications includes neighbourhood-scale blue-green area design (Rozos et al., 2013), whole city cycle modelling (Rozos and Makropoulos, 2013), resilience studies (C. Makropoulos, Nikolopoulos, et al., 2018) and consultancy for circular water neighbourhood (re-)designs (Bouziotas et al., 2019b). Indicative application of combined use of UWOT with sewer mining technology is presented in section 5.1.6.

Regarding the regional (SDM) part of the systems analysis, which was applied in the Flanders' case, the tool has been developed for regional analysis of water systems, building on recent analysis and methods (Pronk et al., 2021).

5.1.3 Developments and advancements within the project

For the purpose of BWS, UWOT is expanded to accommodate the case studies of Flanders and East Frisia in terms of components, extra demand needs, local data assimilation etc. More specifically for Flanders, UWOT topology customizations is investigated for complex processes such as supply through river intake under variable salinity conditions, regional stormwater retention, and demand coverage through subirrigation.

Regarding the regional (SDM) part of the systems analysis, the tool is being developed for application in typical Dutch landscapes. The tool's equations are adapted for the Flemish cases, as the

hydrological characteristics of the Belgian landscapes are not the same as the Dutch ones. Furthermore, the model was applied to explore the interaction between proposed water-smart technologies and the water system, in which sensitivity analyses can provide information on effects under varying circumstances.

For the case study of East Frisia, UWOT components are used to simulate the baseline conditions in a test case and to investigate alternative scenarios. UWOT's outputs (i.e., water demand scenarios outputs) can be used by the Regional Demand-Supply Matching Tool for future-oriented scenarios.

5.1.4 Navigation and primary functionalities

UWOT comes in the form of an executable file (.exe) with its own GUI, where the end user is able to draw topologies, connect different components and perform simulations. The GUI works with Windows 64-bit systems. An example of the tool GUI is provided below (Figure 10).

Figure 10: UWOT's Graphical User Interface (GUI).

The main steps to run a simulation on UWOT are the following (Figure 11):

1. Select the appropriate components to construct a topology.
2. Connect the components to form the examined scenario.

Figure 11: Steps 1 & 2 - Build a topology.

3. After receiving and preparing the input data such as water demand, hydroclimatic time series (to CSV format) etc. for the case study, enter the data and let UWOT check if the data are complete (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Step 3 – Input appropriate data (for example, time series to CSV format).

- Adjust the simulation's options and run the simulation (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Step 4 - Adjust the simulation's options and run the simulation.

- Access the output data from the user interface, visualize or export data to another program or copy the data to the clipboard for further analysis (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Step 5 - Visualize output data.

Similarly, the main steps to build a UWOT topology at a household level, signal-based, from demand nodes to sources, are the following (Figure 15):

1. Add household appliances and group them into different households, mix them together under different households.
2. Include rainwater management and (possibly) greywater recycling components.
3. Log stored water, covered demands, energy requirements at each time step.
4. View results for a specified scenario-topology (set of techs).

Figure 15: Example of UWOT simulation.

5.1.15 Interoperability

UWOT requires standard, headerless CSV files of input, as well as manual input from the user through the GUI. The CSV data required are daily timeseries of water demands, supplied water, rainfall, occupancy, and/or temperature, depending on the components used. Manual input through the GUI is used to set initial conditions (such as initial water levels), as well as other parameters such as treatment

rates and capacity, distribution of water across different sources, etc. Moreover, user interaction with the GUI is needed to view component and system results, in terms of timeseries, in both graphical and tabular format. UWOT saves the topology files as XML files, and exports time series as CSV files, as well as by Windows clipboard copy-pasting (e.g., in MS Excel spreadsheets). No further interoperability with regards to FIWARE is considered. As a tool using third-party data formats (XML/CSV/clipboard and MS Excel) for input and output, the corresponding interoperability maturity level as per D3.1 (section 2.3, Figure 6, p. 25.), is Level 1.

With regards to the regional (SDM) analysis applied in Flanders LL, as the methodology is currently under development and meant for scientific use, interoperability is currently not considered. The user interacts with the SDM through the use of relevant third-party software (Vensim) and saves projects as relevant files.

5.1.6 Indicative applications and synergistic benefits

The range of applications for UWOT has been described in Section 5.1.2, with examples of past projects. Some notable applications of high synergistic benefit include the use of UWOT for the ex-ante assessment or upscaling impact of real circular water pilots, such as a Sewer Mining installation for urban water recycling at the local scale (Makropoulos, Rozos, et al., 2018), or the assessment of the efficiency of decentralized technologies at a neighbourhood-level pilot before its construction (Bouziotas et al., 2019b).

Table 6: Application of UWOT out of the BWS project.

Indicative application of the tool	
Title	Athens demo case
Description	In this case study, UWOT is mainly used to assess the water flows of the sewer mining set-up in the Athens Plant Nursery in Goudi area.
Reference point	https://goo.gl/maps/3pLALyf5Y5ry656P9
Location	Athens Plant Nursery in Goudi area
Country (-ies)	Greece
URL	https://nextgenwater.eu/demonstration-cases/athens/
Project	NextGen
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Scarcity • High or increasing irrigation water demand for urban green spaces. • Need for reuse and recovery schemes for wastewater & sludge.
Tools/Product/Services	UWOT (#22)
Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wastewater treatment technologies for water reuse • Resource for Circular Economy • Water recovery technologies for water reuse

Scales	Local
Legislation	As for the quality of the reclaimed water, SM produces water of a quality that meets all national & the international criteria for unrestricted irrigation and urban use and there is complete elimination of organic carbon and pathogenic content.
Synergistic benefits	Sewer mining unit simulation in UWOT tool.
Requirements and conditions	For the purpose of evaluating the quality of the inflow (BOD concentration), sample testing was carried out over a specific time period (August – October 2018). EYDAP (the water utility in Athens) also provided information regarding the wastewater supply as well as the average daily and annual water usage in the Nursery. Furthermore, monthly time series for rainfall and mean temperature for a specific period of time were acquired through the meteorological station at the National Technical University of Athens campus in Zografou, Greece. The estimation of the water demand was used as an input in UWOT at the pre-processing stage.
Key lessons	In the context of this study, the UWOT is used to assess the water flows of the Sewer Mining set-up in the Nursery. The UWOT simulation shows that SM technology in general is a viable and profitable scheme and can be an interesting alternative water source to cover irrigation needs at the point of demand as well as aquifer recharge during the wet period.
Organisations	NTUA, EYDAP, Chemitec, Municipality of Athens
Contact persons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Christos Makropoulos (cmakro@mail.ntua.gr) (KWR) • Stavroula Manouri (stavroula.manouri@gmail.com) (NTUA)
Data Manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Christos Makropoulos (cmakro@mail.ntua.gr) (KWR) • Stavroula Manouri (stavroula.manouri@gmail.com) (NTUA)
Costs	With regard to the capital cost of the technology in the pilot scale this is about 1,74 euros/m ³ , whereas the operational cost is estimated at 0.5 euros/m ³ .
Tags	Circularity, efficiency, energy, innovations, performance, rainwater harvesting, re-use, recycling, sewer mining, sustainability, water management, wastewater treatment technologies, circular economy, water storage and recovery, etc.
Publications/Reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Liakopoulou, A., Makropoulos, C., Nikolopoulos, D., Monokrousou, K., and Karakatsanis, G. (2020). An urban water simulation model for the design, testing and economic viability assessment of distributed water management systems for a circular economy. <i>Environmental Sciences Proceedings</i>, 2(1), 14. • Plevri, A., Lytras, E., Samios, S., Lioumis, C., Monokrousou, K., and Makropoulos, C. (2020). Sewer Mining as A Basis for Technological, Business and Governance Solutions for Water in the Circular Economy: The NextGen Athens Demo. <i>The 4th EWaS International Conference: Valuing the Water, Carbon, Ecological Footprints of Human Activities</i>, 54. https://doi.org/10.3390/environsciproc2020002054 • Plevri, A., Samios, S., Lytras, E., Papadopoulos, K., Lioumis, C., Lazari, A., Tazes, N., Monokrousou, K., and Makropoulos, C. (2019). Installation of a Sewer Mining Unit in the Athens Urban Tree Nursery. <i>16th International Conference on Environmental Science and Technology</i>. • Plevri, A.; Monokrousou, K.; Makropoulos, C.; Lioumis, C.; Tazes, N.; Lytras, E.; Samios, S.; Katsouras, G.; Tsalas, N. Sewer Mining as a Distributed Intervention

	<p>for Water-Energy-Materials in the Circular Economy Suitable for Dense Urban Environments: A Real-World Demonstration in the City of Athens. <i>Water</i> 2021, <i>13</i>, 2764. https://doi.org/10.3390/w13192764</p>
<p>Images</p>	
<p>Caption/Source</p>	<p>The set-up consisting of a sewer mining unit in UWOT</p>

5.1.7 Accessing tool and test data

Test data and sample tutorials are available in the executable versions of UWOT. Software is available from the Watershare network (<https://www.watershare.eu/>) for research purposes free of charge upon request on a time limited license. For commercial purposes, there are commercial agreement options. Additional information and material can be found in the Water Europe Marketplace (<https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/25>) and the website of the Urban Water Management and Hydroinformatic group (<https://uwmh.civil.ntua.gr/products/86-uwot.html>). Further details on accessing the tool can be provided by Dimitrios Bouziotas (bouziot@mail.ntua.gr).

The BWS training material and the demo time series for the UWOT tool are available at the following link <https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/25> (under the WE Marketplace) and includes:

- An overview presentation of UWOT model introducing the users to its content and role, explaining the way it works and providing results of its application to case studies and insights from past projects,
- A UWOT short guide and FAQ on installation and usage along with the most typical issues and their solutions,
- A UWOT hands-on training presentation and video serving as a step-by-step guide to create a topology and run a simulation using the UWOT model,
- Demo time series of UWOT model in order to perform the hands-on training,
- Video - UWOT hands-on training.

The overview presentation and video are also available via the project's website under the link: <https://b-watersmart.eu/the-urban-water-optioneering-tool/>.

For the regional analysis, the provision of test data and training material is not applicable; the software can be accessed through Vensim software (<https://vensim.com/>).

5.2 Regional demand-supply matching GIS tool (#23)

5.2.1 Tool description and attributes

The Regional Demand-Supply GIS tool (RDSMG) processes open-source information on natural water availability and sectorial consumption. A GIS program (open-source program: QGIS) is used for visualization and processing. In this way, information is bundled and placed in a higher-level context to identify i) possible consumption hotspots and areas with water shortage, ii) alternative water resources or areas with available water sources and iii) water drain from one region to another region. Therefore, different scales and depths of information can be analysed (Figure 16).

In the beginning, we had planned to use the FREEWAT software for its ability to handle large data sets. This is a composite plug-in for the GIS open-source desktop software QGIS (<http://qgis.org>) and was developed in the EU HORIZON2020 project FREEWAT. Since the end of the project, it has become deprecated, and the last stable version is not compatible with current versions of QGIS. Therefore, we decided to set up the tool directly in QGIS as a plug-in. For this reason, the RDSMG tool will stay functional for the foreseeable future (minor version update in QGIS). In addition, by setting it up directly as a plug-in in QGIS, the possibility of interoperability with other QGIS plug-ins is maintained.

Figure 16: Different scales of information.

On the one hand, the tool can help to create awareness regarding the regional limitations of water availability in quantity and quality. In this context, projections show available water sources and water demands for all relevant sectors (domestic, industrial/commercial, agricultural) and the implications of inter-sectorial competition for water in these sectors.

On the other hand, through the targeted integration of all possible water sources, it promotes the use of alternative water resources for processes that do not require drinking water quality. For this purpose,

the sources are described in terms of quantity and quality. More specifically, the user can see all available water sources including details on their proximity, by querying the location in GIS. Based on this analysis, the impacts of alternative water availability scenarios on water demand can be displayed.

Table 7 below includes information about the tool's attributes and descriptions in a tabular format to be used for the update of the detailed page of the tool in the Water Europe Marketplace of T7.1, if needed. The detailed page of the tool can be accessed via the following URL: <https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/35>.

Table 7: Regional demand-supply matching GIS tool's attributes and description.

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A methodology or a process related to the Circular Economy • In addition, a service can be offered to incorporate and evaluate specific local data (non-open source) for a more regionalized analyses or related questions e.g., monitoring or water resource protection
Name	Regional demand-supply matching GIS tool.
Description	Systematic visualization and merging of open-source data (water demand and water sources). Identification of water sources by locations.
Abbreviation	RDSMG
URL	https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/35
Costs	Open source. Costs may relate to a further regionalized study. The amount of costs refers to the scope of the analysis, and work expense e.g., integration of non-commercial data and data evaluation.
Target audience	Water suppliers, public
Actors, roles and interactions	Water utilities: indicate the need of data management.
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	Automatic identification of suitable (alternative) water sources. Visualization of hotspots in water demand and scenarios of water saving.
TRL	Level 7
Technical requirements	No specific requirements
Environment	QGIS (open-source GIS platform)
Version	-
Initial release	2023
License type	free

Programming language/technologies used	Database software (e.g., R Studio, Python version 3.9.5), GIS (program: QGIS version 3.28.5 Firenze)
Open interface	-
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	Data are visualized and processed in open-source GIS program QGIS via the RDSMG plug-in.
Supported spatial scales	Country, federal province, county, region, city.
Supported temporal scales	Annual (for water demand).
Water Use Types	Urban, industry, agriculture (only on county level).
Compatibility with FIWARE	No
Organisations	Open-source development and maintenance by IWW.
Contact details	Katharina Gimbel (k.gimbel@iww-online.de)
Data Manager	Katharina Gimbel (k.gimbel@iww-online.de)
Technologies	In a broader sense: Water recovery technologies for water reuse.
Tags	Water demand, Water resources, Residential, Industrial, Agricultural.
Images	

Caption/Source	Referring respectively to the above figure: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data visualization on different scales (first figure) • Selection of objects depending on the distance to a certain point (second figure)
Publications	Schwesig et al. (2023): Digitale Lösungen für eine wasserbewusste Gesellschaft, Energie Wasser-Praxis, 6+7/2023, pp. 54-59. https://energie-wasser-praxis.de/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/2023_06_06_FB-Schwesig_0607_2023.pdf

5.2.2 Pre-existing background

As the tool was developed from scratch within the scope of the BWS project, there is no pre-existing background to the RDSMG tool.

The data used originates from open-source databases. In this context, data are based on different scales, may differ in availability for different regions or simply may lack GIS references. The most comprehensive data set for German case studies is available for districts (Statistisches Bundesamt) including information about e.g., population, population growth prognosis, per capita consumption, and industrial and agricultural water demand, public and non-public water supply. Information on water resources is given by state offices and may differ in scale as well as depth of information for each state (e.g., numis.niedersachsen.de). For instance, information about groundwater quality is provided for defined groundwater bodies and surface water quality is widely available. Available groundwater quality follows the classification of the European Water Framework Directive (WFD, e.g., umweltkarten-niedersachsen.de). In addition, other nationally available data are used (e.g., CORINE land cover, Census 2011). Grid-based information is available for precipitation (e.g., Deutscher Wetterdienst - DWD).

5.2.3 Developments and advancements within the project

Open-source data has been gathered for the pilot region of Lower Saxony and the association area of OOWV. Data has been – where needed - downscaled and assigned to GIS elements. A systematic scheme has been developed to visualize water demand and sources and identifies areas of high stress. A process has been developed to identify local water resources for a certain water demand in

a certain region defined by the user. The actual RDSMG was implemented in QGIS via a plug-in. It allows the user to select input data, query points and other criteria via a graphical interface.

5.2.4 Navigation and primary functionalities

There are five functionalities of the tool that can be used by the end-user (Figure 17):

- 1) Visualization of data in the viewer mode on different scales:
 - a. Data discretization in dependence of scale.
 - b. Water demands / water sources.
 - c. Heat maps.
- 2) Automated identification of water sources and possible water reuse resources in the vicinity of a defined location (depending on distance). Water quality level can be selected.
- 3) Approximate classification of the financial expenditure for the development of the alternative resource (surface water).
- 4) Display mean annual precipitation data to explore the possibility of using rainwater harvesting as an alternative resource.
- 5) Use of UWOT data for a five-year projection of water demand (depending on availability of UWOT data for the requested point of interest).

Figure 17: Main functionalities of the regional demand-supply matching GIS tool.

5.2.5 Interoperability

Input and output files used for the data are CSV-files. For a convenient query on numerous points of interest, point shape layers are used. For geospatial information shapefiles have been used. The RDSMG tool can optionally process UWOT output data (CSV data). No further interoperability with regards to FIWARE is considered.

5.2.6 Indicative applications and synergistic benefits

Within the BWS project, an interface to the UWOT tool is implemented via the exchange of files in the CSV data format. Small-scale water saving scenarios can be calculated with the UWOT tool, which can then be visualized using the GIS tool.

5.2.7 Accessing tool and test data

The RDSMG tool as well as the example data (collected data) are accessible via the Water Europe Marketplace (<https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/35>) or can be provided by Katharina Gimbel (k.gimbel@iww-online.de).

5.3 Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model (#24)

5.3.1 Tool description and attributes

Tool #24 – *Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model* – is a complete hydraulic and water quality extended-period simulation model for pressure flow networks, designed to simulate the advection, mixing and transformation of waterborne parameters in reused water. It aims primarily at mapping and quantifying risk in reclaimed water distribution networks.

This tool complements Tool #25 in assessing the additional cost, risk and performance changes that may be required in case the supply/demand combinations chosen need to make use of an existing or new distribution network (see overall schematic in Figure 117).

The targeted end users of Tool #24 are hydraulic engineering experts in urban management, municipal and water utility contexts.

The model is deployable at the spatial scale of an urban water distribution network or bulk water network.

This cloud-based tool is developed by BASEFORM using its own proprietary Java-based, web-centric software platform designed for networked infrastructures.

It had a TRL of 3 at the outset of the project and an expected TRL of 7 at the end of the project.

Table 8 below includes information about the tool's attributes and descriptions in a tabular format to be used for the update of the detailed page of the tool in the Water Europe Marketplace of T7.1, if needed. The detailed page of the tool can be accessed via the following URL:

<https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/51>

Table 8: Attributes and description of the reclaimed water distribution network water quality model.

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	A software supporting the Circular Economy
Name	Tool #24 - Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model
Description	<p>A complete hydraulic and water quality extended-period simulation model for pressure flow networks, designed to simulate the advection, mixing and transformation of waterborne parameters in reused water. It aims primarily at mapping and quantifying risk in reclaimed water distribution networks.</p> <p>This tool complements Tool #25 in assessing the additional cost, risk and performance changes introduced in case the supply/demand combinations need to make use of an existing or projected distribution network (see overall schematic presented in Tool #25).</p>
Abbreviation	Not available
URL	https://bwatersmart.baseform.com
Costs	Not available at this stage.
Target audience	Hydraulic engineering experts in urban management, municipal and water utility contexts.
Actors, roles and interactions	This is a specialized model that is best used by hydraulic engineering experts, usually working as part of consultancy in urban management or water utility contexts. It can also be used by the utility staff as part of their operational and engineering tool portfolio.
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	The tool offers a unique standardized means to compare reused water supply/demand combinations through multiple criteria, with a purposefully developed formulation for reused water, on top of advanced hydraulics simulation capabilities.
TRL	7 at end of the project.
Technical requirements	Computer, tablet or smartphone with internet access.
Environment	Any updated internet browser in any operating environment.
Version	Version 2.0

Initial release	2023
License type	Commercial
Programming language/technologies used	Java
Open interface	API, web services, text files, MS Excel files
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	Browser-based graphical user interface.
Supported spatial scales	Neighbourhood, city, region.
Supported temporal scales	Minute, Hour, Day.
Water Use Types	Urban
Compatibility with FIWARE	The model uses BASEFORM's pre-existing internal data model, which is not based on FIWARE. However, it has broad flexibility in terms of data input, being able to read data from any documented file formats, as well as webservices and other common web-accessible supports; and data output, both to files (text, excel and shapefiles/geopkg) and through its own API. Therefore, it can easily accommodate input/output from/to FIWARE-compliant software.
Organisations	BASEFORM
Contact details	Diogo Vitorino (diogo.vitorino@baseform.com)
Data Manager	Diogo Vitorino (diogo.vitorino@baseform.com)
Technologies	Java
Tags	Reuse, water, model, simulation, supply, distribution.

<p>Images</p>	
<p>Caption/Source</p>	<p>Referring respectively to figures above.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection of the color-coded limits for the water quality parameter chosen (BASEFORM). • 3D representation of simulated reused water quality values (BASEFORM).
<p>Publications</p>	<p>Not available</p>

5.3.2 Pre-existing background

BASEFORM software as described in <https://baseform.com/np4/product/>.

5.3.3 Developments and advancements within the project

The model uses previously existing formulations for hydraulics and basic advection, mixing and transformation of parameters in pressurized water distribution networks. The tool implements a new, specific water quality model formulation for reused water, designed within the project. It has been optimised through algorithmic and programming developments for the specific implementation and it uses BASEFORM's geo-based environment and hydraulic simulation framework. The underlying hydraulic and water quality model is based on a complete, specific Java-based implementation that is fully compatible with the EPANET .inp and MSX file formats.

5.3.4 Navigation and primary functionalities

The model runs in BASEFORM's environment as an individual app (see Figure 18). The primary input for the hydraulic model is an EPANET .INP file, and for the water quality an EPANET MSX file. The latter is based on a detailed formulation developed specifically for the project by the LNEC team, which is described in detail in documentation produced by task T2.4.

The model runs based on those two files and the interface allows for querying of results as well as full visualisation in BASEFORM's 3D environment. Some screenshots in the figures below illustrate the software's functionality.

Figure 18: The app's start page displaying some of the model's key parameters and a 2D network schematic. The properties of physical elements such as pipes can be queried by clicking on a pipe. Besides using the Epanet .INP file standard, the model can also be exported to an Excel® format that facilitates section-by-section editing.

Figure 19: Inspecting the distribution of values across the network of a given state variable – in this case, the ‘Quality’ parameter translates the specific formulation developed in BWS for reused water – at a given time step.

Figure 20: Model results on display through the BASEFORM City 3D network interface.

5.3.5 Interoperability

Compatibility with FIWARE is available at read/write level only (through API and/or webservices), as mentioned above on Table 8.

5.3.6 Indicative applications and synergistic benefits

This model is self-contained and, as such, may be used on its own to fulfil its primary purpose. However, in the context of the project, it is intended to be used in conjunction with Tool #25 to qualify the supply/demand alternatives developed there. It aims to assess the risks incurred in transport and distribution of the combination of reused water.

5.3.7 Accessing tool and test data

The tool is part of the set of four tools developed by BASEFORM (#17, #24, #25, #27) for application in the Lisbon Living Lab, where it has been undergoing testing and application to the specific cases being explored in this LL. Sets of test data are available with the software. Real case application data pertaining to the Lisbon Living Lab are available from LNEC.

Accredited users may access the tool at the URL below:

<https://bwatersmart.baseform.com>

For the duration of the project, user credentials should be requested directly from BASEFORM through the following contact point: diogo.vitorino@baseform.com.

5.4 Water-energy-phosphorous balance planning module (#25)

5.4.1 Tool description and attributes

Tool #25 – *Water-energy-phosphorous balance planning* – is a matchmaking environment conceived and designed entirely for BWS, where sources and demand points are combined to enable the design of supply solutions to a set of potential users of reused water.

The supply and demand alternative combinations are assessed and matched through a range of user-selected metrics (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content) over a targeted period. The alternative combinations produced are further made available to Tools #24, #27 and #17 as depicted in Figure 117.

The matchmaking environment is driven by the demand(s) to be satisfied, translated as time series of required monthly volumes over a pre-specified period of time. The user is asked to register potential sources, with corresponding times series of available volumes taking place in the same time window, though not necessarily spanning its entirety.

The user is then asked to combine the available sources to make up the required monthly volumes, while ensuring the energy and nutrient content align with their needs. Such combinations are called ‘alternatives’ and are characterized by the degree to which they satisfy the required volumes over time, as well as by their energy consumption, nutrients contents and cost. One or more alternatives will be designed to solve the demand problem at stake. Figure 117 depicts the logical sequence that ensues after one or more alternatives have been developed, namely the risk assessment stages, before they reach the decision-making environment at Tool #17.

Tool #25's key development period took place between months M18 and M24, with initial Lisbon LL testing release delivered at M26 and the initial project release in M30 as scheduled.

The tool's targeted end users are planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal and water utility contexts.

The tool is deployable at any spatial scale as it applies to any supply/demand context, but indicative scales are city facility (e.g., public park), neighbourhood, city, region. The software allows for full geographic representation of the sources and demands (screenshots below in Table 9).

The tool is developed by BASEFORM using its own proprietary Java-based, web-centric software platform designed for networked infrastructures.

The tool has a TRL of 3 at the outset of the project and an expected TRL of 7 at the end of the project.

Table 9 below includes information about the tool's attributes and descriptions in a tabular format to be used for the update of the detailed page of the tool in the Water Europe Marketplace of T7.1, if needed. The detailed page of the tool can be accessed via the following URL:

<https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/55>

Table 9: Attributes and description of the water-energy- phosphorous balance planning module.

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	A software supporting the Circular Economy.
Name	Tool #25 - Water-energy-phosphorous balance planning module.
Description	A matchmaking environment where sources and demand points are combined. The supply and demand alternative combinations are assessed through a range of user-selected metrics (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content) over a targeted period.
Abbreviation	Not available
URL	https://bwatersmart.baseform.com .
Costs	Not available at this stage.
Target audience	Water demand planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal and water utility contexts.
Actors, roles and interactions	The tools' central use case is in an internal or external expert consultancy role. The targeted user has access to municipal or regional data on water production and water demand (volumes, costs, energy content, nutrient content), or is equipped to estimate those data in an engineering/planning context.
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	Standardized means to combine and assess reused water source combinations to satisfy specific demands.

TRL	7 at end of project.
Technical requirements	Computer, tablet or smartphone with internet access.
Environment	Any updated internet browser in any operating environment.
Version	Version 1.0
Initial release	2023
License type	Commercial
Programming language/technologies used	Java
Open interface	API, web services
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	Browser-based graphical user interface.
Supported spatial scales	Urban facility (e.g., public park), neighbourhood, city, region.
Supported temporal scales	Monthly, annual
Water Use Types	Urban
Compatibility with FIWARE	The tool uses BASEFORM's pre-existing internal data model, which is not based on FIWARE. However, it has broad flexibility in terms of data input, being able to read data from any documented file formats, as well as webservices and other common web-accessible supports; and data output, both to files (text, excel and shapefiles/geopkg) and through its own API. Therefore, it can easily accommodate input/output from/to FIWARE-compliant software.
Organizations	BASEFORM
Contact details	Diogo Vitorino (diogo.vitorino@baseform.com)
Data Manager	Diogo Vitorino (diogo.vitorino@baseform.com)
Technologies	Java
Tags	Reuse, water, supply, demand.

<p>Images</p>	
<p>Caption/Source</p>	<p>The above figures are screenshots that depict, respectively:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The list of matchmaking alternatives available for a given analysis • Specifying a reused water demand point in the matchmaking environment (BASEFORM). <p>The software is available at https://bwatersmart.baseform.com.</p>
<p>Publications</p>	<p>Not available</p>

5.4.2 Pre-existing background

BASEFORM software as described in <https://baseform.com/np4/product/>.

5.4.3 Developments and advancements within the project

The tool is conceived and developed from scratch by BASEFORM within the project, based on the concept created by the LNEC team in task T2.4, and developed jointly with BASEFORM for implementation. It builds upon and benefits from BASEFORM's pre-existing online client-server environment, input/output capabilities, file system and geo-referenced environment for water infrastructures, as well as its graphical user interface.

The tool constitutes a new autonomous module within the BASEFORM environment, which may be deployed on its own as a stand-alone app or in conjunction with the remaining tools (#17, #24, #27) as per the schematic in Figure 117.

5.4.4 Navigation and primary functionalities

The figures below depict the logical navigation sequence across the tool's key functionality. Figure 21 depicts the GUI when the app is started. It displays the available analyses as well as the option to create a new one (top right). An analysis contains one or more matchmaking alternatives for a given supply/demand application case, as well as a set of metrics and a range of analysis timesteps.

Figure 21: GUI when the app is launched.

Figure 22 presents the app's main screen, showing the Supplies tab, which lists all available supply sources registered for the given case. New supply sources may be registered at the top right.

Figure 22: The app's main screen.

While creating or editing a supply source users need to specify its geographical position and add files with time series for water volume available, cost and phosphorus content (Figure 23 and Figure 24).

EDIT ENTITY

Type: RECLAIMED_WATER

Name: Água para reutilização (ApR)

Utility name: AdTA - Águas do Tejo Atlântico

Water loss ratio (%): 10.0

Notes: Notes #1 Water quality: Class A (DL 119/2019), threshold values: E. coli, 10 cfu/100 mL; BOD5, 10 mgO2/L; TSS, 10 mg/L; Turbidity, 5 NTU. Water volume: Reclaimed water potentiallv available IISO

Geometry (lat long): MULTIPOINT (-9.16639593681191 38.73647450194...)

Files:

SERIES: WATER

Period 2023 Jan - 2027 Dec

monthly	150,000 m ³
yearly	1.8 x 10 ⁶ m ³
total	9 x 10 ⁹ m ³

The available volume of ApR is estimated from the capacity of the water main pipe that will carry the reclaimed water from the Alcântara WWTP to the Campolide area. A 500 mm diameter pipeline was considered. Total monthly flow of ApR potentially available: 408.240 m3. This pipeline is expected to come into service in January 2025.

SERIES: COST

Figure 23: Creating or editing a supply source.

Figure 24: Creating or editing a supply source, showing the time series for cost and phosphorus content.

Figure 25 presents the demands tab, which lists all the demands registered for the given case, which will drive the analysis. New demands may be registered at the top right.

Figure 25: The Demands tab.

The below figure (Figure 26) depicts the Matchmaking tab, displaying the matchmaking supply/demand alternatives developed for the current analysis, along with their key metrics. New alternatives may be created at the top right.

Figure 26: The Matchmaking tab.

Figure 27 presents the GUI where users can create or edit a matchmaking alternative, showing investment cost, energy price, unit cost and the indicators' values on the left, as well as the risk score, calculated via the linked Tool #27. The various demands to be satisfied in this case are listed, together with key metrics and their completion % (green field on top right of each demand entry). In Figure 28 the values of the base variables used in the calculation is displayed.

Matchmaking Alternative - 1 - Easy ...

baseform Sérgio Coelho

DEMAND SATISFACTION

Name 1 - Easy win

Investment cost 10,000 €/year

Energy price 0.22 €/kWh

Unit cost with c... 0 €/m³

Description Deixar de usar água potável nos locais de maior consumo (aproveitar efeito de escala), aproveitando infraestruturação em curso/planeada para a cidade --> objetivo: reduzir em pelo menos 25% o consumo de água potável

Risk level LOW

INDICATORS

Satisfied demand (%)	100
Reclaimed water used (%)	0
Reclaimed water use vs availability (%)	0
Energy consumption (kWh/m ³)	0.426
Carbon footprint of energy consumption (kg CO ₂ eq./m ³)	0.106
P-fertilizer production avoided (%)	0
OPEX (€/m ³)	1.006
CAPEX (€/m ³)	45.53 x 10 ⁻³
Total cost (€/m ³)	1.052

VARIABLES

EXPORT

Jardim Amalia Rodrigues GARDEN 100.0

Water cost	188,463 €	Avg. volume	58,894 m ³ /year
Energy cost	25,913 €	Satisfied	294,474 m ³
Carbon footprint	29,447 kg CO ₂	Água não potável	100 %
Phosphorus	0 kg		

Parque Eduardo VII PARK 100.0

Water cost	429,875 €	Avg. volume	136,841 m ³ /year
Energy cost	59,504 €	Satisfied	684,207 m ³
Carbon footprint	67,619 kg CO ₂	Poço Estufa Fria	2.343 %
Phosphorus	0 kg	Água não potável	97.65 %

Jardim da Amnistia Internacional GARDEN 100.0

Water cost	247,247 €	Avg. volume	23,901 m ³ /year
Energy cost	17,494 €	Satisfied	119,505 m ³
Carbon footprint	19,879 kg CO ₂	Água potável	100 %
Phosphorus	0 kg		

Figure 27: Creating or editing a matchmaking alternative.

Figure 28: Creating or editing a matchmaking alternative, displaying the values of the base variables used in the calculation.

Figure 29 presents the editing screen for each demand to be satisfied, showing the combination of supplies used, whereas Figure 30 shows the Map tab which provides a complete mapping environment to geographically display the registered supplies and demands. A variety of mapping layers are available.

Investment cost 10,000 €/year

EDIT

LINKED SUPPLIES **ADD...**

MONTH	DEMAND M3	SATISFIED M3	ÁGUA NÃO POTÁVEL USED / AVAILABLE - M3
2023/01	2,064.88	2,064 (100.0%)	2,064 / 33,339
2023/02	2,483.43	2,483 (100.0%)	2,483 / 35,266
2023/03	2,372.63	2,372 (100.0%)	2,372 / 36,700
2023/04	2,451.35	2,451 (100.0%)	2,451 / 36,597
2023/05	5,298.39	5,298 (100.0%)	5,298 / 31,207
2023/06	4,836.65	4,836 (100.0%)	4,836 / 23,857
2023/07	6,659.42	6,659 (100.0%)	6,659 / 16,211
2023/08	10,962.82	10,962 (100.0%)	10,962 / 5,809
2023/09	9,398.49	9,398 (100.0%)	9,398 / 11,046
2023/10	4,152.1	4,152 (100.0%)	4,152 / 26,272
2023/11	3,988.24	3,988 (100.0%)	3,988 / 29,496
2023/12	4,226.49	4,226 (100.0%)	4,226 / 31,136
2024/01	2,064.88	2,064 (100.0%)	2,064 / 33,339
2024/02	2,483.43	2,483 (100.0%)	2,483 / 35,266
2024/03	2,372.63	2,372 (100.0%)	2,372 / 36,700
2024/04	2,451.35	2,451 (100.0%)	2,451 / 36,597
2024/05	5,298.39	5,298 (100.0%)	5,298 / 31,207
2024/06	4,836.65	4,836 (100.0%)	4,836 / 23,857

LINKED SUPPLIES

Água não potável
Energy Cost (kWh/m3)
0.4
Local energy mix (kgCO2eq/kWh)
0.25

Figure 29: The editing screen for each demand to be satisfied, showing the combination of supplies used.

Figure 30: The Map tab.

5.4.5 Interoperability

Compatibility with FIWARE is available at read/write level only (through API and/or webservice), as mentioned above in Table 9.

5.4.6 Indicative applications and synergistic benefits

As mentioned above, Tool #25 is autonomous and may be deployed on its own, or in conjunction with the remaining tools (#17, #24, #27) as per the schematic in Figure 117. The primary goal is described in 5.4.1. Conceivably, the tool is applicable to any demand-driven matchmaking problem without requiring modification.

5.4.7 Accessing tool and test data

The tool is part of the set of four tools developed by BASEFORM (#17, #24, #25, #27) for application in the Lisbon Living Lab, where it has been undergoing testing and application to the specific cases being explored in this LL. Sets of test data are available with the software. Real case application data pertaining to the Lisbon Living Lab are available from LNEC and CML.

Accredited users may access the tool at the URL below:

<https://bwatersmart.baseform.com>

For the duration of the project, user credentials should be requested directly from BASEFORM through the following contact point: diogo.vitorino@baseform.com.

5.5 QMRA+ for water reuse and agriculture (#26)

5.5.1 Tool description and attributes

Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment (QMRA) is a methodology that can be applied to assess risks of water (re)use and thus support decisions. The QMRA tool enables users to estimate the microbial health risk of using various water sources, including reuse of wastewater. A treatment system can be designed by selecting treatment steps from a wide array of possible treatment technologies. These treatment trains result in a product water quality for which the application can be selected to assess the exposure of humans to this product water and the pathogens it may contain. A calculation is performed according to the QMRA approach that involves the estimation of infection risk per person per year and the DALYs (disability-adjusted life years) per person and year for bacteria (*Campylobacter jejuni*), viruses (rotavirus) and protozoa (*Cryptosporidium*). Most other QMRA tools, e.g. QMRAspot (<https://www.rivm.nl/en/who-collaborating-centre-risk-assessment-of-pathogens-in-food-and-water/tools/qmraspot>), require users to enter microbial monitoring data from the source and treatment system or data that users need to obtain from literature (DPRisk, <https://cawaterdatadive.shinyapps.io/DPRisk/>). These tools also require some training to adequately use the tools. The QMRA+ tool has an easy-to-use web interface with explanations of the required input and how the tool operates and does not require data from the user as data on source water quality and water treatment efficacy from literature is incorporated in the tool. Therefore, the user can start a basic risk assessment using these default values. If the user has more specific data for their system, they can adapt these default values to make the tool more site-specific and accurate.

Objectives:

The tool was designed for users with no or limited experience and knowledge of QMRA, but also provides an effective tool for QMRA experts. It can be used for screening level QMRA to compare different scenarios or water system designs. The tool can also be used for education and training purposes since it's very user friendly and provides help and background information when used. With the basic functionality, generic reference values are provided for all inputs. The outcome should therefore be considered a first estimate of risk but cannot be interpreted as actual compliance to a risk target of a specific system. Since contamination of sources and performance of individual water treatment systems can vary, location specific data is required to reach a realistic risk estimate for a specific system. Users with sufficient QMRA knowledge can use the more advanced features of the tool to adapt the generic input data to locally relevant data on pathogens in water sources, treatment efficacy and exposure through various uses.

History:

The tool was initially developed in the H2020 AquaNES project by KWR and KWB, based on previous work and QMRA tools. The goal was to make QMRA more easily accessible. Within BWS the tool was improved, and new features were added. Technical improvement included alteration of the risk calculation and bug fixing to increase the stability of the tool. Added features include additional water treatment processes and advanced options to adapt input parameters based on user data.

End users:

The target audience for the tool are risk managers of water systems and their stakeholders. The tool can provide a common basis for all stakeholders involved in system selection and design as it allows both experienced and inexperienced users to explore various scenarios and options. It provides a mean to introduce, educate and train QMRA principles to students, operators, engineers and regulators.

Scale:

The tool is targeted at professional water supply systems. The input data is based on professionally designed and operated systems, ranging from small to large systems. Application to neighbourhood or household scale needs careful consideration since the performance, monitoring and management of such small-scale systems can deviate from those of large systems. A user with sufficient knowledge may adapt the standard input values accordingly.

Water use types:

The tool is aimed at water uses that result in direct ingestion of various water uses, including unintended use. Examples are drinking water, irrigation, toilet flushing etc. Specific uses may require adaptation of the frequency and amount of ingestion based on user data.

Developer:

The initial calculation software was developed by KWB in the DEMOWARE project. The initial user interface was developed by KWR within the AquaNES project. Both institutes worked together to develop the final tool. The QMRA+ version was developed by KWR in the BWS project.

Environment:

The tool is web-based. It can be used through popular internet browsers without the need for any downloading of software. The original calculation was developed in R. Functions were programmed in R and integrated in the open-source R-package `kwb.qmra` (v0.2.0) accessible through GitHub (<https://github.com/kwb-r/kwb.qmra>) under the permissive MIT li-cense (<https://github.com/KWB-R/kwb.qmra/blob/master/LICENSE>) and documented under the following link: <https://kwb-r.github.io/kwb.qmra/>. The webtool and GUI were developed in Java on the server side. JavaScript, HTML, CSS are used on the client side.

License:

The webtool is publicly available with the disclaimer that the developers are not responsible for any consequences arising from its use. The original R-code for the tool is accessible through GitHub (<https://github.com/kwb-r/kwb.qmra>) under the permissive MIT license. The R-code doesn't include all functionality of the webtool.

URL:

The tool can be found here: <https://tinyurl.com/QMRAplus>. Users can login to the tool and store system designs for future sessions.

The below table (Table 10) collects the above information about tool's attributes and descriptions in a tabular format to be used for the update (if needed) of the detailed page of the tool in the Water Europe Marketplace of T7.1. The detailed page of the tool can be accessed via the following URL: <https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/56>.

Table 10: QMRA+ tool's attributes and description

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A software supporting the Circular Economy • A methodology or a process related with the Circular Economy
Name	QMRA+ tool
Description	Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment (QMRA) is a methodology that can be applied to assess risks of water (re)use and thus support decisions. The QMRA tool enables users to estimate the microbial health risk of using various water sources, including reuse of wastewater. A treatment system can be designed by selecting treatment steps from a wide array of possible treatment technologies. These treatment trains result in a product water quality for which the application can be selected to assess the exposure of humans to this product water and the pathogens it may contain. A calculation is performed according to the QMRA approach that involves the estimation of infection risk per person per year and the DALYs (disability-adjusted life years) per person and year for bacteria (<i>Campylobacter jejuni</i>), viruses (rotavirus) and protozoa (<i>Cryptosporidium</i>).
Abbreviation	QMRA+
URL	https://tinyurl.com/QMRaplus
Costs	The webtool is freely available.
Target audience	Risk managers, regulators, inspectorates, engineers, stakeholders of water systems (to support discussions), students and water professionals.
Actors, roles and interactions	The tool can be used by individuals to perform risk assessments. The tool can be used for QMRA introduction, education, training. The tool can be used by teams to support discussions and decisions on water system development.
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	The tool is very user friendly compared to other available QMRA tools (e.g., QMRAspot). It is very flexible allowing a wide range of water sources, treatment processes and uses. No user data is required for the basic functionality, however advanced users can adapt input parameters based on their own data.
TRL	7
Technical requirements	The tool can be used through any popular internet browser and doesn't require downloads or computer capacity.

Environment	Web-based
Version	V 0.9.7 alpha
Initial release	2019
License type	Free
Programming language/technologies used	Calculations: R GUI: Java
Open interface	NA
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	GUI web-based
Supported spatial scales	Professionally operated water systems at city level. Knowledgeable users can adapt input parameters to their specific situation by entering data on local water quality, treatment monitoring and use. The tool is not suitable for smaller neighbourhood, industrial or household scale systems since their performance, monitoring and maintenance can deviate from large scale systems run by professionals.
Supported temporal scales	Risks are typically expressed on an annual basis. Daily risk estimates are also provided.
Water Use Types	Drinking, irrigation, toilet flushing and various other uses. Exposure for other use types can be added by experienced users by adapting input parameters.
Compatibility with FIWARE	Not FIWARE compatible.
Organisations	KWR, KWB.
Contact details	Patrick Smeets, KWR (Patrick.smeets@kwrwater.nl)
Data Manager	Patrick Smeets, KWR (Patrick.smeets@kwrwater.nl)
Technologies	Water recovery technologies for water reuse: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wastewater treatment technologies for water reuse. • Rainwater harvesting systems. • Surface water and infiltration systems. • Groundwater systems.
Tags	QMRA, health risk assessment, microbiology, pathogens, infection risk, DALY.

<p>Images</p>	
<p>Caption/Source</p>	<p>Screenshot of the QMRA+ tool risk calculation results.</p>
<p>Publications</p>	<p>Smeets, P. W. M. H., and Miehe, U. (2019, 16 – 20 June). AquaNES QMRA tool: a webtool for quantitative microbial risk assessment of water reuse applications. Paper presented at the 12th IWA International Conference on Water Reclamation and Reuse, Berlin, Germany.</p>

5.5.2 Pre-existing background

The initial calculation software was developed by KWB in the DEMOWARE project. The initial user interface was developed by KWR within the AquaNES project. Both institutes worked together to develop the final tool. The QMRA+ version was developed by KWR in the BWS project.

5.5.3 Developments and advancements within the project

Within BWS the tool was improved, and new features were added. Technical improvements included alteration of the risk calculation and bug fixing to increase the stability of the tool. Added features include additional water treatment processes and advanced options to adapt input parameters based on user data.

The concentration of pathogens in various types of source water, such as sewage, treated sewage, grey water, rivers and groundwater, is suggested by the tool. However, these concentrations can vary significantly between various locations due to the local conditions. Factors such as the level of dilution, number of people impacting the water source, treatment processes in place and the skill of operation can all affect the number of pathogenic micro-organisms in the water. Therefore, an additional feature was added where the user can adapt these concentrations used by the tool based on local monitoring of the source or other information. The minimum and maximum concentrations can be added to resemble the variability of concentrations in the source (Figure 31). These adaptations are the responsibility of the user. The tool cannot check the validity of entered data.

	Min	Max
Bacteria	0.001	1000
Virus	0.1	1000
Protozoa	0.01	10000

Buttons: Get Default Values, Save, Cancel

Figure 31: Screenshot of added feature to enter local pathogen concentration data or estimates for the risk calculation.

Similarly, the tool provides suggestions for pathogen removal by various treatment processes based on available literature. For most processes the reported efficacy varies among studies as they depend on local conditions, treatment design and skill of operation. Since this can range over multiple orders of magnitude, this information is an important source of uncertainty. Users can gain more insight into their own systems by monitoring surrogate organisms before and after treatment that provide validation of the actual treatment performance. More extensive monitoring will lead to a reduction of this uncertainty. Therefore, the user can enter the monitored removal, its standard deviation and the number of measurements this is based on (Figure 32). This is then used in the stochastic risk modelling.

Input of monitoring data for :
1. Membrane filtration

	Mean	StDev	N
Bacteria			
Influent	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Effluent	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Virus			
Influent	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Effluent	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Protozoa			
Influent	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Effluent	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Save **Cancel**

Figure 32: Screenshot of added feature to enter local treatment monitoring data for the risk calculation.

The microbial health risk also depends on the amount of water ingested through various uses. The tool has several types of uses built in such as irrigation, car washing, toilet flushing and drinking. The ingestion is described by the amount of water ingested per use or day and the number of events per year that this use takes place. The amount of water ingested is greatly impacted by the way a person uses the water and the equipment used. There can be very large differences in types of equipment and habits between regions or groups of people. Therefore, the tool allows users to adapt both the volume of water ingested and the frequency of use (Figure 33).

Change values of :
Irrigation, Unrestricted

Water Use Events Per Year	<input type="text" value="70"/>
Water Use per Event (liter)	<input type="text" value="0.005"/>

Get Default Values **Save** **Cancel**

Figure 33: Screenshot of added feature to enter local water use frequency and ingested volume during use for the risk calculation.

5.5.4 Navigation and primary functionalities

The tool consists of the following steps:

Login:

When a user returns to the tool, previous stored work is available. A user can define multiple water use scenarios, e.g., to compare various options for designing new systems (Figure 34).

Figure 34: Screenshot of risk assessment name entry and additional description field.

Water source:

The user can select a type of water source (river, sewage, effluent etc.) and name it. The provided pathogen concentrations can be adapted by knowledgeable users (Figure 32). Instructions: *Select the water source used in the system for which you want to assess the risk. The range of expected concentrations of pathogenic micro-organisms is then displayed under Pathogens. This range will be used in the risk assessment. The ranges are based on guidelines and references, which will be displayed on the Summary page. The 'i' button displays an introduction for each pathogen group and the index pathogen for which the risk is calculated* (Figure 35).

Figure 35: Screenshot of Water source selection and the microbial quality suggested. Hoovering over the information icon provides background on the specific organism for the user.

Treatment:

The user can drag and drop various treatment processes to develop a treatment train. Knowledgeable users can adapt treatment efficacy values (log reduction values) based on their specific data or other knowledge (Figure 36). Support for data interpretation is provided (Figure 36).

Instructions on screen:

- *Drag the treatment processes that are used into an empty box in the process scheme field.*
- *To delete a box click 'x,'.*
- *To add a box click '+' or drag and drop boxes to change the order.*
- *Point at the selected process to display a brief introduction.*
- *The range of log removal of each pathogen group by this process is shown. These log removals are used in the risk calculation.*
- *The references for the log removal values are provided on the summary page.*
- *If you have monitoring data for your processes, add the process here and then adapt the log removal values by clicking the pencil.*

No.	Process Order	Log Removal
1.	Conventional clarification	Bacteria Minimum: 0.2, Maximum: 2.0, Distribution: uniform Viruses Minimum: 0.1, Maximum: 3.4, Distribution: uniform Protozoa Minimum: 1.0, Maximum: 2.0, Distribution: uniform
2.	Granular high-rate filtration	Bacteria Minimum: 0.2, Maximum: 4.4, Distribution: uniform Viruses Minimum: 0.0, Maximum: 3.5, Distribution: uniform Protozoa Minimum: 0.4, Maximum: 3.3, Distribution: uniform
3.	Membrane filtration	Bacteria Minimum: 3.5, Maximum: 6.0, Distribution: uniform Viruses Minimum: 2.5, Maximum: 6.0, Distribution: uniform Protozoa Minimum: 6.0, Maximum: 6.0, Distribution: uniform
4.		

Figure 36: Screenshot of Treatment train selection and the microbial reduction efficacy suggested. Hoovering over the process block provides background on the specific process for the user.

Use:

The user can define a water use (drinking, irrigation, toilet flushing etc.) which is characterised by frequency per year and amount of water ingested (Figure 37). Knowledgeable users can adapt input values to represent their specific situation.

Instructions on screen:

- *Select the intended water use.*
- *If multiple uses are considered, select the one with the highest exposure. 2*

- The exposure of the chosen water use is shown as the number of times the water is used this way and the amount of water that is ingested each time.
- Literature reference for the selected data is shown on the summary page.

Figure 37: Screenshot of Water use selection and the corresponding volume ingested and frequency of use.

Summary:

Overview of the user input and background on the scientific sources for the input values of all QMRA steps (Figure 38). This overview can be printed or stored. After checking the input, the user can start the calculation by clicking that button.

Sewage, Treated	Bacteria
Pathogen	Campylobacter jejuni
Minimum Concentration	0.001
Maximum Concentration	1000.0
Distribution Shape	log10_norm
Reference	WHO (2006) safe use wastewater V2

Figure 38: Screenshot of a detail from the overview of selected inputs, including the data sources used for default values in the tool.

Exposure risk:

Overview of the risk calculation consisting of three parts (Figure 39): i) Textual evaluation of the calculated risk versus risk targets expressed as annual risk of infection or Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALY) for viruses, bacteria and protozoa, ii) Graphical representation of risk estimation including the uncertainty and variability of risk in boxplots, iii) Table representation of calculated risks including percentiles. The user can store or print the results.

Summary of Result

The risk of this scenario can be compared to two commonly applied health based targets (WHO GDWQ 2011):

1 in 10,000 Annual risk of infection or

0.000001 Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALY)

The estimated risk of infection exceeds the health target of 1 infection per 10,000 people per year for Virus

The estimated health risk exceeds the health target of 1 microDALY per person per year for Virus

Figure 39: Screenshots of the output of the calculated risk as risk of infection in textual and graphical form.

Table 11: Screenshot of the output of the calculated risk both as risk of infection in tabular form.

Data	Number/log10	Mean	5%	50%	95%
Source Concentration	N/I	1.25	0.34	1.03	2.89
Conventional clarification	log10	1.1	0.29	1.1	1.91
Granular high-rate filtration	log10	2.3	0.41	2.3	4.19
Membrane filtration	log10	4.75	3.63	4.75	5.88
Total Treatment	log10	8.14	7.74	8.14	8.58
DALY per Year	/person/year	8.06E-9	3.04E-11	3.94E-10	2.46E-8
Exposure per Year	number/person/year	2.96E-4	1.12E-6	1.44E-5	9.03E-4
Infection Risk per Year	/person/year	5.84E-6	2.2E-8	2.86E-7	1.79E-5
Ingestion per Event	litter/event	0.005	0.005	0.005	0.005
Events per year	number/year	70	70	70	70

5.5.5 Interoperability

The tool is not interoperable with other tools in the project and is therefore at FIWARE maturity level 0, (see D3.1 for definitions of maturity levels, section 2.3, Figure 6, p. 25). However, this maturity level follows from the goal of the tool and the characteristics of the user input. The data is included in the tool and the user only needs to make selections. As the tool is designed to explore and compare various water(re)use scenarios, there is no data input needed by the user. The tool doesn't need real time data input for the risk calculation. Location specific monitoring data is generally scarce since monitoring programs for micro-organisms are very costly, especially for pathogens. Depending on the methods and the approach used, the data needs expert interpretation before it can be summarized for the tool. Since this will vary case by case a standard approach could not be developed within the tool.

5.5.6 Indicative applications and synergistic benefits

See section 5.5.1 for intended uses. The tool has been used within BWS to evaluate various design and treatment options for the Flanders drinking water case. Variables were the point of entry of the (upgraded) sewage treatment effluent and various water treatment options for the effluent and/or adaptation of the existing drinking water treatment system. The tool provided a good means to introduce the QMRA methodology to the various project participants. Participants could use the tool to explore other alternatives themselves, thus demonstrating the impact of various design options on health risk.

The tool has also been used in education to introduce MSc students at Utrecht University to the QMRA methodology.

5.5.7 Accessing tool and test data

The tool is accessible at: <https://tinyurl.com/QMRAplus>. No test data is available since data selections are made within the tool. The tool has been tested for the available input data.

5.6 Risk Assessment for urban water reuse module (#27)

5.6.1 Tool description and attributes

Tool #27 – *Risk Assessment for urban water reuse* – is a risk assessment framework that evaluates human and environmental risks incurred by the supply/demand combinations developed in Tool #25. These evaluations are based on a range of current risk standards and regulations including:

- ISO 16075 Guidelines for treated wastewater use for irrigation projects (2020, 2021),
- ISO 20426:2018 Guidelines for health risk assessment and management for non-potable water reuse,
- ISO 20761:2018 Guidelines for water reuse safety evaluation,
- EU Regulation 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse.

The tool works in combination with Tool #25 following the workflow presented in Figure 117 and the description included in the introduction to Tool #17² documented in D3.4. It works as a risk-based gatekeeper that must be cleared for any supply/demand combination to be considered for assessment in Tool #17. Each alternative tested for human risk and for environmental risk undergoes a sequence of steps to translate the aforementioned standards and receives a risk grade. Depending on the targeted risk level, the alternative will either be rejected (and potentially returned to tool #25 for redesign) or approved and forwarded to Tool #17. The tool is functionally linked to Tool #25, which is aware of the alternative's risk score, if available (see e.g., Figure 27).

The targeted end users of Tool #27 are water demand planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal and water utility contexts. Tool #27 is deployable at any spatial scale as it applies to any supply/demand context, but indicative scales are city facility (e.g., public park), neighbourhood, city and region. It has been developed by BASEFORM using its own proprietary Java-based, web-centric software platform designed for networked infrastructures. The TRL level of the tool was 2 at the outset of the project, whereas the ending TRL level is 7. Table 12 below includes information about the tool's attributes and descriptions in a tabular format to be used for the update of the detailed page of the tool in the Water Europe Marketplace of T7.1, if needed. The detailed page of the tool can be accessed via the following URL:

<https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/67>

² Tool #17 – *Environment for decision support and alternative course selection* – is a multi-criteria decision framework designed to enable direct assessment, comparison and prioritization of decisional alternatives. Detailed descriptions about the tool are available in D3.4.

Table 12: Attributes and description of the Risk Assessment for urban water reuse module.

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	A software supporting the Circular Economy
Name	Tool #27-- Risk Assessment for urban water reuse module
Description	<p>A human and environmental risk framework that assesses supply/demand combinations, based on a range of current risk standards and regulations including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO 16075 Guidelines for treated wastewater use for irrigation projects (2020, 2021), • ISO 20426:2018 Guidelines for health risk assessment and management for non-potable water reuse, • ISO 20761:2018 Guidelines for water reuse safety evaluation, • EU Regulation 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse.
Abbreviation	NA.
URL	https://bwatersmart.baseform.com
Costs	Not available at this stage.
Target audience	Water demand planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal and water utility contexts.
Actors, roles and interactions	Working in tandem with Tool #25, this tool has a similar central use case based on an internal or external expert consultancy role. The targeted user has knowledge of the risk assessment guidelines mentioned above (5.6.1); usage of the tool may imply access to municipal or regional data on water production and water demand (volumes, costs, energy content, nutrient content), or is equipped to estimate those data in an engineering/planning context.
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	Standardized means to combine and assess reused water source combinations to satisfy specific demands.
TRL	7 at end of project.
Technical requirements	Computer, tablet or smartphone with internet access.
Environment	Any updated internet browser in any operating environment.
Version	Version 1.0

Initial release	2023
License type	Commercial
Programming language/technologies used	Java
Open interface	API, web services.
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	Browser-based graphical user interface.
Supported spatial scales	Urban facility (e.g., public park), neighbourhood, city, region.
Supported temporal scales	Monthly, annual.
Water Use Types	Urban.
Compatibility with FIWARE	The tool uses BASEFORM's pre-existing internal data model, which is not based on FIWARE. However, it has broad flexibility in terms of data input, being able to read data from any documented file formats, as well as webservices and other common web-accessible supports; and data output, both to files (text, excel and shapefiles/geopkg) and through its own API. Therefore, it can easily accommodate input/output from/to FIWARE-compliant software. Read/write compatibility only (through API or webservices).
Organisations	BASEFORM
Contact details	Diogo Vitorino (diogo.vitorino@baseform.com)
Data Manager	Diogo Vitorino (diogo.vitorino@baseform.com)
Technologies	Java.
Tags	Reuse, water, supply, demand.

Images

Caption/Source

The images above show respectively the main list of exposure scenarios for a given matchmaking alternative, and the configuration tab displaying the risk components (hazards, exposure routes, exposure sites, activities, population at risk). The tool is available at <https://bwatersmart.baseform.com>

Publications

Ribeiro, R., Rosa, M.J. (2022). Avaliação do risco para a saúde humana associado à reutilização de água: construção de cenários de exposição. 20.º ENASB, Cascais, 24-26 novembro 2022, 5 p. (communication in a conference)

5.6.2 Pre-existing background

BASEFORM software as described in <https://baseform.com/np4/product/>.

5.6.3 Developments and advancements within the project

The tool has been conceived and developed from scratch within the project. It builds upon and benefits from BASEFORM's pre-existing online client-server environment, input/output capabilities, file system and geo-referenced environment for water infrastructures, as well as its graphical user interface. The tool constitutes a new autonomous app within the BASEFORM environment, which may be deployed

on its own as a stand-alone tool, or more likely in conjunction with tools #25 and #17 as per Figure 117.

5.6.4 Navigation and primary functionalities

The figures below illustrate the tool's key functionality.

Figure 40: Tool #27's may screen showing the Analysis tab, which displays the available alternatives in the selected folder. Each alternative comes with a color-coded indication of the risk level for each demand considered.

Figure 41 Upon selecting one of the alternatives, the user is presented with the list of created risk scenarios. New scenarios can be created via the button at the top right.

Figure 42: The list of available fields that can be displayed in the scenarios listing.

CAN THE HAZA...	CLASSIFICATION OF THE CONSEQ...	RISK EVALUATION	IS IT NECESSARY TO TREAT RISK?	BARRIERS TO IMPLEMENT / REINFORCE (FROM IS...	PREVENTIVE MEASURES TI
false	2 - MINOR	MODERATE	true	Additional disinfection, low level (i.e., chlorination t...	Awareness: Signage in the Communication: green are
false	1 - INSIGNIFICANT	LOW	false		
false	2 - MINOR	MODERATE	true	Additional disinfection, low level (i.e., chlorination t...	Awareness: Signage in the Communication: green are
false	1 - INSIGNIFICANT	LOW	true	Additional disinfection, low level (i.e., chlorination t...	Training: green area work
true	2 - MINOR	MODERATE	true	Additional disinfection, low level (i.e., chlorination t...	Training: green area work

Figure 43: The scenarios list showing risk evaluation.

EDIT SCENARIO: Scn1 SAVE DELETE

1. RISK IDENTIFICATION

HAZARDS
Pathogenic bacteria: Legionella

EXPOSURE ROUTES
Inhalation

EXPOSURE SITES
Zone: Lawns

POPULATION AT RISK
Users : Weakened immune system

ACTIVITY
Using the green area

HAZARDOUS EVENTS

- Manual watering without the use of PPE
- Passing close to reclaimed water storage lakes
- Failure in the reclaimed water treatment system
- Walking or lying on wet grass with reclaimed water
- Drinking from drinking fountains wet with reclaimed water
- Cross connection with drinking water distribution network
- Using playgrounds / sport equipments wet with reclaimed water
- Maintaining vegetation during spray irrigation without the use of PPE
- Passing through paths bordering the green area during spray irrigation
- Passing through existing paths in the green area during spray irrigation
- Catching fallen objects (e.g. balls) in the reclaimed water storage lakes
- Using lawns / playgrounds / sports equipments / esplanades during sprinkler irrigation with reclaimed water
- Operating or maintaining the automatic irrigation system without the use of personal protective equipment (PPE)

Figure 44: Editing a risk scenario.

Figure 45: The Configuration tab, giving access to the specification of Components, Barriers, Preventive Measures and Hazardous Events.

Figure 46: Creating or editing hazardous events.

5.6.5 Interoperability

Compatibility with FIWARE is available at read/write level only (through API and/or webservices), as mentioned above in Table 12.

5.6.6 Indicative applications and synergistic benefits

As mentioned above, Tool #27 is autonomous and may be deployed on its own, or in conjunction with the remaining tools (#17, #24, #25) as per Figure 117.

5.6.7 Accessing tool and test data

The tool is part of the set of four tools developed by BASEFORM (#17, #24, #25, #27) for application in the Lisbon Living Lab, where it has been undergoing testing and application to the specific cases being explored in this LL. Sets of test data are available with the software. Real case application data pertaining to the Lisbon Living Lab are available from LNEC and CML.

Accredited users may access the tool at the URL below:

<https://bwatersmart.baseform.com>

For the duration of the project, user credentials should be requested directly from BASEFORM through the following contact point: diogo.vitorino@baseform.com.

5.7 Short-term demand forecasting tool (#28)

5.7.1 Tool description and attributes

The tool generates water demand forecasts for the next (or current) day, which can be used to identify high peak loads in certain regions that require actions by the water utility. This is particularly useful during times of drought when water availability is limited, and water distribution must be optimized. A good understanding of the amount of water needed in different districts helps to ensure security of supply, so that each region receives enough but not excessive water supply. The user can interact with the GUI to train machine learning models and use them to generate and visualize demand forecasts. Furthermore, the user can aggregate forecasts for multiple smart meters to achieve the desired spatial resolution. Furthermore, forecasts can be generated via a RESTful API which helps automate further data processing. The API also allows to integrate the tool in already existing platforms that use their own GUI.

Table 13 includes main information about tool's attributes. Further information can be found in the Water Europe Marketplace via the following URL:

<https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/58> .

Table 13: Short-term demand forecasting tool's attributes and description.

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A software supporting the Circular Economy • A service, offered as part of a Circular Economy enabling portfolio
Name	Short-term demand forecasting tool

Description	Two main components: 1. Backend service that allows to train models and create water demand predictions. The service is reachable through its own REST API (documented in OpenAPI), as well as through the Orion context broker (FIWARE). 2. Frontend service that is used to interact with the backend and visualize forecasts or model training results. This component is optional in case a frontend service already exists at the user's organization where the product can be integrated.
Abbreviation	SDFT
URL	-
Costs	The tool is freely available. Infrastructure and personnel costs may occur from deploying and hosting the tool.
Target audience	Water utility that has the software engineering capabilities to integrate the tool into their system. The user that interacts with / applies the tool needs to be able to use a browser and interpret data from the water domain (e.g., water demand line plots).
Actors, roles and interactions	The tool is meant to be used by water utilities. Depending on their expertise, they might need help from external IT experts to integrate the tool into their system before it can be applied.
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	Open-source tool that integrates a large variety of algorithms that are based on fundamentally different approaches (statistical, tree-based, deep learning) that allow the user to easily test and choose the right algorithm for the specific dataset. The requirement for Machine Learning expertise is minimized due to the use of a state-of-the-art hyperparameter optimization technique (BOHB).
TRL	Level 6
Technical requirements	Software engineering expertise to integrate the components (FIWARE components + backend + frontend) into the network and system of the water utility. All components are provided in form of docker containers. Additional expertise is required to install smart meter devices and connect them to the system such that the pre-processed smart meter data is accessible to the tool.
Environment	The tool comes in form of Docker containers and is thus independent of the specific OS.
Version	1.0
Initial release	2023
License type	Open source
Programming language/technologies used	Python (backend) React.js (frontend) FIWARE Docker (for deployment and networking)
Open interface	The tool can be accessed from a GitHub repository. It offers a REST API documented with OpenAPI and can alternatively be accessed through the Orion context broker using a NGSiv2 API (FIWARE).
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	The tool needs a GUI (either the one developed within the project or one that is developed by the water utility). Since it is possible to interact with the backend using only API calls to create the forecasts, the backend can be used as headless software and can be integrate in other services.

Supported spatial scales	The tool can generate forecasts on household scale and aggregate these results up to regional scale.
Supported temporal scales	Hourly
Water Use Types	Water demand in general (residential, industrial, and agricultural).
Compatibility with FIWARE	It is compatible with FIWARE by offering interactions through the Orion context broker.
Organisations	Open-source development and maintenance by IWW.
Contact details	Marcel Juschak (ma.juschak@iww-online.de)
Data Manager	Marcel Juschak (ma.juschak@iww-online.de)
Technologies	-
Tags	Water demand, Residential, Industrial, Agricultural, Machine learning.
Images	<p>Below, screenshots from the developed user interface are shown that illustrate a typical workflow.</p> <h3>Meter Management</h3> <p>Here you can select a Meter, and view his informations. You can also select multiple Meters to create a virtual Meter with the selected meters as submeters. If you don't want a meter in the List, you can delete it via the button in the list. A selected meter will disable other meters that are a submeter of the selected one.</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="width: 45%;"> <p>Meter List:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Device:MPS045009 <input type="checkbox"/> Device:MPS045010 <input type="checkbox"/> Device:MPS045011 <input type="checkbox"/> Device:MPS045012 <input type="checkbox"/> Device:MPS045013 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Device:MPSHeide <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Device:MPSPariser <p style="text-align: center;">CLEAR SELECTION</p> </div> <div style="width: 45%;"> <p>Meter Info:</p> <p>Create virtual meter from selected meters (2)</p> <p>urn:ngsi-Id:Device:MPSHeide urn:ngsi-Id:Device:MPSPariser</p> <p>Name for virtual Meter (optional):</p> <input type="text" value="SupplyZoneX"/> <p style="text-align: center;">CREATE VIRTUAL METER</p> </div> </div> <p>Grouping smart meters into a “virtual meter” that represents a whole supply zone and for which models can be trained.</p>

Model Management

Here you can train a model with all or a subset of the defined meters. If meters are missing, please add them in the Meter Management tab. The model can then be used to create forecasts. Hyperparameter Optimization is used to find the optimal parameter value, if you don't want to input values manually.

Selected Meter:

urn:ngsi-Id:virtualMeter:SupplyZoneX

Comment:

Algorithm:

XGBoost

Hyperparameter optimization:

Number of configurations to run:

TRAIN MODEL

Estimated Time: 2 min.

Training an XGBoost model for a supply zone with automatic hyperparameter optimization (algorithm parameters are optimized automatically such that the user does not need to understand and specify them).

^	urn:ngsi-Id:virtualMeter:SupplyZoneX:MLModel:XGBoost	XGBoost	2023-06-05T09:05:07	2023-06-05T09:05:07	
---	--	---------	---------------------	---------------------	---

MAPE:
5.10109

RMSE:
0.02742

	<p>Model performance on a hold-out dataset for plausibility checking based on error metrics and visualizations of predicted vs. actual water demand.</p> <p>Forecast Data</p> <p>This forecast is generated for 2023-03-14 using meter "urn:ngsi-Id:virtualMeter:SupplyZoneX" and algorithm "XGBoost".</p> <p>Forecast generation for a specific day, using the already trained model.</p>
Caption/Source	Captions are specified directly with the pictures above. Pictures are provided by IWW.
Publications	Not yet available.

5.7.2 Pre-existing background

There is no pre-existing background, the tool was developed within the scope of the BWS project.

5.7.3 Developments and advancements within the project

A backend component was developed as a microservice to create models and generate 24h-forecasts. It assumes the availability of pre-processed, hourly smart meter data inside a MongoDB database within the same network. If smart meter data is lacking, users can make use of data sets that were collected for training of the models.

The microservice's RESTful API was documented with OpenAPI and designed to integrate easily with i) the frontend that is used by the water utility and ii) the Orion context broker that provides an interface to external applications. The frontend was developed based on user stories associated with the different REST endpoints. Similarly, the interaction with the FIWARE context broker was finalized and documented.

A concept was developed that enables the creation of models / forecasts for arbitrary spatial resolutions. Smart meters that are installed in the real world and measure water consumption are referred to as "physical meter". Additionally, the idea of a "virtual meter" was introduced to group meters together (e.g., a supply zone) in a hierarchical manner, as shown in the picture below (Figure 47). The user can create virtual meters for any area according to their specific needs and treat them identically to physical meters, i.e., train models for them and create forecasts.

Figure 47: Data models that are needed to represent and work with virtual meters are iteratively refined to fulfil the requirements that become clearer with growing maturity of the tool.

Suitable algorithms from different backgrounds were selected for the tool, the implementations of which are provided by the open-source library Darts. The water utility might prefer statistical approaches that are easy to understand and thus perceived as more trustworthy. Specifically, the Prophet algorithm is very suitable for data with strong seasonality and very fast to train. XGBoost is a tree-based approach that resembles more classical machine learning and is able to learn very complex patterns from relatively small datasets while doing so with low training times. On the other hand, the provided deep learning-based approaches require much more training time, although their potential is generally higher when more training data is available. Depending on the specific context, the water utility may prefer one approach over the others, although XGBoost is considered to be a good default.

A hyperparameter optimization algorithm “Bayesian optimization with Hyperband” (BOHB) was integrated, using the open-source Ray library to automatically select suitable parameters and reduce the amount of machine learning expertise required by the user.

A weather agent interface was created that allows the water utility to provide data that should be used for training and forecast creation. This additional data would typically constitute weather data, although the interface is general enough to allow for any information that could possibly improve the predictions.

A synthetic dataset was created as part of the documentation that shows the form of the expected data and can be used to test the tool straight away, without connecting the water utility’s own data streams right away.

5.7.4 Navigation and primary functionalities

The GUI (frontend) component is provided as a minimalistic browser-based admin dashboard that can be used to apply the tool. All main functionalities are encapsulated in their own web pages that are easily accessible from a sidebar that is shown on the left side of the screen. These pages include:

1. Defining a new virtual meter that can be used to create models and forecasts for a larger area.
2. Training a model for the virtual meter and checking performance based on error metrics and visualizations.
3. Generating forecasts and visualizing the results with historical load curves as context information for plausibility checking.

The mock-ups below show the UI which consists of the following elements (Figure 48, Figure 49, Figure 50):

Meter Management

Here you can select a Meter, and view his informations. You can also select multiple Meters to create a virtual Meter with the selected meters as submeters. If you don't want a meter in the List, you can delete it via the button in the list. A selected meter will disable other meters that are a submeter of the selected one.

Meter List:

- Device:MPS045009
- Device:MPS045010
- Device:MPS045011
- Device:MPS045012
- Device:MPS045013
- Device:MPSHeide
- Device:MPSPariser

CLEAR SELECTION

Meter Info:

Create virtual meter from selected meters (2)

urn:ngsi-Id:Device:MPSHeide
urn:ngsi-Id:Device:MPSPariser

Name for virtual Meter (optional):

SupplyZoneX

CREATE VIRTUAL METER

Figure 48: Aggregating smart meters (physical meters) to a virtual meter that represents a supply zone.

Model Management

Here you can train a model with all or a subset of the defined meters. If meters are missing, please add them in the Meter Management tab. The model can then be used to create forecasts. Hyperparameter Optimization is used to find the optimal parameter value, if you don't want to input values manually.

Selected Meter:

Comment:

Algorithm:

Hyperparameter optimization:

Number of configurations to run:

TRAIN MODEL

Estimated Time: 2 min. i

Figure 49: Training a model for a previously created virtual meter that represents a specific supply zone using the XGBoost algorithm and hyperparameter optimization based on 15 different configurations that are tested.

Forecast Data

This forecast is generated for **2023-03-14** using meter "urn:ngsi-ld:virtualMeter:SupplyZoneX" and algorithm "XGBoost".

Figure 50: Visualization of a forecast using a previously trained model and comparing the forecast with historical load curves of the recent past for plausibility checking.

5.7.5 Interoperability

The tool currently aims at interoperability maturity level 3 (refer to D3.1 “BWS, FIWARE based interoperability framework”, section 2.3, Figure 6, p. 25.), as it uses NGSi compatible data models. Where possible, existing smart data models are used, e.g., for machine learning models. The solution is FIWARE-ready, as the tool can communicate with the Orion context broker and make parts of the functionality available through it to external apps. If desired, these external apps can read already generated forecasts, but cannot define virtual meters or train models or generate forecasts themselves. This is important for ensuring data consistency and to avoid large computational demands on the water utility’s servers because of external services.

Beyond that, we recommend the use of a FIWARE IoT agent like Draco to store the smart meter data in the database so that it can be used by the tool. However, the choice to use such components has to be made and implemented by the water utility.

5.7.6 Indicative applications and synergistic benefits

Since the tool is driven by smart meter data, it has natural synergistic effects with smart meter technologies. In addition, services that provide historical or forecasted weather data can increase the quality of the results of the tool significantly.

5.7.7 Accessing tool and test data

Users may access the backend and frontend of the tool via the GitHub repository by following the links:

<https://github.com/iwwtech/bws-short-term-forecasting>

<https://github.com/iwwtech/bws-short-term-forecasting-ui>

Further support and guidance can be provided by Marcel Juschak (ma.juschak@iww-online.de).

5.8 SuTRa (#31)

5.8.1 Tool description and attributes

SuTRa is a Python package that calculates the advective removal of microbial organisms (also called ‘pathogens’) from source to endpoint.

Its main features are the following:

- Includes database of removal parameters for microbial organisms,
- Calculates the removal and concentration of the microbial organism over distance and with time.

SuTRa calculates the subsurface removal of microbial organisms over a distance and with time using an analytical approach. The aim is to allow for a quick assessment of subsurface removal of microbial organisms for a growing selection of species. A database was added, starting with plant pathogens ‘solani’ (*Dickeya solani*), ‘carotovorum’ (*Pectobacterium carotovorum*), and ‘solanacearum’ (*Ralstonia solanacearum*). Additional species will be added once more data become available.

SuTRa is developed by KWR Water Research Institute.

The table below (Table 14) includes information about tool's attributes and descriptions in a tabular format for use in updating the detailed page of the tool in the Water Europe Marketplace developed in T7.1, if needed. The detailed page of the tool can be accessed via the following URL:

<https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/Product/59> .

Table 14: SuTRa tool's attributes and description.

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	A software supporting the Circular Economy
Name	Subsurface Transport and Removal
Description	<p>Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) offers numerous benefits including storage of water.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The source water for MAR schemes is often contaminated with pathogens. • One of the advantages of MAR is that the pathogens may be removed during storage and transport. <p>Challenge</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing models for pathogen removal require high expertise (e.g., Hydrus 2D) or are not suited for MAR-applications (QMRAWell). • Removal parameters are hard to estimate. • Dependence on organism related properties (e.g., diameter, survival rate). • Environmental parameters such as temperature, redox conditions, and flow rate. • Existing databases are not tailored to conditions typical for MAR. <p>The aim of this tool is to retrieve plant pathogen transport properties and use this information to predict concentration of pathogens after subsurface storage.</p>
Abbreviation	SuTRa
URL	https://sutra.readthedocs.io/en/latest/tutorial.html
Costs	Use is free of charge.
Target audience	Direct users: Professionals involved in the design (e.g., engineers) or in the evaluation of MAR-schemes (e.g., health experts, pest control experts).
Actors, roles and interactions	Indirect beneficiaries: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural companies: less risk of plant diseases, • MAR-Technology providers: more optimal dimensioning of MAR-schemes.
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	Simple method to get a first estimate of microbial risks of MAR.
TRL	TRL 6

Technical requirements	Computer with Python version 3.6 or higher installed.
Environment	Computer with Python version 3.6 or higher installed.
Version	First version
Initial release	June 2022
License type	MIT License
Programming language/technologies used	Python
Open interface	None. Parameters are currently downloaded with the package (no API).
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	The tool has no GUI.
Supported spatial scales	Most applicable to field scale (1 to 100 meters) since this is the distance over which pathogen transport typically takes place.
Supported temporal scales	Daily.
Water Use Types	Any water type (urban, industrial, rural and agriculture) infiltrated into the subsurface.
Compatibility with FIWARE	NA
Organisations	KWR Water Research Institute.
Contact details	Martin van der Schans (Martin.van.der.schans@kwrwater.nl)
Data Manager	Gerard van den Berg (Gerard.van.den.Berg@kwrwater.nl)
Technologies	Controlled Agricultural Recharge and Drainage (CARD) Large Scale Aquifer Storage and Recovery System (ASR)
Tags	Plant pathogens, groundwater, inactivation.

5.8.2 Pre-existing background

The code is based on the equations given in chapter 6.7 of BTO 2012.015 “*Gezondheidsrisico’s van fecale verontreiniging*” [in Dutch], pp 71-74. The tool has been developed within the BWS project and it is also co-financed by the BTO Joint Research Programme of the Dutch and Flemish Water Utilities.

The computations that the tool makes are incidentally performed on a project-by-project basis mainly based on information on transport and removal of human pathogens.

5.8.3 Developments and advancements within the project

The advancements made within the project with regard to the tool are:

- Collection of scientific data on plant pathogens.
- Derivation of typical transport and removal parameters from these data.
- Development of a pipeline (Python tool) to facilitate fast and efficient computations of plant pathogen concentration in MAR systems.

During transport in the subsurface, microbial organism removal takes place by both attachment to the soil matrix and inactivation. The virus concentration ‘C’ [m-3] through steady-state transport of microbial organisms along path lines in the saturated groundwater can be approximated by:

$$\frac{dC}{dx} + \frac{k_{att} + \mu_1}{v} C = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where:

$k_{att} + \mu_1$ equals the removal rate 'lambda',

' k_{att} ': attachment coefficient [day-1],

' μ_1 ': inactivation coefficient [day-1],

x: the distance travelled [m],

v: the porewater velocity [m day-1] or 'darcyflux divided by the effective porosity'.

Assuming that the background concentration of the relevant microbial organism equals 0, the relative removal ' C_x/C_0 ' can be calculated as follows.

$$\log\left(\frac{C_x}{C_0}\right) = -\frac{(k_{att} + \mu_1) x}{\ln(10) v} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

The attachment coefficient ' k_{att} ' depends on the effective porosity ' ϵ ', the grain diameter of the sediment ' d_c ', 'sticky coefficient' alpha [day-1], the porosity dependent Happel's parameter ' A_s ', diffusion constant ' D_{BM} ' [m² day-1], and the porewater velocity [m day-1].

$$k_{att} = \frac{3}{2} \cdot \frac{(1-\epsilon)}{d_c} \cdot \alpha 4A_s^{1/3} \cdot \left(\frac{D_{BM}}{d_c \epsilon v}\right)^{2/3} \cdot v \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

The sticky coefficient alpha is determined by coefficient ' α_0 ', which depends on both the soil type and the type of organism. Alpha0 is being determined for a reference pH [pH0], e.g., pH=7.5. Alpha relates to alpha0 as follows [corrected for different pH].

$$\alpha = \alpha_0 \cdot 0,9^{\left(\frac{pH-pH_0}{0,1}\right)} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

The other parameters are calculated as follows:

Happel's porosity dependent parameter

$$A_s = 2 \cdot \frac{(1-\gamma^5)}{(2-3\gamma+3\gamma^5-2\gamma^6)} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

Where:

$$\gamma = (1 - \varepsilon)^{1/3}$$

Boltzmann diffusion coefficient:

$$D_{BM} = \frac{K_B \cdot (T+273)}{3\pi \cdot d_p \cdot \mu} \cdot 86400 \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

with Boltzmann constant K_B [$1,38 \times 10^{-23}$ J K⁻¹], organism diameter d_p [m], water temperature T [degr C], and conversion factor 86,400 [s day⁻¹].

The dynamic viscosity ' μ ' [kg m⁻¹ s⁻¹] depends on the groundwater density ' ρ '. The water density is assumed to be 999.7 [kg m⁻³], representative for fresh groundwater in the Netherlands under a reference temperature of 12 degrees centigrade.

$$\mu = \frac{\rho \cdot 497 \cdot 10^{-6}}{(T+42,5)^{3/2}} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

5.8.4 Navigation and primary functionalities

The tool can be accessed through python code as specified in the tutorial <https://sutra.readthedocs.io/en/latest/tutorial.html>.

Running the code involves several steps:

First the type of organism (pathogen) needs to be specified along with its initial concentration. The user also needs to define the environmental conditions for which the pathogen removal rate needs to be computed such as the redox-condition and groundwater flow velocity.

Next, the package retrieves the transport properties of the organism from a database (provided with the software). The user also has the opportunity to manually insert parameters in case they are not provided by the database for a certain organism, or in case the user wants to perform a sensitivity analysis on the parameters provided by the database.

Finally, the removal of the pathogen during soil passage is computed, based on the environmental conditions and transport properties of the organism.

The example below illustrates that the computations are quite easy (for those with a basic knowledge of Python) (Figure 51).

Scenario A: Calculate removal of a microbial organism using default database parameters.

```
## Default removal parameters ##
In [7]: organism_name = "carotovorum"

# Redox condition: 3 options ['deeply_anoxic','anoxic','suboxic']
In [8]: redox_cond = 'anoxic'

# organism diameter [m]
In [9]: organism_diam = 1.803e-6

# Starting concentration
In [10]: conc_start = 1.

# Ambient groundwater concentration
In [11]: conc_gw = 0.

# effective porosity
In [12]: por_eff = 0.33

# Sediment grainsize
In [13]: grainsize = 0.00025

# pH of the groundwater
In [14]: pH_water = 7.5

# Water temperature
In [15]: temp_water = 10.

# Water density [kg m-3]
In [16]: rho_water = 999.703

# Distance traveled along pathline [m]
In [17]: distance_traveled = 100.

# Time traveled [days]
In [18]: traveltime = 1.

# Porewater velocity [m day-1]
In [19]: porewater_velocity = distance_traveled / traveltime
```

First initialize a class for calculating the removal of an organism.

```
In [20]: mbo_removal_scenA = rf.MicrobialRemoval(organism = organism_name)

In [21]: removal_parameters = mbo_removal_scenA.removal_parameters

# Return the (default) removal parameter values
In [22]: print(removal_parameters)
{'organism_name': 'carotovorum', 'alpha0': {'suboxic': 0.3, 'anoxic': 0.577, 'deeply_anoxic': 0.577}, 'p'
```

Calculate final concentration after advective microbial removal

```
# Calculate final concentration and print it
In [23]: C_final_default = mbo_removal_scenA.calc_advective_microbial_removal(grainsize = grainsize,
....:                               temp_water = temp_water, rho_water = rho_water,
....:                               pH = pH_water, por_eff = por_eff,
....:                               conc_start = conc_start, conc_gw = conc_gw,
....:                               redox = redox_cond,
....:                               distance_traveled = distance_traveled,
....:                               travelttime = travelttime)
....:

In [24]: print(C_final_default)
8.2065781569924e-12

# Print lambda (default): removal rate [day-1]
In [25]: print(mbo_removal_scenA.lamda)
25.526085068992856
```

Figure 51: Example of computations in python.

5.8.5 Interoperability

The input and output data, as well as the interoperability options offered by the tool are listed in the below table (Table 15).

Table 15: Input data, output data and interoperability of SuTRa

Input data
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport properties: Travel distance, Travel time, • Aquifer properties: Redox zone, grain size (d50), • Pathogen type: name (we will start with a limited number of indicator organisms), • Input concentration
Output data
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pathogen properties: size, stickiness, etc. • Output concentration
Interoperability options
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open-source python package allows for coupling with existing tools (e.g., UWOT).

- The Python package can be downloaded to a PC from “<https://pypi.org/project/sutra/>” or installed directly using the package installer for Python pip.
- The database of pathogen properties is part of the package and is therefore also downloaded during installation. Consequently, once installed, there is no need for an external connection to import the pathogen database.
- SuTRa is compatible with any operating system that uses Python 3.6 or higher.
- Input data are provided in either numeric (“float”) or textual (“string”) format, which are used as arguments in Python functions, as described in the online manual <https://sutra.readthedocs.io/en/latest/tutorial.html>.
- Output is generated by functions and also consists of numeric (“float”) and texts (“string”) depending on what function the user enters. The user can either retrieve (echo) the input data to check it or analyse the results, such as the output concentration.
- A list of the input-requirements (data format) and functions can be found in the manual at <https://sutra.readthedocs.io/en/latest/tutorial.html>.

5.8.6 Indicative applications and synergistic benefits

The tool has not yet been utilised, it has only been compared to analytical solutions (as benchmark/integration test).

Similar computations have been made in the past to calculate the risks of virus transport in MAR for drinking water purposes.

The tool can be used, for example, in conjunction with UWOT, where the hydrological model is used to calculate residence time, and the SuTRa package is used to compute the resulting microbial risks.

Table 16: Applications of SuTRa out of the BWS project

Indicative application of the tool	
Title	Various locations (outside B-WaterSmart project).
Description	We anticipate the application of the tool to the design of ASR systems for horticulture where pollution of irrigation with pathogens is a concern. In particular, this is of concern when multiple companies share the same ASR since this could increase the risk of cross contamination in case there is not enough residence time in the subsurface to ensure die-off of pathogens. Other applications may include the computation of microbial safety zones as part of QMRA (Quantitative Microbial Risk Analysis) around drinking water production sites.
Reference point	To be determined. We are open to facilitating the testing of the tool by third parties.
Location	NA.
Country (-ies)	NA.
URL	NA.
Project	NA.
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High or increasing irrigation water demand for agriculture, • Increasing water demand by growing industrial sectors, • Need for reuse and recovery schemes for wastewater & sludge.

Tools/Product/Services	NA.
Technologies	Controlled Agricultural Recharge and Drainage (CARD) Large Scale Aquifer Storage and Recovery System (ASR)
Scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local (e.g., single treatment plant, industrial site or city quarter)
Legislation	Water quality standards for both groundwater (EU WFD) and drinking water.
Synergistic benefits	Improved water quality and safety.
Requirements and conditions	A prerequisite is an understanding of the hydrological conditions (travel distance, residence time) and ideally also the redox status of groundwater (oxic, anoxic).
Key lessons	NA.
Organisations	NA.
Contact persons	NA.
Data Manager	NA.
Costs	Several billable hours to days, depending on background knowledge, information available.
Tags	NA
Publications/Reference	NA
Images	NA
Caption/Source	NA

5.8.7 Accessing tool and test data

The tool is accessible through the following URL where users may find instructions on the installation process: <https://pypi.org/project/sutra/>.

Documentation and additional information may be found at <https://sutra.readthedocs.io/en/latest/> or/and provided by Martin van der Schans (Martin.van.der.schans@kwrwater.nl).

6 Tools and Methods for LL Flanders

6.1 Key WS challenges, ambition and case study description

Flanders is a region with high water demand due to high population density and high industrial and agricultural activity. The region faces increasing limitations in freshwater availability and decreasing groundwater levels. The deterioration of surface water quality during dry summers has negative consequences for drinking water production. At the Water Production Centre (WPC) De Blankaart water intake is limited during the dry summer months as the water quality of the river is too low to be suitable for treatment in the current facility. Next to freshwater limitation, there is also an increasing risk of flooding during high intensity precipitation events, especially in urban areas. These issues are expected to increase in frequency and duration under climate change.

Currently, there are strong initiatives in Flanders to improve the robustness of the water system with the aim of taking significant steps towards implementation and upscaling of circular solutions for developing a smart and sustainable water system within the next 3-5 years. The development of a stronger water management and optimal use of the available water resources is encouraged and supported by the current Flemish government for example through the Blue Deal programme. The water-smart opportunities in the Flanders LL are to establish regional circularity in the water system by using alternative water resources for drinking water supply, and to secure irrigation by interaction with the urban reuse cycle.

In BWS, smart solutions are developed for alternative circular water sources for drinking water and agriculture. The main challenges we are addressing in this project are firstly, the need for technologies for water reuse and practical testing of their operation at demonstration sites to gain a better understanding of purification needs and the efficiency of these approaches. Secondly, better understanding is needed on microbial risk assessment methods to help determine the design requirements of purification and subsurface passage systems. Furthermore, we aim to develop better connections between wastewater utilities, drinking water utilities, municipalities, and farmers to help identify potential circularities. Within the water system, everything is connected. Interventions in the water system, such as the ones investigated within this project, can affect and be affected by other system components. An understanding is needed of the potential contribution and impact of local circular solutions on the water system at a more regional level to better understand and identify potential trade-offs and benefits and to help decision makers make choices and develop strategies.

6.2 Application of tools and methods

6.2.1 Selected tools and technologies of pilots

There are two parts to the technology development in BWS LL Flanders. The first aims to improve the robustness of the drinking water supply by expanding drinking water treatment capacity with an advanced Closed Circuit Reverse Osmosis (CCRO) system that will allow the WPC to take in low-quality surface water (aquifer storage recovery - technology #2). In parallel, the potential for effluent reuse for drinking water is explored as an alternative or supplementing water source (effluent reuse for drinking water production - technology #3). The aim of this demonstration is to compare these solutions and analyse what their relative benefits and trade-offs are or how they could enhance each other. In the second demonstration, a system is developed for stormwater reuse for agriculture (urban stormwater reuse for agriculture - technology #5). A stormwater retention basin is built by the city of

Mechelen to prevent flooding of urban areas. Within BWS a system is developed to make the water from the basin available for subirrigation at nearby fields. The Stormwater Reuse Management system (tool #21) is used to control the outflow from the basin and the water distribution for irrigation to optimize the functioning of the basin for flood prevention and availability of water for irrigation during dry periods.

There is a need to place these technological demonstrations in a broader context to assess how they can contribute to a more robust and smarter water system at a regional level. The regional analysis and UWOT (tool #22) were used to assess the demonstrations in their regional context with regard to their impact on water availability and resilience of the water system. Next to that, the potential to include alternative water sources while minimizing negative impact on local nature and environment in order to design a sustainable water supply for the future was analysed. The regional analysis was used to identify regional effects of changes in water supply and demand. The results can be used to start collaborations and can help communication between stakeholders in the region.

A critical success factor for water reuse is the assessment and control of microbial safety risks. The QMRA+ (tool #26) is developed to support the design and assess the required treatment needed for water reuse. QMRA+ is a valuable tool for quantitative microbial risk assessment that can be used to assess existing purification systems and to help determine the design requirements of purification systems for e.g., alternative water sources with regards to microbial safety requirements. Within the Woumen case, QMRA+ was used to help design the effluent reuse demonstration system by comparing the safety of various treatment options and point supplementation of the existing drinking water system. The SuTRa tool builds on microbial risk assessment to specifically model (plant) pathogen removal during subsurface passage of managed aquifer recharge and infiltration schemes. In the Mechelen case this helped to determine the minimum design parameters and residence time required for pathogen removal. The outputs from SuTRa may support the regional analysis or similar studies in related projects by providing input parameters on subsurface passage if these are included in the conceptual design.

The LL Flanders technologies and tools and their link to the living lab challenge and strategic objectives are presented in Figure 52. The high-level interactions among tools and the pilots are depicted in Figure 53.

CHALLENGES LL Flanders – High drinking water demand due to dense population, high irrigation water demand for agriculture, groundwater overexploitation, water quality deterioration, water scarcity due to droughts and climate change.

Figure 52: The LL Flanders technologies and tools and their link to the living lab challenge and strategic objectives.

Figure 53: Tool and pilot high-level interaction.

6.2.2 Integrative use of tools, pilot interaction and data flows

With regard to UWOT and the Regional Analysis, both methods involve water systems analysis and proceed by designing model architectures with multiple interacting components at a regional level. For the tools to be used in an integrated fashion, thus, it makes sense to pool resources and steps in the (a) conceptualisation of regional modelling cases within the Flanders LL, and (b) the data inventurisation, collection and preparation process. Both stages are done in collaboration with the Flanders LL regional stakeholders, as (i) their input and concerns are valuable in identifying regional issues and design smart water applications with practical interest, and (ii) regional data is needed which is only accessible at the utility or municipal level and can be requested from selected stakeholders. Figure 54 below depicts the conceptualization process chain (incl. data flows) for the UWOT and Regional Analysis models.

Figure 54: Conceptualization process chain (incl. data flows) for the UWOT and Regional Analysis models.

To align workflows, the creation of both UWOT and Regional Analysis models was based on a common conceptualization process chain that was performed online using “miro” (Figure 55), a visual collaboration platform for cross-functional teamwork (<https://miro.com/app/dashboard/>). The process chain included the following stages:

1. The concept stage, where, following a series of group meetings with regional Flanders stakeholders, the main problems of the area were discussed, and regional applications were outlined. This creative process resulted in multiple ideas on regional issues, which were then evaluated against model characteristics and capabilities. The goal was to decide which regional applications have high interest and are feasible within the modelling domain of UWOT and the regional analysis.
2. The model stage, where initial model topologies were created from selected ideas in stage (1). This led to model files for UWOT and the Regional Analysis, where parameters were outlined, and data requirements to run the models were determined.
3. The data inventurisation and request stage, where data needs that follow from stage (2) were inventorised and tabulated. Moreover, meetings with selected regional stakeholders that can be data providers were held in order to identify potential data sources and the overall data availability. At this stage, possible open-access data sources were also discussed (e.g., regional hydrometeorological databases, data repositories, census data etc.).

Figure 55: Snapshot of the miro working environment (canvas) for the conceptualisation and data flows of the UWOT/Regional Analysis tools.

QMRA+ was used to assess the microbial safety using quantitative microbial risk assessment. It was used in BWS LL Flanders in relation to the technology development (Task 2.3.1) on potential effluent reuse for drinking water. The tool was used to help determine the minimum design requirements of the purification system with regards to microbial safety by comparing various treatment schemes. Next to supporting the design of the technical solutions, QMRA+ and SuTRa can also help inform the water system modelling done with UWOT and the Regional Analysis tool as they can give an indication of the microbial water quality. UWOT and the Regional Analysis tool can only model water quantities. However, considering water quality and safety requirements is essential for successful implementation of water reuse. SuTRa can be used to help determine the minimum transport time and/or distance for subsurface infiltration and storage solutions required to remove pathogens. These design parameters inform the boundary conditions for water system modelling.

The Stormwater Reuse Management System (tool #21) which is reported in D3.4, is integrated with the technology development of the stormwater management system (Task 2.3.2). The tool is intended to be used to control the basin inlet and outlet and distribute irrigation water to fields based on water availability and demand. The tool is based on the specific design parameters and local situation of the stormwater management system and has a local scale. The output from the tool can be used to inform and calibrate the modelling in UWOT and the Regional Analysis Tool with regards to the stormwater reuse case. As these tools are strongly integrated in the smart-technology development, the discussion below is focused on UWOT and the regional analysis model.

6.2.3 Pre-processing stage and input data

During the initial conceptualization stage (“Concept” stage in Figure 54), different regional issues in Flanders were discussed in a series of meetings with a stakeholder group comprising participants from de Watergroep (DW production), Aquafin (WW treatment plants and actors of WW reuse), the region of Mechelen (provincial and urban development actors) and VITO (technology provider for RW harvesting). Different aspects of the regional water system with regards to water smartness were

discussed, such as: safe DW provision and the challenge of river salinization, the potential of WW reuse as an extra source, regional issues with flood risk in urban areas, water used for irrigation and the potential of using RWH as an extra source etc. During these sessions, it was acknowledged that Flanders is an extensive, diverse area that faces multiple issues across water cycle domains. The stakeholder group therefore decided to focus on two regionally representative sub-regional use cases with a high interest in water resources modelling (see Figure 55) that could form the basis of UWOT/Regional Analysis modelling: Woumen (Dijsmuide) and Mechelen. The overview of the two cases is presented in the below figure (Figure 56).

Figure 56: Overview of the two use cases for UWOT/Regional Analysis in Flanders LL.

The first case of Woumen (Dijsmuide area) features an issue of DW availability: the main source of river Ijzer offers insufficient water availability for drinking water production due to operational intake limitations, resulting mainly from a combination of low discharge (especially in summer and autumn months) and high salinity. Likewise, the polder system in the region faces similar problems with water level maintenance and salinisation in dry summers. This puts the DW production facility of Bekken de Blankaart (Figure 57) under stress, as intake limitation restrict the levels of the intake reservoir and translate to unguaranteed DW production. Moreover, the effect of future deteriorating conditions (e.g., due to climate change) on this system vulnerability remains to be explored. Against this issue, there is ongoing research by regional actors to (a.) explore additional RO treatment options of (high salinity) intake water to ensure a safer DW stream, (b.) explore the possibility of using WW reuse (from the effluent of WWTP) as an extra source of water intake for DW.

Figure 57: Schematic of the Woumen DW production case.

The second case of Mechelen (Hombeek area, Figure 58) focuses on a peri-urban area that sees agricultural usage and has increased water needs that lead to depletion of local sources (e.g., low surface water and groundwater levels). Moreover, during wet periods, there is risk of flooding damage in neighbouring urban areas due to insufficient capacity of the current stormwater discharge systems. As a result, a stormwater buffer reservoir that will be used as a retention basin during flood events has been built in the area. This reservoir could be used in conjunction with a sub-irrigation network to cover the irrigation needs for agricultural fields in the area. The interplay of these two objectives (flood volume retention vis-à-vis coverage of agriculture needs) could be explored using water systems modelling.

Figure 58: Schematic of the Mechelen RWH-subirrigation case.

Following the delineation of these two cases of interest to the stakeholders, the first model conceptualisations are sketched and the corresponding data needs are outlined. The input data needed for the regional analysis, as well as feedback on the conceptual set-up of the analysis, were collected during several meetings with the stakeholders for the two different cases. During this phase, the stakeholder group was divided into two focus groups (one for each case). The process of conceptualizing models and requesting data (model and data inventorisation stages of Figure 54) is iterative, leading to a sequential improvement of the initial model topologies as well as an inclusive review of the data needed for both cases. Table 17 and Table 18 present an overview of the data needs, which are shared across both methods, as well as the various data sources used to cover them.

Table 17: Input data for the UWOT/Regional Analysis for the Woumen case.

Input data		
Data type	Description	Source
Precipitation (P)	Point rainfall measurements from Zarren station	Flemish government open data website (waterinfo.be)
Potential evapotranspiration (ET)	Penman-Monteith ET from Zarren station. Missing values in October 2008, May 2009, April and May	Flemish government open data website (waterinfo.be)

	2015, June 2016 replaced with station Waregem.	
IJzer discharge upstream	Measured discharge IJzer at Keiem (10km downstream), rescaled to discharge at Woumen using modelled mean flows from VMM	DOV portal (https://www.dov.vlaanderen.be/portaal/)
IJzer chloride concentrations	Chlorine (Cl) measurements (location B7 upstream of the intake)	Data obtained from de Watergroep
Inflow brooks to polders	Measured discharge Steenbeek, rescaled using modelled mean discharges from VMM for other brooks	DOV portal (https://www.dov.vlaanderen.be/portaal/)
Chloride levels polder	Cl measurements (location B10 upstream of the Stenensluisvaart)	Data obtained from De Watergroep
WWTP discharge	Measured discharge (effluent, WWTP exit)	Geoloket, VMM
WWTP discharge chloride level	Measured discharge chloride levels	Geoloket VMM
De Blankaart DW facility technical specifics	Basin geometry and volume, average daily DW production capacity, Chlorine intake threshold	Provided by de Watergroep

Table 18: Input data for the UWOT/Regional Analysis for the Mechelen case.

Input data		
Data type	Description	Source
Precipitation (P)	Point rainfall measurements from Bonheiden station. Missing values April 2014, September 2016, October and November 2018 filled with Boortmeerbeek	Flemish government open data website (https://www.waterinfo.be/)
Potential evapotranspiration (ET)	Penman-Monteith ET model results from Herentals station. Missing values 2010 and 2015 filled with Liedekerke.	Flemish government open data website (waterinfo.be)
RW retention basin pilot specifics	Retention basin geometry and volume, technical schematics	Provided by VITO
RW retention basin serviced areas	Total urban area whose outlet is directed to the retention basin	Provided by VITO/Mechelen municipality

Regarding the preprocessing work of the stormwater reuse management system (tool #21)³, which is reported in D3.4, this included:

- A buffer basin has to be equipped with a control valve and a PLC that can connect with the control in the cloud.
- All polluting water streams that might have been connected to the stormwater collection system in the past, such as combined sewer overflows, wastewater inlets, etc. must be disconnected from the system to ensure pure rainwater being used as source for the irrigation system.

³ The stormwater reuse management system (tool #21) is part of D3.4. Nevertheless, the preprocessing work and lessons learned are being documented in D3.5 as part of the LL work in order to provide the complete picture of the Flanders case since it is related with other tools.

- The agricultural fields need to be equipped with a subirrigation system, either by constructing a new system or by transforming the existing drainage system into a subirrigation system.
- A water transport network between the buffer basin and the agricultural fields needs to be installed.
- Minimum required sensor data:
 - water level in the buffer basin,
 - water level in the feeding tank of the subirrigation system,
 - groundwater level in the agricultural fields
 - precipitation measurements
 - temperature measurements
- Minimum required systems characteristics:
 - Basin dimensions for storage characteristics, including floor level and external overflow crest level.
 - Connected effective runoff surface area.
- Minimum required external data:
 - Rainfall forecast (volume or intensity) for at least 3-6 hours with high temporal (equal to better than 15 minutes) resolution for a location relevant for the stormwater runoff
 - Characteristics of fields (whether subirrigation wanted, priority of field, max heights of the groundwater at what time of the year, surface area)
- Additional data not essential but desirable for further optimization of the system performance may include:
 - Detailed local weather forecasts covering information such as temperature, solar radiation, etc.
 - Discharge measurements on pipes to the subirrigation system.
- Safe operation of the upgraded system must be ensured. This can be achieved through detailed, model-based hydraulic analysis to determine safe water levels in the buffer basin for the fallback control on the edge device.

The QMRA+ tool requires the user to select its type of source water, the water treatment processes used and the intended use of the produced water. The QMRA+ tool then uses default values from scientific literature and guidebooks to provide concentrations of pathogens in the source, efficiency of treatment systems, frequency of use and volume ingested per use. The users are allowed to adapt these standard values when they have more accurate information from their specific situation or system. This could be from water quality analysis, treatment challenge testing or user assessment. Point of attention for interpreting the tool results is a lack of expert knowledge of the user. Insufficient understanding can lead to misinterpretation of results. The tool provides a best estimate of water safety based on typical systems elsewhere. However, all input variables show large differences between individual systems. Therefore, it rather assesses the potential of a system. Verification of local water quality and treatment performance is essential to draw conclusions about safety of the actual system. Therefore, in most cases it is recommended to use the tool with consultancy support.

Note that the tool only focusses on microbial risks and does not consider costs, chemical parameters etc. therefore the tool not suitable for complete optimization of e.g., a wastewater reuse plant.

6.2.4 Setup process and application

6.2.4.1 UWOT setup and application

Woumen

Following the data inventurisation process described in Section 6.2.3, the data is pre-processed to be inserted into the model and a UWOT model topology with all needed system components to represent the intake system of Woumen is designed (Figure 59).

Figure 59: UWOT topology schematic of the Woumen (DW intake) case.

With regard to data preprocessing, data from the shared UWOT-Regional Analysis database (Table 17) is loaded in a python data processing environment (featuring Jupyter Notebooks running python 3.6 with the packages of numpy 1.18.1, pandas 1.3.5, matplotlib 3.1.3, and seaborn 0.10.0), cleaned, and converted to data formats suitable for UWOT modelling (i.e., CSV time series of individual variables). Time series are inserted at a daily timestep for the period 1-1-2006 to 31-12-2020 where most data variables do not have significant missing values or gaps. This data timeframe (simulation period) is shared with the Regional Analysis tool as well. The data preprocessing steps include:

- Cleaning river discharge data and interpolating missing values. Negative values in river discharge indicating flow from the sea (i.e., salinity intrusion) are converted to zero values, as the model requires non-negative flow data as input.
- Extracting point precipitation and evaporation data in millimetres (mm) and checking for missing or erroneous values.
- Extracting salinity data (to accompany river discharge data) in mg/L and checking for missing or erroneous values.

- Extracting WWTP effluent (WW quantity) data and checking for missing or erroneous values.
- Formulating urban demand scenarios and the corresponding time series. Actual urban water demands in Woumen are indicated as unknown from the stakeholder group, so assumptions on demand scenarios are made to generate the corresponding input for UWOT. This is further explained in Section 6.2.5.
- Necessary unit conversions to prepare data for the UWOT model, including converting volumes from m³ to liters (L), flows from m³/day and m³/s to L/day, and hydrological data from mm/day to L/day (by multiplying with the appropriate regional surface).

An example of the processed time series (river discharge Q in m³/day) is shown in Figure 60.

Figure 60: Input data for discharge of the IJzer. Negative discharge values are converted to zero.

For further analysis, a baseline (reference) case that represents present-day system reality is formulated, along with several scenarios featuring the use of water-smart technologies. All scenarios use a common topology file to allow for recursive running (Figure 59), where some components (such as the WW reuse) are only conditionally used. The following assumptions are used for all scenarios:

- The IJzer river is the sole raw water intake source to the WPC De Blankaart storage basin, with other secondary sources considered too small to contribute to intakes significantly.
- The model extent includes components relevant to the Woumen DW production facility, as well as urban water demand components. Other regional natural systems (e.g., the polder system) are excluded but treated in the supplementary Regional Analysis.
- The drinking water production capacity is constant throughout the year and set at 40000 m³/d. The actual daily capacity reaches this value, unless: (a.) there are intake availability issues due to low discharge, (b.) the intake source salinity level reaches values higher than 180 mg/L, where production stops and the intake capacity is set to zero. This capacity threshold S_{thr} is a model parameter (Table 19) that can be altered by water-smart technologies, such as the use of CCRO.

- The Woumen unit has a maximum storage capacity of $3 \cdot 10^6$ m³, which is determined by its 60-ha area and maximum allowable water level.

An overview of the parameters assumed by UWOT is shown in Table 19.

Table 19: Parameters for UWOT and the reference situation for the Woumen case.

Parameters for the UWOT modelling of Woumen DW system	
DW optimal production capacity	40000 m ³ /d
Storage basin area	600000 m ²
Maximum storage basin water depth d_{max}	5.5 m
Maximum volume of storage basin	$3.3 \cdot 10^6$ m ³
Initial volume of storage basin	$1.8 \cdot 10^6$ m ³
Production rules	Production capacity set to optimal unless: (a.) incoming river discharge $Q < 40000$ m ³ /d or (b.) incoming river salinity $S < S_{thr}$
Salinity threshold S_{thr} for baseline (reference) case	180 mg/L
WW reuse rate at baseline (reference) case	0

Mechelen

Following the data inventurisation process described in Section 6.2.3, the data is pre-processed to be inserted into the model and a UWOT model topology with all needed system components to represent the system of Mechelen is designed. The system corresponds to the RWH pilot being in operation and receiving runoff from the serviced area. The model is a representation of the regional water system, thus representing water fluxes (rainfall, runoff, retention, and coverage of subirrigation demands) in a simplified way. Flows are calculated on a daily timestep for the period 1-1-2006 to 31-12-2022, to be consistent with the Regional Analysis tool. The input data that is needed is described in Table 18. The input data consists of two meteorological variables: potential evaporation and precipitation, as well as the technical characteristics of the retention basin, which are provided by the LL regional stakeholders.

Figure 61: UWOT topology schematic of the Mechelen (RWH basin) case.

For the analysis in UWOT, the baseline (reference) scenario considers the retention basin being operational under the case of implementation with sub-irrigation, i.e., connecting the outlet of the retention basin with a sub-irrigated area, with a set maximum daily subirrigation capacity Q_{sub} . The assumption is made that the retention basin is used to cover (part of) the evapotranspiration demands of a cultivation (using a single crop type) in a subirrigation area A_{sub} . The equivalent crop demands are thus calculated as $D_{sub} = C \cdot PET \cdot A_{sub}$, where C is the crop coefficient (similar to calculations as per FAO), which is typically ranging from 0.90 to 1.10-1.25. Seasonal variability in the crops (growth cycles) is not taken into account, and a constant state of crops along the year is assumed. Open water evaporation on the basin is considered small relative to other fluxes (such as inflows and the subirrigation discharge) and is not taken into account. For the urban areas that contribute to rainwater harvesting, 20% of the precipitation is considered to be evaporating. Moreover, the area is split between impervious areas (that fully contribute to runoff, without infiltration, following the interception and evaporation losses), and pervious areas that have a specific infiltration capacity. An overview of the parameters for the Mechelen UWOT topology can be seen in Table 20.

Table 20: Parameters for UWOT and the reference situation for the Mechelen case.

Parameters for the UWOT modelling of Mechelen RWH system	
Total urban areas* serviced by retention basin A_{urban}	120775 m ² *reflects combined sewer drainage area in Mechelen
Impervious to total ratio	40%
Urban drainage area, impervious $A_{urban, imp}$	48310 m ²
Urban drainage area, pervious $A_{urban, prv}$	72465 m ²
Urban drainage area, pervious soil capacity	200 mm
Urban drainage area, pervious soil capacity (initial value)	50 mm
Filter (pretreatment) capacity for RWH unit to retention basin	500 m ³ /day

Subirrigation network capacity Q_{sub}	100 m ³ /ha/day
Retention basin infiltration rate	0.14% of maximum basin volume
Reservoir volume V_{basin}	2188 m ³
Reservoir volume V_{basin}, initial value	1000 m ³
Reference case crop factor C	0.9
Irrigated area $A_{\text{irrigation}}$	83000 m ²

6.2.4.2 Regional analysis setup and application

Woumen

For the regional analysis of the Woumen case, a system dynamics model was developed (Figure 62). The regional analysis consists of four subsystems: the IJzer (top), the polder system (middle), the drinking water production system (bottom) and the WWTP (right). The model represents the water stocks and flows in the system over time in a simplified way, as well as part of the chloride flows. Flows are calculated on a daily timestep for the period 1-1-2006 to 31-12-2020.

Input data for the regional analysis are described in Table 17 and streamflow (discharge values) of the IJzer are shown in Figure 60. The input data consist of meteorological variables and characteristics of the hydrology in the area (discharge values). In Table 21, the values for the different parameters in the regional analysis are given.

A reference situation and several scenarios have been explored for the regional analysis. We have assumed that no water intake from the IJzer can take place when negative discharges occur (due to seawater intrusion). Negative values were therefore converted to zero (Figure 60). A minimum environmental flow was not taken into account. Additional water from sources other than the IJzer (the Blankaartvijver and Driekappelvijver) is not included in the regional analyses, because these flows are small compared to the intake from the IJzer. In the reference situation, the IJzer is the only water source and water intake to the storage basin is stopped when salinity values are higher than 180 mg/l. The desired drinking water production is kept constant throughout the year at 40 000 m³/d.

The following scenarios were included in the regional analysis:

1. Reuse of effluent. All available water from the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) in the area, is used as an additional water source for drinking water. Water quality of the effluent and the effect on the minimum environmental flow were not taken into account.
2. Implementation of CCRO system. To overcome issues with high salinity values in the IJzer a CCRO system is installed parallel to the existing treatment. The fraction of water treated with the CCRO system depends on the salinity values in the storage basin. The water that reaches the production station cannot exceed salinity values of 180 mg/l. If the salinity level in the storage basin is higher than 180 mg/l, the fraction of water treated with the CCRO system depends on the actual salinity level. Water from the existing treatment process is mixed with the outflow from the CCRO system to ensure the salinity level remains below the threshold before entering the production process. When the salinity levels in the storage basin are lower

than 180 mg/l, 10% of the water is treated by the CCRO system to minimize the flow but avoid standstill of the system. In this scenario, there is no intake criterium for the intake of water from the IJzer to the storage basin.

3. Implementation of both measures. Effluent is used as additional source for drinking water, the specific treatment of the effluent is not modelled. A CCRO system is installed for the intake from the storage basin. The measures are implemented with the same assumptions as in scenario 1 and 2.

Figure 62: Regional analysis for the Woumen case. Blue: semi-natural water system, purple: human water system; boxes are stocks, coloured lines are flows; grey/no boxes: system characteristics, constants and output; green boxes: input

Table 21: Parameters and assumptions for regional analysis of the reference situation for the Woumen case.

Parameters drinking water system	
Intake criterium salinity	180 mg/l
Area storage basin	60 ha
Maximum depth basin	5 m
Production capacity	40000 m ³ /d
Production	Intake from the storage basin decreases when the basin is <80% full, reducing to 0 when the basin is 20% full (1m water depth)
Production loss existing treatment	5%
Fraction water to CCRO	0
CCRO recovery fraction	90%
Parameters wastewater system	
Fraction reuse	0
Parameters polder system	
Area polder (managed water level)	1300 ha
Surface level	3 m TAW
Areal fraction surface water	4%; estimated from topographic maps
Ditch bottom level	1.7 m TAW; assumed 1.3 m below surface level following van der Gaast (2006)
Maximum water storage root zone	5.4 cm (available water clay soil (Staring B11) between wilting point and field capacity 0.18 cm ³ /cm ³ (Heinen et al. 2020); root zone depth grass 30 cm)
Evapotranspiration factor	Reduces when soil water is <80% of field capacity decreasing to 0 at the wilting point
Capillary rise	Varies between 0 and 4 mm/d depending on root zone water storage and groundwater depth, based on critical z values from Heinen et al. (2020), soil B11
Groundwater storage coefficient	0.1
Drainage resistance	40 days
Target water level	2.7 m TAW (level most of year, overeenkomst peilbeheer 2019)
Pumping capacity polder discharge	1 m ³ /s. In reality 2 m ³ /s (overeenkomst peilbeheer), adapted to ensure normal model behaviour

Mechelen

For the regional analysis of the Mechelen case, a system dynamics model was developed as well (Figure 62). The model represents the water stocks and flows in the system over time in a simplified way. Water quality was not taken into account for this case. Flows are calculated on a daily timestep for the period 1-1-2006 to 31-12-2022.

Input data for the regional analysis are described in 6.2.3. The input data consist of two meteorological variables: potential evaporation and precipitation. In Table 20 the values for the different parameters in the regional analysis are given.

A reference situation and two scenarios have been explored for the regional analysis. In the reference situation, it is assumed that precipitation from the region leads to runoff to the Oude Tantelaerloop. We considered a runoff coefficient of 0.8, meaning 20% of the precipitation is lost, for example due to evaporation, before reaching the stream. In the regional analysis, a spatial component is not included, which means all precipitation reaches the stream in the same timestep (daily). The stormwater retention basin is simplified to a rectangular basin with straight edges instead of sloping edges. We explored two scenarios with the proposed measures:

1. Implementation of a stormwater retention basin. Precipitation is stored in a retention reservoir. The reservoir loses water through evaporation and infiltration to the groundwater. Operational rules to optimize the available storage in the system were not taken into account.
2. Implementation of a stormwater retention basin in combination with subirrigation for agriculture. We have assumed that water is pumped into the subirrigation system throughout the year with a capacity of 830 m³/d to supply an area of 83 000 m² (100 m³/ha per day). Again, optimal management of the reservoir and the subirrigation system was not taken into account.

Figure 63: Regional analysis for the Mechelen case. Blue: semi-natural water system; boxes are stocks, coloured lines are flows; grey boxes: system characteristics, constants and output, green boxes: input.

Table 22: Parameters and assumptions for regional analysis of the reference situation for the Mechelen case.

Parameters stormwater reservoir	
Area storage basin	2188 m ²
Maximum depth basin	1 m
Area connected	121000 m ²
Bottom level reservoir	7.5 m TAW
Infiltration reservoir	20 mm/d
Parameters subirrigation system	
Pumping capacity	830 m ³ /d
Maximum groundwater level	9.1 m TAW (-0.5m below surface level)
Parameters agricultural area	
Area subirrigation	83 000 m ²
Surface level	9.6 m TAW
Groundwater storage coefficient	0.1
Crop type	Grass
Ditch bottom level	8.3 m TAW; assumed 1.3 m below surface level following van der Gaast (2006)
Drainage level	8.6 m TAW; assumed 1 m below surface level
Maximum water storage root zone	5.4 cm (Water content clay soil (Staring B11, Heinen et al. 2020) at pF=250 cm about 0.49, at pF=16000 cm about 0.32, giving a water availability of 0.18, assuming a rooting zone depth of 30 cm giving 5.4 cm of water storage capacity in root zone)
Evapotranspiration factor	Reduces when soil water is <80% of field capacity until it reaches 0 at the wilting point
Drainage resistance drainage system	5 days
Drainage resistance brook	40 days
Groundwater level deep groundwater	6.5 m TAW
Resistance deep groundwater	500 d

6.2.4.3 QMRA+ set up and application

The QMRA+ tool was used in the Woumen case to explore water safety implications of various concepts involving the use of effluent to supplement the drinking water supply. Options studied included supplementing the Blankaart raw water reservoir with post-treated effluent and direct drinking water production from effluent to supplement the current drinking water supply. Various combinations of treatment processes were evaluated for these purposes. The risk assessment was mostly based on literature data for effluent quality and treatment process efficacy for pathogen removal or inactivation. Limited data for fecal indicator organisms from the current surface water source, the IJzer, were available to estimate the concentration of pathogenic microorganisms.

The QMRA+ tool was also used to demonstrate that the upgraded drinking water treatment is capable to produce safe drinking water from the reservoir water.

6.2.5 Results

6.2.5.1 UWOT results

Woumen

For the case of Woumen, UWOT is used as a stress-testing platform to explore if the current system implementation can satisfy present-day demands. Moreover, stress-testing is extended to predict how vulnerable the current system is towards changes in factors such as the river intake salinity and regional demand, as well as to explore if water-smart technologies can alleviate these (potential) vulnerabilities. To do this, UWOT requires a water supply strategy (defined by the drinking water production rules seen in Table 19), as well as an assumption on the regional demands that are served in the Woumen area. As demand data are not available from any source (third-party sources or stakeholder groups), the following alternative (i.e., mutually exclusive) assumptions are made on the demand side to generate the corresponding demand time series which are required as UWOT input:

- A **variable demand** assumption, which assumes that a similar variable quantity to the observed - and available, as input - WWTP effluent is requested from clients. The main attributes of the variable demand assumption are shown in Figure 64.
- A **constant demand** assumption, which assumes that a set daily quantity D_s of water (in m^3/day) is requested by regional clients.

Variable demand time series attributes

mean value μ	11260	m^3/day
standard deviation σ	6998	m^3/day

Figure 64: Variable demand time series, cloned from the WWTP effluent data.

The variable demand assumption, while relying on available WW effluent data and taking into account daily variability, has limitations. Firstly, it implicitly assumes that the same area serviced by the WWTP is also serviced by the DW utility. This may be untrue, as the DW facility potentially serves third-party areas in an inter-connected (looped) supply network. Moreover, WWTP effluent data might be affected by rainfall in combined sewer overflow events, leading to deviations between drinking water and

observed wastewater. To counteract these limitations, both assumptions (variable and constant) are employed in the stress-testing analysis.

Stress-testing is based on using UWOT to perform simulations at the daily timescale in the system and its components, thus measuring how each component behaves in terms of flow variability, overflows, time points with low or empty storage levels etc. With a time window from 2006 to the end of 2020, a total of 5479 daily timesteps are used per simulation, with UWOT returning time series of flows and water storage for each simulation. An example of the returned time series is given in Figure 65, under the assumption of a constant regional demand $D_s = 25000 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$, with the upper panel showing DW available in the basin, followed by model logs of the basin being under stress and failing to deliver water, as well as the actual water deficits. This is output in the form of daily time series for a single simulation; one may observe that the stressed states correlate with the failure states, even though an event which leads to low water levels might not necessarily translate to an actual system failure and inability to deliver water.

Figure 65: Snapshots of the UWOT model results for the Woumen case, under the assumption of constant demands set to $25,000 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$.

Once these time series are returned by the model, the output data is post-processed to assess the percentage of time the intake basin was under stress (i.e., meaning the volume of available drinking water being alarmingly low) or completely empty (i.e., meaning no availability of drinking water to satisfy demands). Evidently, to make these considerations, one must consider how exactly “low levels” in the basin volume are defined, which has a degree of subjectivity. For instance, in the upper panel of Figure 65, the stress threshold (i.e., red line in upper panel) is arbitrarily set to $30\% V_{\max}$, which results in specific patterns for the stress logs in the panel that follows. To overcome this subjectivity, the results are instead presented in the format of “stress curves” (Figure 66), i.e., a graphical representation of different volume thresholds in the basin water volume (normalised in $[0,1]$ and expressed as the ratio of V/V_{\max} , in the x-axis) against the amount of time (%) that these or lower volumes are observed (i.e. $P(V \leq V)$) in the y-axis. A stress curve can be thus perceived as the analogue

of a Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) for the water basin and the intake system in general, starting from [0,0] and reaching [1,1]. Its interpretation is intuitive, as the further the curve lies towards the lower right part of the graph and the $x=1$ line (i.e., the tank being full), the more secure and less vulnerable the system is. For further visual help, we also depict stress curves along with the $x=y$ line, which represents a system that empties in a linear fashion, with a light grey colour.

As a first step of the stress-testing analysis, the effects of an increase in regional demands to the present-day Woumen drinking water system are explored. This increase could be attributed, for instance, to a change in regional population, or a change in the supply strategy of the utility to include and serve additional areas. The results, in the form of stress curves, under both assumptions of variable or constant demand are shown in Figure 66, where:

- the left panel shows the assumption of variable demand being increased by a set percentage, up to a triple amount (increase by 200%). In terms of mean values, the range of increase is from 11260 m³/day (present-day assumption) to 33780 m³/day (200% increase), which is deemed reasonable, considering the present-day treatment capacity of 40000 m³/day.
- The right panel shows the assumption of constant demand starting from 10000 m³/day and being incrementally increased by 5000 m³/day up to 40000 m³/day, which is equal to the drinking water production capacity.

The results of Figure 65 demonstrate that the basin continues to operate well under demands in the range of 10000-25000 m³/day, but begins to experience significantly more stress and, eventually, failure for larger values. Demand values >30000 m³/day translate to disturbed operational states in the system, thus rendering the system prone to failure, as less than 50% of its maximum volume is available at more than 50% of the simulation time under both demand assumptions. In these disturbed states, there is also significant failure in delivering drinking water to clients in the range of 15%-40% of the time.

Figure 66: UWOT stress-testing of Woumen against an increase in regional demands, under the assumption of a variable demand that is being increased by a set percentage (left panel) or a constant demand being incrementally increased (right panel).

As a next step of the stress-testing analysis, the effects of increased salinity in the river IJzer source are explored. For this and to conserve space, the analysis focuses on the constant demand assumption only, assuming constant demands of 15000 and 25000 m³/day which correspond to normal operational states of the basin (see also Figure 66). River salinity in the source for dry months is then increased by an increment of 25% up to a doubling of salinity rates (increase by 100%). The results demonstrate that, for low water demand values, the drinking water system can mitigate a worsening salinity future without significant loss of reliability or failure rates. However, if water demand requests become significant (e.g., right panel of Figure 67), then any worsening salinity future will translate to significant stress levels and failure rates (>10% for significant (>50%) salinity increase). This means that the drinking water system is particularly prone to the combination of worsening salinity levels paired with increased demand needs.

Figure 67: UWOT stress-testing of Woumen against % increase in river salinity, under the assumption of two different constant demand rates D_s of 15000 m³/day (left panel) and 25000 (m³/day).

Besides highlighting the vulnerabilities of the current state of the drinking water production system, the stress-testing analysis can assess the efficiency of water-smart technologies for Woumen. Two proposed measures (as discussed and prioritized by regional stakeholders in previous meetings) are considered:

- The **reuse of wastewater (WW) effluent** from the Woumen WW treatment plant (WWTP). To proceed with this scenario a steady reuse rate Q_r (in m³/day) is assumed, meaning that (up to) Q_r of WW daily are treated at an acceptable level and added to the production capacity of the system. The daily amount can be lower if the WW effluent does not exceed that reuse rate, i.e., in case of low flows. Three different reuse rates Q_r are considered: 5000 m³/day, 10000 m³/day, and 20000 m³/day. It is noted that the mean flow rates range typically up to 12000 m³/day, so the first two values can be considered realistic, while the third one is an upper limit reachable only on certain timeframes.
- The installation of a **Closed-Circuit Reverse Osmosis (CCRO) unit** as part of the drinking water production facility in Woumen. This added treatment step leads to uninterrupted drinking water production for intakes with higher salinity. As a result, it is assumed that the CCRO

installation leads to an increased salinity threshold S_{thr} compared to the baseline (reference) case. Other factors, such as the CCRO efficiency or capacity are not considered in this analysis but are instead treated in the Regional Analysis. Three different increased thresholds are considered for the analysis, representing different CCRO layouts: 280 mg/L, 380 mg/L and 480 mg/L.

For both of these water-smart technology scenarios, constant demand rates of 15000 m³/day, 25000 m³/day and 35000 m³/day are considered, representing different levels of light, medium and heavy use of the production facility to cover potential regional demands.

Figure 68: UWOT stress-testing of Woumen for different WW reuse scenarios, under the assumption of different constant demand rates D_s of 15000, 25000 and 35000 m³/day.

Concerning the measure of WW reuse, the results can be seen in Figure 68, where (a) the continuous line represents present-day conditions, without any reuse, and (b) the dotted lines represent different WW reuse rates (5000 m³/day, 10000 m³/day, 20000 m³/day). Figure 68 shows that the introduction of WW reuse improves the reliability of the DW production unit considerably, particularly for the

medium and heavy demand cases of 25000 m³/day and 35000 m³/day. Interestingly, differences between larger reuse rates are not significant under the light and medium demand assumption, indicating that there is no added value by investing in large WW reuse capacities. A higher WW reuse capacity (>10000 m³/day) only becomes important if daily demands become high; in that case, a mostly empty and unreliable drinking water production unit (continuous, teal line) is converted to a reliable one, with system failure rates lowering from >20% to 8-10% and with the basin emptying with a lower rate than the linear equivalent (grey dotted x=y line).

Concerning the measure of CCRO, the results are demonstrated in Figure 69 (for present-day salinity conditions in the source) and Figure 70 (for 50% worsening salinity conditions in the source). It can be observed that the introduction of added treatment with the CCRO system improves the reliability of the drinking water production system under regular regional demands (15000 – 25000 m³/day) but becomes less efficient under the high demand scenario. Moreover, higher threshold scenarios prove to be less efficient than the scenario that leads to $S_{thr} = 280$ mg/L and even partly coincide with the lower threshold scenario in the case of high demands in Figure 69. This means that an added investment in large CCRO capacities has to be significant (i.e., raising S_{thr} considerably higher than the 280-480 mg/L zone) to be translated to improved reliability to the system.

Figure 69: UWOT stress-testing of Woumen for different CCRO layouts that lead to three different production thresholds, under present-day salinity conditions in IJzer.

Under deteriorating salinity conditions (Figure 70), the importance of a CCRO system increases, as it is able to drastically reduce the stress curve to cover the normal range of regional demands (15000-25000 m³/day). However, and similarly to Figure 69, the measure appears to be less efficient in the high demand case of 35000 m³/day. In that case, all layouts manage to decrease a 40% failure rate of the reference case to 18%-22%, but the stress curves continue to indicate a highly stressed system that empties rapidly.

Figure 70: UWOT stress-testing of Vrouwen for different CCRO layouts that lead to three different production thresholds, under deteriorated salinity conditions in Ijzer (salinity increase by 50%).

Mechelen

The goal of the retention basin in Mechelen is twofold: (a) to mitigate flooding issues and (b) to increase water availability for agriculture in the region. For both of these functions, the Mechelen retention basin is stress-tested and the response of the retention system is evaluated against variability in the urban area used for harvesting, under the assumption that more areas with similar rainfall-runoff characteristics are introduced to the existing RWH system.

Firstly, UWOT simulates the response of the retention basin for the 14 years of simulation at the daily scale. The results, shown as daily time series in Figure 71, show that the retention basin has periods of both full and empty storage, which appears to be seasonal and is affected by (a.) the variability in crop evapotranspiration demands, which are higher during summer, warm months, and (b.) the availability of incoming water in terms of runoff. It is noted, at this point, that the results of Figure 71 reflect the implementation of the basin without any operational rules; the introduction of any extra rules (e.g., discharging before the anticipation of flood events, based on forecasts) will significantly affect basin storage levels and overflows.

Figure 71: Snapshots of the UWOT model results (retention basin response) for the Mechelen case.

Seasonal effects are further demonstrated by aggregating and presenting results in the monthly average level. Figure 72 shows the monthly variability in multiple aspects of the retention basin system in terms of average water stored per month, modelled runoff and average crop demand deficits. In terms of basin water storage, the basin appears to be filling in winter months and almost empty during the summer season, where the mitigation of runoff (from convective events) also is higher. The reduction in runoff appears to be significant across the entire year (comparing the baseline runoff (before placing the retention basin), in light blue, with the post-basin runoff, in grey), and more profound in spring, summer and autumn months. Again, the introduction of operational rules might change this

seasonality and increase effectiveness, in case seasonal rules (i.e., higher discharges during winter months) are applied.

Notably, the retention basin is empty during summer months, resulting in crop demand deficits. The average crop demand deficits correspond to the net effect of using water from the retention basin; they are thus covered by groundwater reserves or other sources beyond the scope of the model (and are partly covered by the infiltration from the retention basin), or they are mitigated by a loss of crop yields due to the inability to provide an amount equal to the potential evapotranspiration of the cultivated area. More elaborate effects of subirrigation on groundwater cannot be captured through UWOT due to model limitations and are thus not included as part of the results; instead, they are explored as part of the regional analysis, which discusses the effects of the retention basin to groundwater tables extensively.

Figure 72: Monthly variability in the Mechelen retention basin in terms of storage, runoff and coverage of crop demands.

The effect of introducing larger urban areas upstream is explored in Figure 73. In this analysis, the retention basin keeps the same design but the serviced urban area upstream (i.e., the area whose discharge is led to the retention basin) grows by 20%, 40% and 60% respectively. The ratio of pervious and impervious areas remains the same, as the household types in the area are uniform. Along with this increase, the pretreatment discharge capacity to the area is increased from 500 m³/day to 600, 800 and 1000 m³/day, respectively, to accommodate larger runoff influxes. The results show that the introduction of larger inflows has a beneficial effect on crop demands, leading to lower deficits; however, it comes with a trade-off to the flood-proofing capacity of the retention basin, as the basin remains fuller across multiple months and has a loss in its runoff reduction capacity (around 2%-25%, depending on the month).

Figure 73: Monthly variability in the retention basin with the introduction of larger harvesting areas (20% - 60% increase in serviced urban areas).

6.2.5.2 Regional analysis results

Woumen

In the reference situation, the salinity levels in the IJzer frequently led to intake stops from the river to the storage basin (Figure 74). Because intake for drinking water production from the basin is reduced as soon as the basin reaches 80% capacity (assumption in the regional analysis), the intake stops from the river had a large influence on the total drinking water production. Actual production was lower than the desired production in almost every summer, except the summer of 2008. Especially in 2011, 2017 and 2019, intake stops due to high salinity levels in the IJzer led to lower drinking water production.

Figure 74: Drinking water production in the reference situation and salinity levels in the IJzer (measured).

The proposed measures to make the drinking water production more robust have different effects. In all scenarios, the total amount of drinking water produced increased when compared to the reference situation (Figure 75 and Figure 76). However, actual production was still lower than the desired production (fraction production lower than 1) in many summers during the time period. In total over the entire time period, the desired drinking water production was reached 70.4% of the time in the reference period, for scenario 1, 2 and 3 this percentage increased to respectively 72.3%, 77.4% and 79.1%.

Figure 76 shows the fraction of production in more detail for the last years in the time period. The largest increase in drinking water production is found when both measures are implemented (scenario 3). Reuse of effluent only (scenario 1) has the lowest increase in production. During dry periods, the amount of water available from the WWTP decreases while at the same time the water quality of the IJzer deteriorated. That means water availability from both sources decreased in dry periods, leading to less drinking water production. Installation of the CCRO system only (scenario 2) led to higher

drinking water production compared to the reference situation and scenario 1, but less production compared to scenario 3. In scenario 2 more water was taken from the IJzer, because the water quality did not lead to intake stops. However, the discharge of the IJzer was too low to sustain the drinking water production during dry periods. This is also the case in scenario 3, although the production in this scenario was highest, because effluent was available during the dry periods, albeit in smaller quantities.

Figure 75: Fraction of the desired drinking water production for the reference situation and different scenarios for complete time series.

Figure 76: Fraction of the desired drinking water production for the reference situation and the different scenarios for part of the time series.

The implemented measures did not only impact the total drinking water production, but also had different effects on the total water intake from the IJzer to the storage basin. The total water intake from the IJzer per year was lower in scenario 1 (water reuse) compared to the reference situation (Figure 77). For scenario 2 (CCRO system), the total water intake was higher every year, because the high salinity levels did not lead to intake stops anymore. When both measures are implemented (scenario 3), water intake is lower in most years, because the reuse of effluent replaces the water from the IJzer. However, in years when the IJzer had very high salinity levels, 2011 and 2017 (Figure 74), total water intake in scenario 3 was higher than the reference situation, because water from the IJzer was taken over a much longer period when the CCRO system was available.

Figure 77: Total water intake per year from the IJzer for the reference situation and the different scenarios.

When both measures are implemented, the total drinking water production originates from three different water sources: effluent, water treated in the existing treatment system, water treated with the CCRO system. In scenario 3, the main water source was still the existing treatment, followed by effluent and the CCRO system (Figure 78). The amount of effluent clearly fluctuated throughout the year, with higher amounts available in winter than in summer. The amount of water treated with the CCRO system was small due to the assumption made that 10% of all water from the storage basin is treated in the CCRO system during periods when water quality is not an issue. When salinity levels were too high, the contribution of the CCRO system to the total production clearly increased (2011, 2017, 2019, 2020). The exact division of the water between the existing treatment and the CCRO system is not known, but this would obviously affect the division between the sources.

Figure 78: Division of the total production of drinking water across the different sources for scenario 3.

Mechelen

The aim of the stormwater retention basin is to prevent problems with flooding in urban areas and to increase the water availability for agriculture in the region. The implementation of a stormwater basin led to a strong reduction in runoff to the Oude Tantaerloop, especially when combined with subirrigation (Figure 79). For the complete period the average runoff to the stream was 71 582 m³/y for the situation without retention basin, 57 888 m³/y for scenario 1 and 5 632 m³/y for scenario 2.

Figure 79: Runoff from precipitation to the Oude Tantelaerloop for the reference situation and after implementation of the retention basin (scenario 1 and 2).

Peaks in daily runoff were also reduced in the scenarios. For the reference situation the peak runoff during the entire period was 6 091 m³/d, this was reduced to 6 047 m³/d in scenario 1 and to 4 741 m³/d in scenario 2. The reduction in peak values was limited in scenario 1, because the basin was filled to capacity most of the time due to the lack of management rules in the regional analysis (Figure 80). The basin was only emptied during very dry periods (2018). When the water is used for subirrigation (scenario 2), more storage was available in the basin and thus peak values and total runoff to the stream could be reduced further. This indicates that proper management of the retention basin and/or use of the stored water is needed to prevent flooding. When operational rules of the basin are optimized, for example, by emptying the basin based on the weather forecast, the peak values can be reduced more efficiently.

Figure 80: Volume of water in the stormwater retention basin for the two scenarios.

Water from the stormwater retention basin can be used to irrigate nearby agricultural fields through subirrigation. This increases the water availability for agriculture and affects more components of the water system than implementing a retention basin alone. When the water from the retention basin was used for subirrigation, groundwater levels below the fields increased during the entire period (Figure 81). Groundwater levels showed the largest increase during winter with a maximum increase of 1.45 m. During summer, groundwater levels increased by around 0.5 m, with a minimum increase of 0.06 m in the spring of 2020.

Figure 81: Groundwater levels in the situation without subirrigation (scenario 1, equal to reference situation) and for the situation with subirrigation (scenario 2).

The increase in groundwater levels had a positive effect on the crops. We have used the actual evapotranspiration to illustrate the effect on crops, because more evapotranspiration indicates better crop growth and thus higher yields. Subirrigation led to a higher actual evapotranspiration during the entire period (Figure 82). The average yearly evapotranspiration increased from 351 mm/y in scenario 1 to 406 mm/y in scenario 2. In both scenarios, the average potential evapotranspiration of 496 mm/y was not reached due to water limitations. There is a clear difference in the effect of subirrigation between the years. Yearly average precipitation in the region is 738 mm/y. In a wet year, like 2016 (precipitation 905 mm), actual evapotranspiration was almost equal to potential evapotranspiration for both scenarios. In a dry year, like 2018 (precipitation 527 mm), the actual evapotranspiration in scenario 2 was much higher than in scenario 1, at 349 mm and 271 mm respectively.

Figure 82: Yearly potential evapotranspiration based on observations (input) and yearly actual evapotranspiration for the different scenarios (scenario 1 is equal to reference situation).

The increased groundwater levels can also impact the drainage to streams. The extra drainage to streams caused by the subirrigation in scenario 2 was limited (Figure 83), because groundwater levels were still relatively deep (in wet periods still about 1 m below surface level). It was also assumed that the groundwater drained towards the Dorpsloop and not to urban areas. That means the extra drainage did not increase the risk for urban flooding.

Figure 83: Drainage from the groundwater to the stream in scenario 2 and measured precipitation (input).

6.2.5.3 QMRA+ results

The QMRA+ tool was used to assess the safety various options for combinations of treatment processes shown in Table 23. Results from the application of QMRA+ tool showed that the current source, the IJzer river, contains significant fecal contamination. Therefore, the post-treatment of effluent for supply to the raw water reservoir can be relatively limited. This wouldn't affect the current contamination level in the reservoir. In most cases the post-treated effluent contained fewer pathogens than the current source. One example of QMRA+ output is shown in Figure 84. The boxplots indicate the variability and uncertainty about the annual risk of infection from treated effluent. This demonstrates that the predicted risk is several orders of magnitude below the health target of 1 infection per 10,000 persons per year as indicated by the red line.

Although chemical risk assessment wasn't part of the study, a typical post treatment system for effluent was evaluated for the effect on microbial drinking water quality. Such an extensive post-treatment would (in theory) be sufficient to directly produce safe drinking water, according to the QMRA+ tool. This demonstrates that integrating microbial and chemical risk assessments is needed to find safe and efficient solutions for effluent reuse.

Limitations of the study were mostly due to the lack of site-specific data on actual pathogen concentrations in the various sources (current river IJzer or effluent) and data on actual treatment performance for pathogen removal and inactivation in the current drinking water system. Obtaining this data would require a long-term monitoring program for pathogens which is costly and therefore not feasible within the constraints of the project. Pilot research to assess the efficacy of post-treatment options for effluent would provide more adequate, site-specific, data for the risk assessment.

Table 23: Studied treatment and supplement options and the assessed risk according to the QMRA+ tool expressed as log of infection per person per year. Values not meeting the Dutch guideline value of 4 are highlighted in red.

Scenario	UF	RO	RO50%	NF	UV	GAC	CONV	IC12	RSF	GAC	CI2	DAF	DRSF	AOP	UV	RO	Infectie			DALY			
																	B	V	P	B	V	P	
1 Effluent huidig- Drinkwater huidig							X	X	X	X	X							2,6	0,7	0,1	5,4	2,8	2,9
2 Effluent optie1-Drinkwater huidig	X	X			X	X	X	X	X	X	X							19	14	14	22	16	17
2h Effluent optie UF-UV - Drinkwater huidig	X	0			X	X	X	X	X	X	X							10	6,8	7	13	8,9	9,9
3h Effluent optie UV - Drinkwater huidig	0		0		X	X	X	X	X	X	X							7,1	4,8	3	10	7	5,9
16 IJzer-Blankaart-Drinkwater huidig							X	X	X	X	X							4,1	1,3	3,2	7	3,4	6,2
17 IJzer-Blankaart-Drinkwater nieuw										2X	X	X	X	X	X			6,4	5,4	4,8	9,3	7,5	7,7
18 Effluent-RSF- Drinkwater nieuw			RSF							2X	X	X	X	X	X			7,2	5,2	3,5	10	7,4	6,5
19 Effluent-NF-Drinkwater nieuw				X						2X	X	X	X	X	X			12	11	8,3	14	12	11

Figure 84: Output of the QMRA+ tool for scenario 19, effluent post treatment with nanofiltration and the upgraded drinking water treatment. Red line indicates the Dutch guideline value of 1 infection per 10,000 persons per year.

6.3 Lessons extracted

6.3.1 Lessons from the UWOT analysis

Woumen

- The present-day drinking water production system in Woumen appears to be under stress and is particularly susceptible to deteriorating changes in both salinity (e.g., due to lower discharge in IJzer) and demands (e.g., due to the addition of clients, regional immigration or added industry needs). The system can presently cover daily average demands of 30000 m³/day without having a significant failure and emptying rate. The maximum theoretical capacity of 40000 m³/day cannot be met with equal demands without the basin emptying.

- In the case of worsening salinity, the basin will be able to operate without disturbance only for low demand requests (10000-15000 m³/day). A combination of high regional demands with worsening salinity rates will quickly render the drinking water production system, with significant failure rates (>10%).
- Both measures (WW reuse and CCRO) improve the water security of Woumen assuming demands remain at reasonable levels. However, the effectiveness of the measures is limited when regional demands become high (>30000 m³/day). The measure of WW reuse appears to be more efficient when regional demands increase, given the considered measure design ranges.
- The results indicate that the most efficient way to secure the system against future stresses is to combine both measures (i.e., WW reuse from the local WWTP and CCRO), without (over)relying on one solution, especially if high demand scenarios are considered.
- The model is limited by the lack of data, particularly on the demand side, as well as the CCRO implementation specifics. More information on these datasets would make the stress-testing analysis more accurate, particularly with regard to the actual, operational stress of the DW system. However, this limitation is mitigated by assuming multiple demand scenarios and exploring how the Woumen DW basin behaves under increasing urban water demands.

Mechelen

- The retention basin in Mechelen appears to fulfil the goal of flood-proofing the area, as it leads to runoff reduction rates that range from 22%-94% (depending on the month of reference). The values that are mentioned refer to the retention basin implementation without any operational rules; they can thus be further improved with the introduction of operational rules, e.g., emptying the basin during winter months and when anticipating flood events. The stormwater management tool (tool #22) was developed to implement these operational rules and ensure optimal use of the basin and collected stormwater.
- The design of the retention basin can accommodate an expansion in the serviced urban areas upstream, but with a compromise of its runoff reduction capacity of 30-40% for certain months. This will have a beneficial effect on subirrigation and may accommodate larger irrigated surfaces as well, but the trade-off with flood-proofing has to be taken into account, especially during autumn and winter.
- With regards to subirrigation, the basin appears to cover the majority of crop demands but comes with shortages in demand coverage in the summer months. This might lead to lower crop yields than the ones optimally planned for the given area; however, the crop demands could be covered by additional surface or groundwater sources.
- Considering the modelling of subirrigation, UWOT is limited with regard to predicting groundwater levels due to the lack of modelling vadose zone dynamics. The effects of subirrigation on groundwater are thus explored and discussed as part of the supplementary regional analysis.

6.3.2 Lessons from the regional analysis and the stormwater reuse management system

Woumen

- Implementation of the measures increases the total drinking water production and combining the two measures results in the highest production. In all scenarios, however, desired drinking water production could not be reached during dry periods, because not enough water is available in the IJzer and through effluent.
- Reuse of the WWTP effluent led to less water intake from the IJzer, however, this also means the water is not available in other places anymore. The contribution of the WWTP effluent to environmental flows in the larger region is not clear, so this would need to be investigated further.
- Installation of the CCRO system on the other hand led to increased water intake from the IJzer, which means less water will be available downstream especially during drier periods. This

extra water abstraction during a period when water quality is already deteriorating, might lead to more saltwater intrusion upstream. It was not possible to include this effect in the regional analysis, because a more detailed surface water model is needed.

Mechelen

- The stormwater retention basin was able to reduce the total runoff and peak runoff in the Oude Tanteleersloop, especially when the water was used for subirrigation. When the operational rules of the basin are optimized, peak values can be reduced even more.
- Water supplied through subirrigation to the agricultural fields led to higher groundwater levels and higher evapotranspiration values. Crop yields were increased.
- Excess water from the subirrigation partly left the system through drainage to surface water. However, this water left the system towards the Dorpsloop and therefore did not increase the risk of flooding in the urban areas near the Oude Tanteleersloop. When implementing the system in a different area, the extra drainage caused by higher groundwater levels should be considered to make sure the risk of flooding is not impacted.

Specifically, for the stormwater reuse management system (tool #21)⁴ which is part of D3.4, the lessons learned are the following:

- Identifying and disconnecting existing pollution sources from the storm water system can be tedious, but it is paramount to ensuring system performance and allowance.
- Further purification of the stormwater may not be required by law but can provide an additional advantage for further flexibilization of re-use scenarios. In addition to the legal perspective, the water quality should be judged from a risk assessment point of view.
- PLC providers are currently designing and commercializing inexpensive hardware while still complying with industrial safety standards, hardware delivery times and software support may still form bottlenecks, especially with regard to short-term implementation.
- Fully edge-computing-based implementation of local control remains a desirable but currently unrealistic goal. This leads to hybrid solutions, here a combination of Python as an edge-computing language and the configuration of I/O based on conventional PLC-setup-packages. The setup of simple edge-based OPC-servers may form a solution to this drawback if it remains unaddressed by the hardware providers.
- The incorporation of external rainfall forecast data may prove challenging, especially when anticipating multiple data providers: available data formats, subscription models and service level agreements may vary considerably.
- Depending on the cloud service provider, the cost for design and hosting online the data transformation and control service (here: Python-based Azure-Databricks notebooks running as scheduled batch workflows on a dedicated compute cluster) as well as data storage and querying may be considerable. Simple on-premises hosting could form a solution if the forecast data volume allows. This may require a technology change, especially for data storage formats and workflow organization (replacing Databricks by either local or self-hosted Jupyter-Notebooks, or pure Python).
- The required real-time data exchange between project partners and external parties (e.g., for weather forecasts) requires sound preparatory communication. Typically handled data formats may vary considerably. Emerging concepts, such as dataspace, may provide an apt solution to this challenge in the future.

⁴ The stormwater reuse management system (tool #21) is part of D3.4. Nevertheless, the preprocessing work and lessons learned are being documented in D3.5 as part of the LL work in order to provide a complete picture of the Flanders case since it is related with other tools.

6.3.3 Lessons from SuTRa and QMRA+

SuTRa tool was used to compute the microbial risks of Drinking Water Wells in a natural area. Firstly, the residence time between the source of contaminations and the groundwater well was computed as was the travel time. This required an update of the transport parameters, based on recent field investigations. The advantage of using the SuTRa tool over existing tools that are usually used to compute residence time (such as regional groundwater models) is that SuTRa allows for an explicit schematization of the well construction. Thus, high vertical flow velocities in the annulus of the well are taken into account more accurately. Figure 85 below depicts an example of the removal of pathogens from groundwater following infiltration from the surface during transport to a well.

Figure 85: Example of the removal of pathogens from groundwater following infiltration from the surface during transport to a well on the left side of the image. Note that concentration reduction is depicted on a 10log scale.

With regard to each link with QMRA+, SuTRa is a process-based model that provides insight into the removal of pathogens during soil passage. Soil passage is one of the many treatment steps that can be considered by QMRA+. SuTRa can thus provide more detailed insight into the removal efficiency of one of the treatment steps that is simulated by QMRA+. QMRA+ allows for site specific pathogen removal based on the outcomes of the SuTRa tool, making the risk estimate more specific to the studied situation.

6.4 Summary table of the Flanders LL

Table 24: Summary table for LL Flanders.

Title	Assessment of alternative water sources and increasing freshwater availability for drinking water and agriculture in Flanders
Description	<p>The smart stormwater reuse management system (tool #21) is used to control the outflow from the basin and the water distribution for irrigation to optimize the functioning of the basin for flood prevention and availability of water for irrigation during dry periods. There is a need to place these technological demonstrations in a broader context to assess how they can contribute to a more robust and smarter water system at a regional level. The regional analysis and UWOT (tool #22) were used to assess the demonstrations in their regional context with regard to their impact on water availability and resilience of the water system. Next to that, the potential to include alternative water sources while minimizing negative impact on local nature and environment in order to design a sustainable water supply for the future was analysed. The regional analysis was used to identify regional effects of changes in water supply and demand.</p> <p>A critical success factor for water reuse is the assessment and control of microbial safety risks. The QMRA+ (tool #26) is developed to support the design and assess the required treatment needed for water reuse. QMRA+ is a valuable tool for quantitative microbial risk assessment that can be used to assess existing purification systems and to help determine the design requirements of purification systems for e.g., alternative water sources with regards to microbial safety requirements. Within BWS, QMRA+ is used to help design the effluent reuse demonstration system by back casting the required removal rate. The SuTRa tool builds on microbial risk assessment to specifically model (plant) pathogen removal during subsurface passage of managed aquifer recharge and infiltration schemes. This helps determine the minimum design parameters and residence time required for pathogen removal. The outputs from SuTRa may support the regional analysis or similar studies in related projects by providing input parameters on subsurface passage if these are included in the conceptual design.</p>
Reference point	<p>Woumen: https://shorturl.at/mCUZ4 Mechelen: https://shorturl.at/ayEFP</p>
Location	LL Flanders combines case studies on smart alternative water solutions from different locations in Flanders. Extension of the drinking water production capacity and potential effluent reuse for drinking water is studied at the combined case studies of Woumen. Stormwater reuse for agriculture is studied in the city of Mechelen. The findings of the UWOT and regional analysis modelling can be used to put these local case studies in the regional context of Flanders.
Country (-ies)	Belgium, (UWOT is also applied in East Frisia, Germany)
URL	NA
Project	BWS
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water scarcity, • Limitations to water reuse due to high salinity/nitrates, • Untapped efficiency potential of water resources,

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High or increasing irrigation water demand for agriculture, • Water quality deterioration, • Usage of captured rainwater for non-potable (irrigation) uses, • Groundwater overexploitation, • Limitations to water reuse and recovery due to low acceptance.
Tools/Product / Services	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Stormwater reuse management system (#21) 2. Urban Water Optioneering Tool (#22) 3. QMRA+ for water reuse and agriculture (#26) 4. SuTRa (#31)
Technologies	<p>QMRA: Water recovery technologies for water reuse including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biological systems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Membrane systems ○ Adsorption systems ○ Advanced oxidation processes (AOP) <p>UWOT (#22)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Including any other Tools/Product/Services, around the Circular Economy, that have been applied in the case study/Living Lab. • Water recovery technologies for water reuse: (Local) wastewater treatment technologies, rainwater harvesting systems, surface water and infiltration systems. <p>Stormwater management: urban water buffer technologies</p>
Scales	<p>Stormwater reuse management system: Local (e.g., single treatment plant, industrial site or city quarter).</p> <p>QMRA, SuTRa: local</p> <p>UWOT: Local, neighbourhood, regional, city/provincial</p>
Legislation	<p>EU Legislation for water reuse (both for potable and non-potable reuse). Drinking Water Directive, Flemish drinking water law</p>
Synergistic benefits	<p>Use of UWOT for the ex-ante assessment or upscaling impact of real circular water pilots. The QMRA+ tool allowed users to balance health risk versus other impacts such as costs, environmental impact and resilience.</p>
Facts of the applied technologies	<p>NA</p>
Key Performance Indicators	<p>NA</p>
Requirements and conditions	<p>UWOT: Data input from specific partners (water utilities, technology providers, pilot project managers).</p> <p>QMRA+: Since very little location specific data (e.g., pathogens in effluent and in the current water source) were available, the uncertainty about the risk is relatively large. Still, the comparison between different scenarios was feasible and helped support decisions on system design.</p>
Key lessons	<p>QMRA is a new and complex topic for most water professionals and other stakeholders. The QMRA+ tool proved to be very accessible, and users quickly learned the principles of QMRA through the tool and were at the same time able to apply this through the tool in the project. It also provided a common ground for discussions, thus avoiding discussions about the safety of various scenarios.</p>

	UWOT can be used to model the expected effectiveness of measures with regards to water quantity under different scenarios. However, results can be limited by data availability, and results should be validated together with stakeholders.
Lessons learned from technology operation	NA
Technology performance and best practices	NA
Outcome of assessments	NA
Organisations	De Watergroep, Aquafin, Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt, City of Mechelen, Vito, KWR Water Research
Contact persons	Geertje.pronk@kwrwater.nl, Han Vervaeren (De Watergroep, han.vervaeren@dewatergroep.be, Birte Raes (Aquafin) birte.raes@aquafin.be, Joris De Nies (Joris.De.nies@proefstation.be), Stijn Van Goethem (stijn.vangoethem@mechelen.be), Patrick Smeets (KWR) Patrick.smeets@kwrwater.nl (QMRA+), Marjolein van Huijgevoort (KWR) (Marjolein.van.Huijgevoort@kwrwater.nl)
Data Manager	Glotzbach, Raul <Raul.Glotzbach@kwrwater.nl>
Costs	NA
Tags	Stormwater, buffer, rainwater harvesting. Water system modelling, hydrology Effluent reuse, wastewater reuse, drinking water, QMRA, health risk assessment
Publications/ Reference	NA
Images	NA
Caption/Source	NA

7 Tools and Methods for LL East Frisia

7.1 Key WS challenges, ambition and case study description

The OOWV (Lower Saxony, Germany) is one of the largest water suppliers in Germany with an area of 7.550 km², providing drinking water from groundwater resources to private, industrial, and agricultural customers (and treating wastewater in ~50% of the area). It is confronted with climate change, which causes hot and dry summer periods with increasing water demand in various sectors (households, industry, and agriculture) and increasing pressure on groundwater resources. Furthermore, emissions from agriculture affect the usability of water resources for drinking water purposes. The goal of OOWV is to identify unused water resources and increase the reuse of process water and treated wastewater in water-intensive sectors. For this purpose, OOWV is striving to increase the capacity of the water supply by i) identification of alternative resources, ii) intelligent protection strategies for groundwater bodies, and iii) improving the treatment of process water for reuse e.g., in the dairy industry. In the long term, integrated water resource management for the OOWV supply area is to be established using water reuse and alternative supply concepts. The methods and instruments developed in BWS as well as the technical know-how gained in the field of water reuse technologies are an important element in this.

7.2 Application of tools and methods

7.2.1 Selected tools and technologies of pilots

The East Frisian LL aims to identify untapped water resources and increase reuse of process water and treated wastewater in water-demanding key industries to reduce pressure on groundwater resources. Within the BWS project, a pilot plant is operated to test improved treatment of process water (vapour condensate and whey permeate) for reuse in the water-intensive sector of dairy production (technology #6). Besides, options for new digital solutions (e.g., machine learning) for monitoring were evaluated. A GIS-based spatial multi-criteria approach (tool #23) was developed to identify municipal and industrial water requirements and match these with regionally available water resources. The extended UWOT model (tool #22) was used to simulate alternative water demand and supply options under different climatic and demand change scenarios for a test case. A data driven tool (#28) for short-time water demand forecasting was developed, based on time series from smart meters and advanced stochastic demand modelling techniques.

The LL East Frisia technologies and tools and their link to the living lab challenge and strategic objectives are presented in Figure 86.

Figure 86: Systemic solution of LL East Frisia

7.2.2 Integrative use of tools, pilot interaction and data flows

Pilot activities and the development of digital tools in LL East Frisia are interlinked to a limited extent only. Pilot plant data will be embedded in the water demand-supply tool in the same way that increased industrial reuse by recirculation strategies will be included as a potential future water saving potential in large scale water management and upscaled to regional water saving potentials for industrial water demands. However, the technology that is piloted within the BWS project represents only one of various technological solutions for industrial reuse.

The three digital tools within LL East Frisia are interlinked as well. However, the regional demand supply matching is operating on a different scale compared to the other tools. UWOT and the Short-term demand forecasting tool are based on a small-scale analysis, while the regional demand supply matching tool is used for large scale analyses. The data flow between the tools can therefore be described in the way that UWOT and SDFT are producing water demand scenarios that can be included in the RDSMG for future-oriented scenarios. Conceptual data flow, integrative use of tools as well as pilot interaction are summarized in Figure 87 below.

Figure 87: Tool and pilot data flow within LL East Frisia

7.2.3 Pre-processing stage and input data

7.2.3.1 Urban Water Optioneering Tool (#22)

In the case study of East Frisia, UWOT (tool #22) is mainly used to simulate the water flows (water demand and supply points) for a test case and to investigate alternative scenarios based on different climatic and demand change conditions or with the implementation of partially decentralised technologies. The first step to start constructing the UWOT model was to define the test case. The fictitious example region is rather rural with some industrial priorities.

The data chosen for water demand and supply points corresponded to an annual timestep whereas the temporal scale applied in UWOT simulation was daily (in correspondence with the meteorological data), so the data was downscaled to be able to be used with UWOT. In case of missing data, the missing values/parameters used in the model relied on assumptions.

7.2.3.2 Regional demand-supply matching GIS tool (#23)

No special preparation in the sense of measurement campaigns or definition of a baseline was required to use the tool in the LL context. A data package is already provided with the tool. Therefore, only some data sets are specific for the LL and need to be updated for use in other contexts. The data include administrative data (e.g., administrative units, national borders, etc.), meteorological data, population data, data on water production, infrastructure (e.g., extraction facilities, road network, etc.) and others. Not all data need to be available for the use of the tool, and additional categories can be added. However, the functionality of the tool may be limited by missing data. The corresponding data sources for the application in LL East Frisia can be found as a compilation in the tool description. The tool itself is provided as a QGIS plug-in and can be used with the QGIS functions for plug-ins (e.g., batch processing).

7.2.3.3 Short-term demand forecasting tool (#28)

To apply the tool in the LL, it was necessary to first deploy smart meters that measure hourly water consumption or water flow. The resulting time series data is the core requirement of the tool, as every forecast represents the predicted continuation of the historical measurements. In general, the

organisation that plans to apply the tool is responsible for pre-processing the data to ensure a sufficient quality. Furthermore, it is possible to incorporate additional external data into the forecasts, like weather information. The only requirement is that associated time series for all historical water consumption measurements and for the prediction horizon can be provided. This can happen on a per-meter basis, as the user has to define which information will be used for what (set of) meter(s). For example, precipitation data may be used for smart meters with specific ids or lat/lon coordinates, but not for others. Any numerical time series data may be used as additional information for creating the water demand forecast as well. Examples of the expected smart meter meta data, measurement data and optional external data are given in the associated GitHub repository reported in section 5.7.7.

7.2.4 Setup process and application

7.2.4.1 Urban Water Optioneering Tool (#22)

To start building the baseline UWOT model for the test case, it was important to identify the different components that needed to be inserted in the model as well as the connection(s) among them. Four different categories/points of demand were assumed for the test case: (a) the household appliances (domestic uses), (b) industry and corresponding water needs, (c) livestock and (d) agriculture. Typical household appliances which need water for their function were selected for the model simulation. These were the dish washer (DW), the kitchen sink (KS), the hand basin (HB), the shower (SH), the toilet (WC) and the washing machine (WM). The number of households as well as each household's occupancy (approximately two persons) were estimated. The next step is to define the water usage (L/use) and the frequency of use per device. The default values are the following (Table 25):

Table 25: Default values of household appliances

	Water usage/capacity (L/use)	Frequency of use
Dish washer	35	0.3
Hand basin	2.1	7.15
Kitchen sink	2.1	7.15
Shower	35	0.71
Toilet	7	4.64
Washing machine	45	0.34

Considering the characteristics of all devices in the household, the residents per household (occupancy) and the number of households in the test case, UWOT model is used to calculate the total domestic water demand and produce the daily time series for the simulation's period of time. Additionally, it estimates the greywater/blackwater all these devices produce after their function. The UWOT schematisation for households is presented in Figure 88.

Figure 88: Households' schematization in UWOT.

At this point, it is important to mention that the baseline model was calibrated based on chosen annual domestic water demand data. To run the simulation in a daily timestep, there was a need to disaggregate the annual value into monthly values (seasonal variability) and then daily ones. The seasonal variability of water consumption is taken from literature and varies between 81% and 114% of average monthly household demand (Gerin et al., 2014), as shown in the Table 26:

Table 26: Seasonal variability of domestic water consumption.

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Percentages	1.09	1.14	1.08	1.03	0.99	0.94	0.81	0.83	0.94	1.01	1.05	1.09

The following categories were simulated: industry and livestock. The annual quantity of water demand derived from the industry was equally divided into 365 days of the year to calculate the daily water consumption from this use. As for livestock, based on annual water demand data and the assumption of average daily water requirements per animal (Stewart and Rout, 2007), the number of animals was estimated and inserted into the model. The assumptions regarding the water needs are the following:

Table 27: Water demand assumptions per farm animal.

Farm animals	Water demand (L/head/day)
Dairy cattle	45
Beef cattle	30
Sheep	3
Goats	5
Pigs	11
Poultry	30

The components that represent the industry and livestock categories are shown in Figure 89.

Figure 89: Industry and livestock schematization in UWOT.

The last category of water users introduced in the model was agriculture which is simulated based on data extracted from the CORINE Land Cover (CLC) shapefile⁵ for the test case, to have fewer data to manage. Based on the CLC's categories, the main category that represents agricultural areas of different types is considered to be of type "2". The test case region includes the codes "2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land", "2.3.1 Pastures" and "2.4.3 Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation". The category "2.1.1" was not selected to be further investigated as it refers to non-irrigated land. As a result, two new components were added to the model to simulate the agricultural areas, as it is shown in Figure 90. The values selected for water usage, evaporation and infiltration are based on assumptions, as the corresponding data was not available. For pastures the selected values were 300 mm water usage/capacity, 20% evaporation and 0 infiltration whereas for the other agricultural areas the corresponding values were 300 mm water usage/capacity, 30%

⁵ <https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover>

evaporation and 0.002 (days⁻¹) infiltration coefficient. The agricultural water needs are mainly covered by farmers' wells, so there was a need to add another component to simulate this type of source. The water usage/capacity regarding the whole number of wells (used in agriculture) in the area was not known and selected to be equal to 43200 m³/day (using a default UWOT brand).

Figure 90: Agricultural areas schematization in UWOT.

The water needs derived from the other uses (households, industry and livestock) are covered by groundwater and tapped springs (Figure 91). The groundwater supplies 99.80% of total water demand whereas the tapped springs only supply the remaining 0.20%.

Figure 91: Supply points used to cover water demand from households, industry and livestock.

The completed baseline model is presented in Figure 92 and the zoom windows that follow (Figure 93 - Figure 97).

Figure 92: Baseline model for test case.

Figure 93: Baseline model for test case – zoom window 1.

Figure 94: Baseline model for test case – zoom window 2.

Figure 95: Baseline model for test case – zoom window 3.

Figure 96: Baseline model for test case – zoom window 4.

Figure 97: Baseline model for test case – zoom window 5.

Based on the available regional meteorological data, the selected time period for the simulation of the baseline scenario was 01/01/2017-31/12/2021. Considering that the available data regarding the water needs provided refer to a single year, there is the assumption that the different quantities of water demand/supply follow the same annual pattern for the 5-year period of simulation.

After the finalization of the baseline scenario, more future scenarios are examined to investigate the impact of climate change and other external conditions (population increase, changes in livestock/agricultural areas/industrial water demand, implementation of decentralized technologies for water management etc.) on water demand quantities in the test case for the next 5-year period.

The first category of scenarios is related to households' projection for the next years. Two scenarios are created that examine a 1% and 2% increase in the number of households respectively for the next 5 years (based on data derived from the Federal Statistical Office of Germany⁶).

The second category refers to industrial water demand scenarios by examining a decrease from 0.5% to 4% (Wackerbauer, 2017) in order to investigate its impact on total water demand. More specifically, the scenarios examined were the following:

- 0.5% decrease
- 2% decrease
- 4% decrease

The third category examines changes in livestock by decreasing animals' population by 1 to 2% (based on Eurostat data for livestock population in the EU, 2010-2021).

The fourth category of scenarios is related to the effect of climate change on water demand by examining percentage changes in meteorological data (precipitation and temperature). The meteorological data are inserted into the model as input data for the BG components that simulate the agricultural areas. As a result, the percentage changes implemented in the baseline model mainly affect the agricultural water demand in the area. The percentage changes that were examined were the following (the assumptions are based on data derived from the World Bank Group⁷):

- 10% decrease in mean annual precipitation combined with a 2% rise in mean annual temperature.
- 20% decrease in mean annual precipitation combined with a 5% rise in mean annual temperature.

This category can also combine changes in agricultural areas, in the range of 0.5-1%.

The fifth and last category examines the implementation of decentralized technologies for water management. More specifically, a greywater treatment and recycling scheme is applied to 30% of the households, which will use treated water (instead of groundwater or tapped springs) to cover their WCs' water demand. The greywater treatment plant is lumped as one unit and assumed to have a capacity of 1.400.000 L/d. Its schematization is shown in Figure 98.

⁶ <https://www.destatis.de/EN/Themes/Society-Environment/Population/Households-Families/Tables/projection-household.html>

⁷ <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/germany/climate-data-historical>

Figure 98: Greywater recycling scheme

Indicative results of all these scenarios (baseline + future), either individual or in combination, are presented in sub-chapter 7.2.5 to investigate their impact on water management.

7.2.4.2 Regional demand-supply matching GIS tool (#23)

The data used in the tool are from publicly available sources. They are subject to the general conditions for the use of public data (use, copy, distribution). The respective terms of use are provided in the tool manual/description for the data along with the respective data sources and links to the corresponding websites. The data were assigned to GIS elements.

A distinction can be made between two types of input: The input of the data that serve as the basis for the calculation of the tool, and the input of the points at which the tool is to be used. The selection of the data used for calculation is done via a drop-down menu. The selection of the query points can be done in three ways: 1) the point can be selected via a click on the map; 2) the coordinates can be entered manually; 3) a point layer can be used. The last option is particularly practical if several points are to be queried at the same time.

Since it may happen that not all data is fully and up-to-date available to the user for the desired query area, the input parameters are divided into necessary and optional parameters. The necessary parameters are those that are at least required to be able to use the tool and used for the internal calculations. If the optional parameters are missing, the tool can be used, but some additional functionalities/statements may be limited.

The tool processes annual totals/annual data. Per capita water consumption is given in litres per day. There is the possibility to use UWOT results in the tool. The UWOT input data is converted into annual data by the tool after input.

To maintain consistency, it is recommended to use only data from within one year when updating, even if some data sets may be available for more recent years.

The data provided is available for the LL East Frisia area, some of the demo data is clipped to the area of Lower Saxony. However, the tool works for all of Europe, as long as the corresponding data is used as input (see also chapter 7.2.3.2).

7.2.4.3 Short-term demand forecasting tool (#28)

Figure 99 shows the architecture of the tool and contrasts which components have to be provided by the user of the tool (yellow) against the components already included in the tool (blue). The user has to implement a measurement agent that periodically updates the smart meter measurements in the Mongo database (preferably every hour). There is no requirement on how this is achieved, except that new entries appear in the database regularly. The weather agent is an optional module to incorporate additional, external data into forecasts of specific smart meters. To this end, the tool provides a Python interface that needs to be implemented by the organization. In this interface, the organization provides additional data depending on the smart meter ids or coordinates. The main component of the forecasting tool (referred to as “core tool” in the architecture diagram) provides an OpenAPI-documented, RESTful API to make integration with existing systems easy. If the core tool is not integrated into an existing system, a frontend that was co-developed during the project can be used to interact with it. If desired, generated forecasts are made accessible through the NGSI context broker. It is important to note that external apps have read-only access to smart meter forecasts through the context broker. Thus, they rely on the organization that deployed the tool to create forecasts

periodically. This is important to ensure that external apps cannot affect the data consistency or computational load on the servers.

Figure 99: Architecture of Short-term demand forecasting tool (#28).

The tool is organized in Docker containers that are controlled with Docker compose commands. It is highly recommended to deploy the tool on a server that has GPU access, as deep learning-based methods require a lot of computing power. However, this requires additional steps to make communication between the GPU and the Docker container possible (see the tool’s readme file for details). The GitHub repository (please refer to section 5.7.7) contains a .env file that defines the configurations that have to be set, for example if the tool should communicate with the context broker or weather agent or how many computational resources it should allocate for training. More specific details on the deployment of the tool can be found in the associated GitHub repository.

7.2.5 Results

7.2.5.1 Urban Water Optioneering Tool (#22)

Based on the data and the assumptions already described in sub-chapter 7.2.4, the selected time period for the simulation of the baseline scenario was 01/01/2017-31/12/2021 (5 years in total), using daily timestep. To avoid the large amount of time series produced, the results are aggregated and presented in a monthly timestep.

At the household level, the pattern of water demand derived from the use of domestic appliances is shown in the Figure 100.

Figure 100: Baseline scenario - Monthly water demand for domestic use.

The decline noted in months 6-8 (June-August) is mainly following holiday patterns in the test case residents.

At this stage, it is useful to also present the greywater production from the households, in order to later be compared with the results of the scenario regarding the implementation of decentralized greywater treatment technology in the area. The monthly greywater production is shown in Figure 101 and shows the potential of greywater reuse in the test case. Naturally, it follows the variability seen in Figure 100.

Figure 101: Baseline scenario - Monthly greywater production from domestic use.

The monthly quantities for water demand in industry are equal to about 3.69 hm³ and for livestock are about 1.40 hm³.

By summarizing all these water demands into one diagram, taking into account that these needs (from households, industry and livestock) are covered by groundwater and tapped springs, the total monthly potable water demand in the test case is shown in Figure 102. It is important to mention that the agricultural water demand is separately examined due to the fact that its needs are covered by farmers' wells. Therefore, the term "total water demand" doesn't include the agricultural water needs.

Figure 102: Baseline scenario - Total monthly water demand covered by groundwater and tapped springs.

The last category of water demand in the test case is for agricultural purposes and it is presented in Figure 103. The increased water demand shown for the years 2018 and 2019 is a result of low precipitation combined with high temperatures during the summer-autumn period.

Figure 103: Baseline scenario - Monthly water demand for agricultural purposes

The next step in this process is the comparison between the results from the baseline model and the different categories of scenarios (regarding the next five-year period) that were referred to in sub-section 7.2.4. In short, the five categories are the following:

1. 1% and 2% increase in the number of households.
2. 0.5%, 2% and 4% decrease in industrial water demand.
3. Changes in livestock by decreasing animals' population between 1 and 2%
4. Climate change related scenarios, by examining a 10% decrease in mean annual precipitation combined with a 2% rise in mean annual temperature as well as a 20% decrease in mean annual precipitation combined with a 5% rise in mean annual temperature. This category can also combine changes in agricultural areas, in the range of 0.5 - 1%.
5. Implementation of decentralized technologies for water management, by applying a greywater treatment and recycling scheme in the 30% of the households, which will use treated water (instead of groundwater or tapped springs) to cover their WCs' water demand. The greywater treatment plant is assumed to have a capacity of 1400000 L/d.

First category: 1% and 2% increase in the number of households.

A 1% and 2% increase in the current number of households can raise the total annual water demand by about 0.45% and 0.8% respectively, as it is shown in the Table 28.

Table 28: Total annual water demand changes due to an increase in the number of households.

Total annual water demand changes due to an increase in the number of households (hm³)		
Baseline scenario	1% increase	2% increase
8.85	8.89 (≈0.45% increase compared to the baseline scenario)	8.92 (≈0.80% increase compared to the baseline scenario)

Second category: 0.5%, 2% and 4% decrease in industrial water demand.

A 0.5%, 2% and 4% decrease in the industrial water demand can decrease the annual water demand by about 0.23%, 0.9% and 0.8% respectively, as shown in Table 29.

Table 29: Total annual water demand changes due to a decrease in the industrial water demand.

Total annual water demand changes due to a decrease in the industrial water demand (hm³)			
Baseline scenario	0.5% decrease	2% decrease	4% decrease
8.85	8.83 (≈0.23% decrease compared to the baseline scenario)	8.77 (≈0.90% decrease compared to the baseline scenario)	8.70 (≈1.70% decrease compared to the baseline scenario)

Third category: Changes in livestock by decreasing animals' population between 1 and 2%

A 1% and 2% decrease in the animals' population can decrease the annual water demand by about 0.23% and 0.34% respectively, as shown in Table 30.

Table 30: Total annual water demand changes due to changes in livestock by decreasing animals' population.

Total annual water demand changes due to changes in livestock by decreasing animals' population (hm³)		
Baseline scenario	1% decrease	2% decrease
8.85	8.83 (≈0.23% decrease compared to the baseline scenario)	8.82 (≈0.34% decrease compared to the baseline scenario)

Considering that the term “total water demand” refers to the summary of water needs derived from the three examined categories (households, industry and livestock) which cover their needs from groundwater and tapped springs, it was examined the impact that a 2% (in absolute term) change (increase/decrease) in each category can have on the total amount of water demand. The results are presented in Figure 104.

Figure 104: Percentage impact of a 2% change of each category on total water demand

The diagram shows that the total water demand is more sensitive to changes that are related to industry than households and less so than livestock.

Fourth category: Climate change related scenarios.

The examined climate change scenarios that are examined to investigate their impact on the agricultural sector are the following (Table 31):

Table 31: Climate change related scenarios and their impact on agricultural water demand.

Climate change related scenarios and their impact on agricultural water demand						
Baseline scenario	Scenario 1: 10% decrease in mean annual precipitation combined with a 2% rise in mean annual temperature	Scenario 2: 20% decrease in mean annual precipitation combined with a 5% rise in mean annual temperature	Scenario 3: 10% decrease in mean annual precipitation combined with a 2% rise in mean annual temperature. + 0.5% decrease in agricultural area	Scenario 4: 10% decrease in mean annual precipitation combined with a 2% rise in mean annual temperature. + 1% decrease in agricultural area	Scenario 5: 20% decrease in mean annual precipitation combined with a 5% rise in mean annual temperature. + 0.5% decrease in agricultural area	Scenario 6: 20% decrease in mean annual precipitation combined with a 5% rise in mean annual temperature. + 1% decrease in agricultural area

The results are shown in Figure 105.

Figure 105: Results from climate change scenarios implemented on agriculture.

The greater difference among the scenarios examined can be found between the Scenarios 1 and 2 (also compared to the baseline) which indicates the impact of temperature and rainfall on agricultural water demand whereas a 0.5 - 1% change on agricultural areas does not seem to play crucial role on the results.

Fifth category: Implementation of decentralized technologies for water management.

The results regarding the domestic water demand (and the total water demand respectively) before and after the implementation of greywater treatment plant (decentralized technology) are presented in Table 32 and Table 33.

Table 32: Annual domestic water demand changes due to the implementation of greywater recycling (GWR) technology

Annual domestic water demand changes due to the implementation of greywater recycling (GWR) technology (hm³)	
Baseline scenario	GWR scenario
3.75	3.43 (≈8.50% decrease compared to the baseline scenario)

Table 33: Annual total water demand changes due to the implementation of greywater recycling (GWR) technology

Annual total water demand changes due to the implementation of greywater recycling (GWR) technology (hm³)	
Baseline scenario	GWR scenario
8.85	8.53 (≈3.60% decrease compared to the baseline scenario)

The results show that greywater recycling technology has a significant impact on potable water demand and can play a major role in attempts to reduce potable water needs in the household level. Compared the greywater quantities at both scenarios (baseline and GWR), it is obvious that the second approach significantly reduces the amount of greywater finally produced, as it is recycled inside the household (Figure 106).

Figure 106: Greywater production in the baseline and GWR scenarios

7.2.5.2 Regional demand-supply matching GIS tool (#23)

The results of the tool are the collection of publicly available data resources and the tool itself (QGIS plug-in). To illustrate the functioning of the tool, a sample scenario is presented below. A consideration of alternative water use in the Nordenham industrial area, district of Wesermarsch, was chosen as a fictitious application example. The chosen scenario envisages that part of the water required for production should be obtained from alternative sources, as it is assumed in the scenario, that no special demands are made on chemical and biological quality for the planned use. To get an overview of the resources available at the sample site, the RDSMG tool is used.

For this example, the site of interest was selected via a point layer, and the corresponding input data was selected via the dropdown menu (Figure 107).

Figure 107: Screenshot data selection regional demand-supply matching tool (#23)

If available for the selected point, the tool provides the following data: administrative information, land use information, information on drinking water - water consumption and water extraction, information on groundwater and surface water bodies, as well as alternative resources and, if available, optional user-defined data (examples in Figure 108). The query indicates groundwater of sufficient quality and a yield of > 40 l/s for the selected point (Figure 108). In this simulation, however, the focus is to be on the water resources that can be used alternatively to groundwater or water from drinking water supply.

The tool shows three possible alternative resources: firstly, the surface water of Blexer Sieltief/Blexer Tief is only 415 m away and could possibly be used. The second alternative resource is the Nordenham sewage treatment plant, which is about 1.2 km away. Both resources would be linked to construction investments, as the corresponding pipelines would have to be built over these distances. It would also have to be clarified whether these waters meet the process requirements or would have to be treated accordingly and whether the available quantities are sufficient for the demand. Treatment would involve further costs that should be taken into account. A third option is the use of rainwater. The tool determines a mean annual precipitation of 761 mm for the query point. This means that a roof area of only 100 m² has the potential to recover 76 100 l/a. Since a hall roof is many times larger, the amount of water potentially available is many times greater. If, in addition, the water volumes of the other sealed surfaces are also used instead of being discharged into the sewerage system or land drainage, the water volume available is many times greater. For use as process water, rainwater would have the advantage of low mineralisation.

Figure 108: Screenshots query output (without map) example case regional demand-supply matching tool (#23)

In this selected example, this information could serve as a starting point for further, targeted investigations and feasibility studies on the use of one or more of the alternative resources. The RDSMG tool can be used not only for estimating alternative water resources, but also for strategic

planning of e.g., sites for new developments, especially with regard to aim of building with alternative, more environmentally friendly standards in terms of water conservation.

7.2.5.3 Short-term demand forecasting tool (#28)

The results consist of the headless core tool and the optional frontend, which can both be used to train machine learning models on smart meter data to create 24-hour forecasts on different spatial scales. In the following, a typical workflow is shown. In Figure 109, the user starts by aggregating existing smart meters to a “virtual meter” that represents a larger zone for which he/she wants to create forecasts. In Figure 110, the user then chooses this virtual meter and one of the implemented algorithms to train a model. As they usually do not know which hyperparameters to choose for the algorithm, the users select to perform an automatic hyperparameter search (using Bayesian optimization with Hyperband) to find the best set of hyperparameters according to 15 trial runs. In Figure 111, the user examines the performance of the model with reference common error metrics and by contrasting predicted versus actual consumption on a holdout dataset (note that the final model is trained on this data, too). Finally, the user can generate forecasts using this model for dates in the future, as seen in Figure 112. By comparing the predicted load curve against historical values of the same day of the last week and last month, the user can quickly check the prediction for plausibility. The same workflow can be done without any UI and thus be automated with additional organization-specific computations that make use of the predictions. For example, an alert can be sent in case the predicted water demand exceeds a threshold.

The tool provides algorithms that use very different approaches (statistical, tree-based, deep-learning) that each may be more appropriate for different datasets. The user has to empirically determine the best approach for his specific context. For the smart meters used in the LL, the XGBoost algorithm proved to produce good results (see Figure 111) while keeping the computational load low (few minutes) as compared to the deep-learning approaches which can take up to hours to train. On the other hand, statistical approaches were found to be lacking in performance even though they are very fast to train. In general, performance depends on two major factors. Firstly, the amount of randomness in the historical water demand by definition heavily affects predictability and can vary a lot across different scenarios like a house of retired people or a young family. Secondly, low data quality can render prediction models useless. In the LL, a problem was that some sensors would, from some point forward, regularly drop measurements which led to data gaps in most days’ measurements.

In conclusion, the tool allows the user to aggregate smart meters and train and query machine learning models for short-term demand forecasts through either a UI or a restful API. Both good and bad results could be achieved for smart meters used in the LL, depending on the nature of the measured area and sensor malfunctions.

Meter Management

Here you can select a Meter, and view his informations. You can also select multiple Meters to create a virtual Meter with the selected meters as submeters. If you don't want a meter in the List, you can delete it via the button in the list. A selected meter will disable other meters that are a submeter of the selected one.

Meter List:

- Device:MPS045009
- Device:MPS045010
- Device:MPS045011
- Device:MPS045012
- Device:MPS045013
- Device:MPSHeide
- Device:MPSPariser

CLEAR SELECTION

Meter Info:

Create virtual meter from selected meters (2)

urn:ngsi-ld:Device:MPSHeide

urn:ngsi-ld:Device:MPSPariser

Name for virtual Meter (optional):

SupplyZoneX

CREATE VIRTUAL METER

Figure 109: Aggregating smart meters to a virtual meter to train and query models with.

Model Management

Here you can train a model with all or a subset of the defined meters. If meters are missing, please add them in the Meter Management tab. The model can then be used to create forecasts. Hyperparameter Optimization is used to find the optimal parameter value, if you don't want to input values manually.

Selected Meter:

urn:ngsi-ld:virtualMeter:SupplyZoneX

Comment:

Algorithm:

XGBoost

Hyperparameter optimization:

Number of configurations to run:

TRAIN MODEL

Estimated Time: 2 min.

Figure 110: Model training with hyperparameter optimization.

urn:ngsi-Id:virtualMeter:SupplyZoneX:MLModel:XGBoost XGBoost 2023-06-05T09:05:07 2023-06-05T09:05:07

MAPE: 5.10109

RMSE: 0.02742

Figure 111: Evaluation results of model training in terms of performance on hold-out dataset.

Forecast Data

This forecast is generated for **2023-03-14** using meter "urn:ngsi-Id:virtualMeter:SupplyZoneX" and algorithm "XGBoost".

Figure 112: Short-term demand forecast with historical reference values for plausibility checking.

7.3 Lessons extracted

The implementation of UWOT tool gave a good impression for the water use in the different sectors. It could have multiple benefits for water management strategy in case more data becomes available regarding the different water users and sources. Additionally, it could be useful to know the policy and measures related to water management to further investigate possible future scenarios based on real data and not assumptions. Some main conclusions produced from the examined scenarios' results are the following:

- The water system was found to be more sensitive to changes that are related to the industry in comparison with the households and the livestock.
- The impact of climate change (regarding meteorological conditions, mainly temperature and rainfall) on agricultural water demand is crucial whereas small changes on agricultural areas don't seem to significantly affect the water needs.
- The greywater recycling (GWR) technology has a significant impact on potable water demand and can play a major role on attempts for reducing potable water needs in the household level. It has the potential to reduce the annual domestic water demand by 8.50% and the annual total water demand (including households, industry, and livestock) by 3.60% in the test case.

The model can be adjusted to account for changes in any scenario parameters (e.g., population increase, livestock changes, industry changes, climate-driven scenarios etc.).

The RDSMG tool was implemented in the LL and has great potential to become a key monitoring and decision-making tool for sustainable water resources and water demand management in the region. However, its acceptance and usefulness very much depend on the input data available. For this first-time implementation the main ambition was to make the most use of publicly available information from national, regional, and local databases. With this information on water resources usage and water demands, it was possible to derive important insights on regions with surplus and exceeding water demands as presented in section 7.2.5.2. However, publicly available data shows some gaps with regards to industrial uses and only limited data is available on water extractions by self-supply systems. This limits the user's benefit with regards to investigating potentials for industrial reuse and future predictions on agricultural water demand in the region. The highest benefits from the tool can be derived if data sets are regularly updated and enriched by new information collected from stakeholders.

The SDFT was successfully implemented in the city of Lohne. The results of the case study application prove the usefulness of the tool for predicting future load profiles of municipal water demand in the districts under investigation. Nevertheless, the accuracy of the prognosis depends very much on the positioning of smart meters in the network and the demographic information available in this section of the supply network. For future studies, a large-scale implementation of smart meters would be desirable instead of summarized measurements of small city districts in order to enhance the prognoses' quality.

7.4 Summary table of the East Frisia LL

Table 34: Summary table for LL East Frisia

Title	East Frisia LL
Description	<p>In the case study of East Frisia, the UWOT (tool #22) is mainly used to simulate the water flows (water demand and supply points) in a test case and to investigate alternative scenarios based on different climatic and demand change conditions or with the implementation of partially decentralised technologies.</p> <p>The regional demand-supply matching GIS tool is used to identify i) possible consumption hotspots and areas of water shortage, ii) alternative water resources or areas with available water sources and iii) water drains from one region to another.</p> <p>The short-term demand forecasting tool is used to generate water demand forecasts for the next (or current) day, which can e.g., be used to identify high peak loads in certain regions that require actions by the water utility.</p>
Reference point	City of Lohne in Germany: https://goo.gl/maps/L52XBGhKqkib8mdGA (application area for tool #28)
Location	City of Lohne
Country (-ies)	Germany
URL	https://mp.watereurope.eu/d/CaseStudy/19
Project	BWS
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High drinking water demand due to a dense or growing resident population, • Impact of climate change on irrigation water demand for agriculture, • Need for reuse and recovery schemes for greywater. • Other
Tools/Product/Services	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Urban Water Optioneering Tool (#22) 2. Regional demand-supply matching GIS tool (#23) 3. Short-term demand forecasting tool (#28)
Technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource for Circular Economy • Water recovery technologies for water reuse • Wastewater treatment technologies for water reuse • Groundwater systems • Urban rainwater harvesting systems.
Scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local (e.g., single treatment plant, industrial site, or city quarter), • Regional (across several municipalities and/or administrative borders, incl. rural areas)
Legislation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate Adaptation Strategy & Plans + Circular Economy Action Plan (EU); Water Framework Directive (WFD) • Smart meters: Metering Point Operation and Data Communication in Intelligent Energy Networks Act; IT Security Act • Federal Water Act (Wasserhaushaltsgesetz, WHG, in German) • Drinking water Ordinance (Trinkwasserverordnung, TrinkwV) • Metering Point Operation and Data Communication in Intelligent Energy Networks Act (Gesetz für den Messstellenbetrieb und die Datenkommunikation in intelligenten Energienetzen, MsbG) • Law on the Federal Office for Information Security (German: Gesetz über das Bundesamt für Sicherheit in der Informationstechnik, BSI) • IT Security Act (German: IT-Sicherheitsgesetz, IT-SiG)

Synergistic benefits	<p>Pilot plant data can be embedded in the water demand-supply tool in the way that increased industrial reuse by recirculation strategies will be included as a potential future water saving potential in large scale water management and upscaled to regional water saving potentials for industrial water demands.</p> <p>UWOT and the Short-term demand forecasting tool are based on a small-scale analysis, while the regional demand supply matching tool is used for large scale analyses. The data flow between the tools can therefore be described in the way that UWOT and STDFT are producing water demand scenarios that can be included in the RDSMG for future-oriented scenarios.</p>
Facts of the applied technologies	<p>-</p>
Key Performance Indicators	<p>-</p>
Requirements and conditions	<p>For the purpose of constructing a baseline model for the testcase, data related to water demand per user (household, livestock, and industry), water supply option and meteorological conditions are estimated. Agricultural data are extracted from CORINE Land Cover (CLC) shapefiles. Based on the CLC's categories, the main category that represents agricultural areas of different types is considered to be of type "2". The test case region is considered to include the codes "2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land", "2.3.1 Pastures" and "2.4.3 Land principally occupied by agriculture, with significant areas of natural vegetation". The category "2.1.1" was not selected to be further investigated as it refers to non-irrigated land. Other parameters regarding the agriculture, livestock and households are missing and assumptions are included in the model, based on relevant references.</p> <p>No special preparation in the sense of measurement campaigns or the definition of a baseline was required to use the regional demand-supply matching GIS tool in the LL context. A data package including only publicly available information is already provided with the tool. Therefore, only some data sets are specific to the LL and needed to be added and the data were assigned to GIS elements.</p> <p>To apply the short-term demand forecasting tool in the LL, it was necessary to first deploy smart meters that measure hourly water consumption or water flow.</p>
Key lessons	<p>The implementation of the UWOT tool in the test case produced useful results for water use in the different sectors. It could have multiple benefits for water management strategies in case more data becomes available regarding the different water users and sources. Additionally, it could be useful to know the policies and measures related to water management in order to further investigate possible future scenarios based on real data and not assumptions. The model can be adjusted to account for changes in any scenario parameters, (e.g., population increase, livestock changes, industry changes, climate-driven scenarios etc.).</p> <p>The RDSMG tool has great potential to become a key monitoring and decision-making tool for sustainable water resources and water demand management in the region. However, its acceptance and usefulness very much depend on the input data available. For this first-time implementation the main ambition was to make the most use of publicly available information from national, regional, and local databases. In the future, highest benefits from the tool can be derived if data sets are regularly updated and enriched by new information collected from stakeholders.</p> <p>The STDFT was successfully implemented in the city of Lohne. The results of the case study application prove the usefulness of the tool for predicting future load profiles of municipal water demand in the districts under investigation. Nevertheless, the accuracy</p>

	smart meters in the network and the prognosis depend very much on the positioning and demographic information available in this section of the supply network. For future studies a large-scale implementation of smart meters would be desirable instead of summarized measurements of small city districts in order to enhance the prognoses' quality.
Lessons learned from technology operation	-
Technology performance and best practices	-
Outcome of assessments	-
Organisations	OOWV IWW ICCS/NTUA
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Costs	The UWOT software is available for research purposes free of charge upon request on a time limited license. For commercial purposes there are commercial agreement options. The other tools are open source and free of charge.
Tags	climate change, re-use, recycling, water management, greywater, rainwater, groundwater, water reuse, water demand, water supply, machine learning, GIS
Publications/Reference	Schwesig et al. (2023): Digitale Lösungen für eine wasserbewusste Gesellschaft, Energie Wasser-Praxis, 6+7/2023, pp. 54-59. https://energie-wasser-praxis.de/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/2023_06_06_FB-Schwesig_0607_2023.pdf

Images

UWOT baseline model for the test case

Screenshot data selection regional demand-supply matching tool (#23)

Forecast Data

This forecast is generated for **2023-03-14** using meter "urn:ngsi-Id:virtualMeter:SupplyZoneX"

Short-term demand forecast with historical reference values for plausibility checking

Caption/Source

Captions are specified directly with the pictures above. Pictures are provided by ICCS (picture 1) and IWW (picture 2 and 3).

8 Tools and Methods for LL Lisbon⁸

8.1 Key WS challenges, ambition and case study description

Lisbon has a smart management strategy for all key areas of urban development. The city aims at providing high quality of life for an increasing population and growing economy, whilst tackling climate change challenges based on a green-blue problem-solving infrastructure. As such, the key smart-water **challenges** of the Lisbon Living Lab (Lisbon LL) targeted in BWS are (i) a growing resident population and economy, dependent on distant freshwater resources (up to 100 km), (ii) climate challenges (e.g., droughts and floods) and (iii) need to increase urban green areas. Actions to address these challenges include (i) improving the water supply / demand management and ultimately the city's water-energy-phosphorus (WEP) footprint while increasing the green areas, (ii) promoting the safe use of alternative sources (e.g., reclaimed water), and (iii) promoting climate-ready (water-energy efficient, climate-change proof) housing. Figure 113 presents the **Lisbon LL ambition**.

Figure 113: The Lisbon LL ambition.

The Lisbon LL gathers six partners working for these goals:

- **CML** (Lisbon Municipality) is the Lisbon case-study problem owner; as such, CML makes the city's data and resources available as a living lab in the project, promotes the Lisbon Community of Practice (CoP), participates in the BWS Innovation Alliance, tests the Lisbon LL solutions developed within the project and plays a key role in disseminating and promoting the

⁸ This section has been included in both deliverables (D3.4/D3.5) since it provides information on the integrative use of tools that are applied in Lisbon case. Six tools have been developed as part of this LL work, which have been split and documented in the 2 toolkit reports.

adoption of these solutions among its extensive networking platforms. CML also develops the urban water cycle observatory, through a linked third-party – LEN (Lisboa E-Nova).

- **LNEC** (Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil) is the mentor and R&I partner for the Lisbon LL, responsible, among others, for the development of the knowledge, methodologies and analytics behind the tools of (health and environment) risk assessment, reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution network, WEP balance, and decision support of alternative courses of action based on performance-cost-risk indicators. LNEC also participates in the development of the water reclamation protocol for potable water reuse in beverage industry for artisanal craft beer production.
- **ADTA** (Águas do Tejo Atântico) is the water utility enabler of Lisbon LL, providing real data (on wastewater treatment and water reclamation) for several tools and is responsible for conducting the pilot tests needed to develop the water reclamation protocol for potable water reuse in craft beer production.
- **ADENE** (Agência para a Energia) is a solution provider responsible for developing the knowledge and tools for climate-readiness certification.
- **BASEFORM** is a solution provider responsible for developing the software for the risk assessment, reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution network, WEP balance and decision-support tools.
- **ICS-UL** (Instituto de Ciências Sociais da Universidade de Lisboa) is a cross-cutting R&I partner integrating the social sciences and humanities and is the Lisbon CoP moderator.

Case study description

Lisbon LL aims (i) to demonstrate the potential for safe potable water reuse in the beverage industry in the **mid to long run**, and (ii) in the **short term**, to promote water (and related energy and phosphorus) efficiency, water smart allocation (fit-for-purpose quality), circular economy, and safe non-potable urban water reuse, work that is to be developed within the following tasks:

- Task 2.4.1 Protocol for water production from wastewater,
- Task 2.4.2 Water matrix and concepts behind water observatory,
- Task 2.4.3a Urban WEP balance,
- Task 2.4.3b Risk management - health component,
- Task 2.4.3c Risk management - groundwater component,
- Task 2.4.3d Reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution system,
- Task 2.4.4 Water-smart for climate ready certificates.

8.2 Application of tools and methods

8.2.1 Selected tools and technologies of pilots

Lisbon LL developed methods, algorithms and software for a smart allocation of the water quality (fit-for-purpose) and quantity (water efficiency) in the city (Figure 114), delivering the following Data Application Products (DAPs):

- **Tool #20 - Urban Water Cycle Observatory**, to systematise, collect and facilitate access to data at city the level and at the single users/consumers level (DAP 2).
- **Tool #24 – Reclaimed water quality in the distribution network**, for modelling reclaimed water quality in the distribution network (DAP 2).

- **Tool #25 - Water-Energy-Phosphorus balance planning**, a module for the quantification of the city water cycle components and assessment of water-energy-phosphorus balance for non-potable uses (DAP 2).
- **Tool #27 - Risk assessment for urban water reuse**, a module for the implementation of alternative water sources (DAP 6).
- **Tool #17 - Environment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action**, a decision support tool for WEP sustainable management based on performance-cost-risk assessment (DAP 2), which integrates the above three tools (#24, #25, #27)
- **Tool #33 - Climate readiness certification**, with climate-readiness index and the subsequent auditing/certification mechanism for Climate Readiness of households, buildings and neighbourhoods (DAP 10).

Furthermore, a protocol for food-grade water production from treated wastewater by ozone/reverse osmosis for craft beer production is being demonstrated for communicating and disseminating (C&D) safe water reuse and thus building trust in this resilient, rainfall-independent water source. The development of this **Technology Product (TP)**, TP1, does not involve software production, and consequently there is no link to T3.5 in this case.

Figure 114: The LL Lisbon tools.

The links with Lisbon LL **pilots** (WP2, tasks 2.4) are the following (Figure 115):

- TP#1 / task 2.4.1: 1 ozone oxidation/reverse osmosis (O3/RO) pilot installed at Beirolas water resource recovery facility (WRRF) for demonstration of water reuse in the food industry, namely, in artisanal craft beer production (direct potable reuse, DPR).

- Tool #25, Tool #27, and Tool#17 (and at city level, Tool #20) / task 2.4.3 (and task 2.4.2): 10 green urban areas for WEP sustainable management based on performance-cost-risk assessment, comprising 2 non-potable water uses (irrigation and landscape lakes) and 4 potential water sources, two currently used (drinking water and groundwater) and two new, i.e., reclaimed water and spring water from the Águas Livres aqueduct.
- Tool#24 / task 2.4.3: 3 reclaimed water distribution systems (RWDSs) for water quality modelling (1 rooftop-garden's irrigation circuit, 1 reclaimed water distribution network in the city (near "Frente Ribeirinha"), 1 park's irrigation circuit), to support the residual chlorine management for a safe water supply.
- Tool #33 / task 2.4.4: 9 pilots for water-smart climate-readiness certification (3 households, 3 buildings, 3 neighbourhoods).

Figure 115: The LL Lisbon pilots.

8.2.2 Integrative use of tools, pilot interaction and data flows

Making Lisbon a water-smarter city implies the involvement of different stakeholders in the provision and use of water. Thus, the Lisbon LL is focused on the development of software tools to facilitate safe water reuse and improve water-energy-phosphorous efficiency in non-potable uses, improving Lisbon's climate resilience to water scarcity. The following approaches were considered for the desired transformation into a water-smarter society:

- To increase the citizens' awareness about the local context regarding the water use in the city via the provision of appellative information on water consumption, wastewater treatment, and fit-for-purpose water use, particularly, safe water reuse.
- To inform individual entities (public or private major water consumers) about their water consumption, in case of smart water metering, and increase their awareness on wastewater treatment and fit-for-purpose water use, particularly, safe water reuse.
- To support the decision-making process of water demand planners and managers in urban, municipal and water utility contexts, by delivering an overview of the current water supply and water demand in the city to enable prioritizing strategic and tactical planning options.
- To guide or assess the promotion of climate adaptation in housing via a certification process used by housing owners and planners.

The level of integration between these tools naturally depends on the purpose for which they are used, which in turn is associated with the target user. Thus, the software applications developed at the Lisbon LL were designed to work as follows:

- Use of the **tool #20** alone with two distinct objectives in mind:
 - To increase the citizens' awareness of the urban water cycle by providing yearly-based, easy-to-read information on the city's water cycle (public access, top-down approach).
 - To promote an easier, faster, and more flexible way to access the detailed water consumption data on water facilities (usually, large consumers) and to provide a repository of information (private access, bottom-up approach).
- Integrated use of **tools #17, #24, #25, and #27** with the following objective:
 - To support urban management authorities and water utilities in making smart and climate-resilient water decisions for an efficient water-energy-nutrient balance in the city including safe water reuse, by enabling direct comparison of alternatives for matching water supply and water demand to satisfy specific non-potable uses.
- Use of the **tool #33** alone with two distinct objectives in mind:
 - To guide the design and assessment of the climate readiness potential of existing households, buildings or neighbourhoods.

Although they were not designed for integrated use in a single decision-making process, there are links between tools #20 and #33 and between these and the #17, #24, #25 and #27 tool group:

- From tool #20 to tool #25 - detailed information on water consumption locations, e.g., municipal green areas, when using the private access mode.
- From tool #17 to tool #20 or to tool #33 – general information on water management planning broken down by alternative water sources, as well as information on water related energy and phosphorus content.

Tools #17, #24, #25, and #27 were designed for **integrated use**, with each tool representing a step in the decision-making process (Figure 116), namely:

- Step 1 (tool #25) – Matchmaking of water sources (potential supplies) and water demands to enable the design of supply chain solutions (the shorter and more circular the better) to a set of potential users of non-potable water, namely, reclaimed water and other water sources alternative to those currently in use (e.g., groundwater). The supply/demand alternative combinations (matches) over a target period are assessed through a range of performance and cost metrics, for supporting strategic and tactical (aligned) planning (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content). This step produces the alternative combinations targeted for decision-making in step 4.
- Step 2 (tool #24) – In case of reclaimed water use, it is convenient to map and quantify risk in the water distribution network. This tool is a complete hydraulic and water quality extended-period simulation model for pressure flow networks. It complements Tool #25 in assessing the additional cost, risk and performance changes that may be required for the supply/demand combinations chosen to make use of existing or new distribution networks.
- Step 3 (tool #27) – In case of reclaimed water use, it is necessary to assess human health and environmental risk considering the applicable legislation (e.g., the Portuguese Decree-Law 119/2019) and the best practice as presented, for example, in relevant ISO standards (series [ISO 16075](#) Guidelines for treated wastewater use for irrigation projects (2020, 2021), [ISO 20426:2018](#) Guidelines for health risk assessment and management for non-potable water reuse and [ISO 20761:2018](#) Guidelines for water reuse safety evaluation), based on which the [EU Regulation 2020/741](#)⁹ on minimum requirements for water reuse in agricultural irrigation was developed. Tool #27 works as a risk-based gatekeeper that must be cleared for any supply/demand combination to be considered for assessment in Tool #17. Depending on the risk level targeted for completion, it will be rejected (eventually go back to tool #25 for redesign), or otherwise cleared and move on to Tool #17.
- Step 4 (tool #17) – For all matchmaking alternatives, a final prioritization between the supply/demand combinations developed in Tool #25 and qualified by Tools #24 and #27 support the decision on the course of action for a water-smarter city, for the specific case studied or others within comparable contexts. This tool is designed to enable users to select the best water source combinations to satisfy specific non-potable uses, and to align with strategic and tactical planning options on the governance of water sources and water uses in an urban setting. As previously referred, the supply/demand alternative combinations are assessed and prioritized through a subset of standardized, user-selected key performance/cost/risk metrics, extracted from those employed to qualify the initial selection in Tool #25 (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content) and to further qualify the risk assessment in Tool #27, as well as in Tool #24, if applicable, e.g., in case a network to distribute very-high quality reclaimed water for unrestricted urban uses (class A, according to 119/2019¹⁰ and EU reg 2020/741) is needed, as in Lisbon city (Lisbon LL).

Figure 117 illustrates the data flows among tools #17, #24, #25, and #27 and the pilots.

⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32020R0741>

¹⁰ <https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/decreto-lei/119-2019-124097549>

Figure 116: The LL Lisbon tools for a smarter water demand management and pilot interaction (step-by-step process).

Granularity: city/ city zone/ city facility

Figure 117: The LL Lisbon tools for a smarter water demand management and its data flows (start from top, tool #25).

8.2.3 Pre-processing stage and input data

The necessary steps and processes that need to be fulfilled before being able to apply the Lisbon LL tools along with related technologies are presented in Table 35 to Table 40. For each tool, the related WP2 task(s) for pilot data collection is(are) presented.

The Pre-Processing Stage includes the following aspects: identification of relevant actors, definition of case extent, definition of baseline, collection and editing of input data, conduction of workshops, and installation of equipment.

The Input Data is organized in the following aspects: primary data, background data, water data, and additional data.

Table 35: Data requirements for tool #17.

T3.5 tools		#17 Environment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action
T2.4 subtasks		T2.4.3a Urban W-E-P balance T2.4.3b Risk management - health component T2.4.3c Risk management - groundwater component T2.4.3d Reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution system
Pre-processing stage	Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water demand planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal, and water utility contexts.
	Case extent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Link to other strategic and tactical planning options related to water management in an urban setting, e.g., feeding the infrastructure asset management planning.
	Baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The high-level goal of this tool is to enable users to select the best combination of water sources to satisfy specific non-potable uses, and to enable prioritisation of strategic and tactical planning options on water management in an urban setting.
	Input data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metrics from Tools #25 and #27, as well as from Tool #24, if applicable (i.e., when the possible degradation of the distributed water quality is a critical point in the reuse system, namely, when the reclaimed water is class A).
	Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP1/T1.3 training action scheduled for April 18, 2024
Input data	Primary data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metrics employed to qualify the initial selection in Tool #25 (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content, geolocation) and for further qualification through risk assessment in Tool #27 and potentially in Tool #24, if applicable, as illustrated in Figure 117 and listed in Table 37, Table 38 and Table 39, respectively.
	Background data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse and climate action.
	Water data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The water data relevant (i.e. the primary data above) for tools #24, #25, and #27, illustrated in Figure 117 and listed in Table 37, Table 38 and Table 39, respectively.

Table 36: Data requirements for tool #20.

T3.5 tool	#20 Urban Water Cycle Observatory
T2.4 subtask	T2.4.2 Water matrix and concepts behind water observatory

Pre-processing stage	Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public access – citizens, urban management authorities, academia, NGOs, media, and other key stakeholders. Private access – municipalities (especially, Lisbon municipality in the scope of the Lisbon LL), private institutions of public interest, private entities with large water consumption.
	Case extent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This tool can function as a data repository.
	Baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public access – provision of information on an annual basis, related with main water flows, consumption disaggregation (by type of use and type of user), amount of treated wastewater and reclaimed water production. Private access – visualization of aggregated consumptions and costs per typology of water use, water consumption evolution, and individual consumption analysis.
	Input data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public access – collection of annual open data regarding the city's urban water cycle (drinking water, wastewater and reclaimed water), edition privileges the use of infographics. Private access – collection of water consumption data registered through smart meters, edition via a set of analytics.
	Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP1/T1.3 training action scheduled for November 16, 2023
	Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Private access – water smart meters
Input data	Primary data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public access – open data of water consumption, wastewater treatment, and reclaimed water production in the city. Private access – smart meter data on water consumption, location of the consumption points.
	Background data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse and climate action.
	Water data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The same as primary data.

Table 37: Data requirements for tool #24.

T3.5 tools	#24 Reclaimed water quality model in the distribution network	
T2.4 subtasks	T2.4.3d Reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution system	
Pre-processing stage	Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hydraulic engineering experts in urban management, municipal, and water utility contexts.
	Case extent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessment of the need for disinfection and residual chlorine in the design of distribution networks or, in the case of already constructed networks, to evaluate the disinfection efficiency and introduce adjustments as needed for water safety.
	Baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complete hydraulic and water quality extended-period simulation model for pressure flow networks, designed to simulate the advection, mixing, and transformation of waterborne parameters and the chlorine decay (residual disinfectant management) in reclaimed water.

	Input data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This tool includes complete descriptors for network assets, demands, operational constraints and rules, and state variables describing hydraulics, travel time, and advection/transformation of water quality parameters (incl. free- or combined chlorine content).
	Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP1/T1.3 training action scheduled for February 15, 2024
	Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water smart meters, chlorine sensors, etc.
Input data	Primary data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water demand descriptors. Reclaimed water supply descriptors.
	Background data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse, water losses management.
	Water data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water quality (WQ) descriptors: WQ boundary conditions (e.g., chlorine concentration, ammonium concentration), WQ formulation(s) Water network operation descriptors: e.g., flow, velocity, pressure.
	Additional data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Network descriptors: e.g., irrigation network plant, pipe diameters, location of irrigation devices (e.g., sprinklers), irrigation schedule.

Table 38: Data requirements for tool #25.

T3.5 tools	#25 Water-Energy-Phosphorus balance planning	
T2.4 subtasks	T2.4.3a Urban W-E-P balance	
Pre-processing stage	Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal, and water utility contexts
	Case extent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tool is applicable to any demand-driven matchmaking problem (as it is, requiring no modification).
	Baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardized means to combine and assess water source combinations to satisfy specific demands.
	Input data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The matchmaking environment is driven by the demand(s) to be satisfied, translated as time series of required monthly volumes over a pre-specified period. The supply and demand alternative combinations are assessed through a range of user-selected metrics (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content).
	Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP1/T1.3 training action scheduled for April 18, 2024.
	Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water meters – supply and demand.
Input data	Primary data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water demand descriptors. Water supply descriptors.

	Background data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse and climate action. • National regulations: e.g., Decree-Law 119/2019 on water reuse. • European regulations: e.g., Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (recast) (new proposal under approval).
	Water data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water descriptors: volumes (availability/supply and consumption/demand), water price (supply). • Related energy descriptors: energy content water (supply). • Related phosphorus descriptors: P concentration in reclaimed water (supply).
	Additional data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alternative specific costs: CAPEX and OPEX, energy. • Carbon footprint.

Table 39: Data requirements for tool #27.

T3.5 tools		#27 Risk assessment for urban water reuse
T2.4 subtasks		T2.4.3b Risk management - health component T2.4.3c Risk management - groundwater component
Pre-processing stage	Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water demand planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal and water utility contexts.
	Case extent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human health and environmental risk assessment associated to water reuse in agriculture.
	Baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardized means for building the hazard exposure scenarios and to assess the risk associated with each scenario.
	Input data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Descriptors of the main features of the urban facility (e.g., public park) that may impact the human and environment exposure to the hazards present in the reclaimed water. • Human health and environmental risk assessment requires basic knowledge of risk management and of the legislation applicable to water reuse.
	Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP1/T1.3 training action scheduled for March 14, 2024.
Input data	Primary data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water demand descriptors relevant for risk assessment.
	Background data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse and climate action. • National (Portuguese) regulation: Decree-Law 119/2019 on water reuse. • European regulation: Reg. (EU) 741/2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse in agricultural irrigation. • International standards: e.g., ISO 16075-2:2020, ISO 20426:2018, ISO 20761:2018.
	Water data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reclaimed water quality.

Additional data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On risk treatment measures.
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Table 40: Data requirements for tool #33.

T3.5 tool		#33 Climate readiness certification
T2.4 subtask		T2.4.4 Water-smart for climate ready certificates
Pre-processing stage	Actors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Householders, urban planners, municipalities, the building industry, and Climate Ready Certificates auditors.
	Case extent	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Link to other housing certification system.
	Baseline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A single certificate to assess the water efficiency, the water-energy nexus performance, and the climate adaptation evaluation of households, buildings, and neighbourhoods. The evaluated projects can be in the design phase, new construction, or in use.
	Input data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The CRC methodology has closed questions that can be answered by a single option, multiple options or percentages. Each of the 96 evaluation criteria has an associated score and the answers are ordered by descending score.
	Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP1/T1.3 training action scheduled for December 12, 2023
	Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water meters, water pressure sensors.
Input data	Primary data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Households, buildings, and neighbourhoods – description of water distribution network and related equipment and devices
	Background data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse and climate action. European standards: e.g., EN 16941 series on on-site non-potable water systems.
	Water data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water quality descriptors: e.g., chlorine concentration (if water supplies (e.g., treated greywater) other than drinking water are used for non-potables uses). Water network descriptors: e.g., flow rates, pressure.
	Additional data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy descriptors (onsite systems): e.g., energy consumption in water distribution, energy consumption in water treatment. Climate adaptation descriptors: e.g., climate risks maps, climate adaptation measures targeted to housing.

8.2.4 Setup process and application

Table 41 to Table 46 present information about the setup process and application of the Lisbon LL tools #17, #20, #24, #25, #27, and #33, respectively. For each tool, the related WP2 task(s) for pilot data collection is (are) presented.

Table 41: Setup process and application: tool #17

T3.5 tool	#17 Environment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action
T2.4 subtask	T2.4.3a Urban W-E-P balance T2.4.3b Risk management - health component T2.4.3c Risk management - groundwater component T2.4.3d Reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution system
Data inputs and model initialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tool allows for the specification of the key parameters: objectives, timesteps, metrics, alternatives. There is also the ability to import or export from/to a dedicated Excel® format, which facilitates sharing of results or further manipulation of the analysis. When the tool is started, it displays the available analyses (imported from tool #25) as well as the option to create a new one. When an alternative is created here, its values are either typed in on this screen or imported using the Excel® import/export facility. An analysis contains a set of alternatives, a set of metrics to assess them, over a set of timesteps. It may include the specification of different scenarios (external contexts).
Parameters and assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Most of the metrics are imported directly from a linked Matchmaking analysis (tool #25), along with the alternatives, using the option available through the last item on the menu of tool #17. The user can also add new metrics directly in this environment by filling out the Data Table, which contains the metrics' values for each alternative at each time step. This applies to water reuse risk metrics (tools #24 and #27). Other metrics can be defined by the user. The user introduces in the Metrics Editor the relationship between the metric's 'real world' values and a standardized 0-to-3 scale that is used throughout the app, effectively turning each metric into an index. Metrics may be given a relative weight from a closed list (0.5, 1, 2) – this is used later when ranking the alternatives.
Temporal or spatial scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monthly, annual Neighbourhood, city, region
Design of scenarios	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The baseline scenario corresponds to the “business as usual” alternative (first year of the planning timeline). The supply and demand alternative combinations are assessed over a targeted period (planning horizon). The time frame for evaluating the impact of the plan is the analysis horizon. The 3D cube of tool #17 provides an overview of the decisional problem with the 3 dimensions – alternatives (Z-axis) over time (Y-axis) and across all metrics (X-axis) – simultaneously displayed. This allows for a unique overall perception of the dynamics of decision among the alternatives.
Deployment of the tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This tool may be applied to any decisional problem of the same type (alternatives vs. metrics over time). In the implementation that is embodied in Tool #17, it is designed to work in tandem with Tool #25 and assess the supply/demand matchmaking alternatives developed there.

Table 42: Setup process and application: tool #20

T3.5 tool	#20 Urban Water Cycle Observatory
T2.4 subtask	T2.4.2 Water matrix and concepts behind water observatory
Data inputs and model initialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public access – open data on water consumption, wastewater treatment, and reclaimed water production in the city. Private access – water consumption per facility, aggregation per type of use, associated costs, performance indicators, georeferencing of facilities.
Parameters and assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tool #20 allows the identification and quantification of the main water flows in the city of Lisbon, disaggregating, whenever possible, the consumption by type of user and type of use. In this sense, the information provided allows the characterization of Lisbon's territory regarding water supply and wastewater collection and treatment.
Temporal and spatial scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In terms of scale application, public access has a broader implementation at the city scale, as the private access can be implemented at an entity or even at a single water meter scale.
Design of scenarios	NA
Deployment of the tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public access – is in use by the Lisbon Municipality in the scope of the Lisbon Living Lab. Additionally, it is starting to be well known by citizens, resident's associations, NGOs, etc. Private access – is in use by the Lisbon Municipality in the scope of the Lisbon Living Lab. Additionally, there are two other entities, associated to Lisboa E-Nova, that are using this private access for water, such as the public passenger transport company (buses and trams).

Table 43: Setup process and application: tool #24

T3.5 tool	#24 Reclaimed water quality model in the distribution network
T2.4 subtask	T2.4.3d Reclaimed water quality modelling in the distribution system
Data inputs and model initialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cadastral and demand data and operational parameters to simulate the movement, mixing, and dynamics of key reclaimed water parameters throughout the network. The primary input for the hydraulic and water quality model is an Epanet.INP file and an EPANET MSX file, respectively. The model runs based on those two files and the interface allows for querying of results as well as full visualisation in BASEFORM's 3D environment.
Parameters and assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Parameters for water quality modelling of reclaimed water distribution networks, incorporating sensor data (e.g., flow, chlorine residuals, temperature, turbidity, pH).
Temporal and spatial scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Minutes, days. Urban water distribution network or bulk water network.

Design of scenarios	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This tool offers a unique standardized means to compare reclaimed water supply/demand combinations through multiple criteria, with a purposefully developed formulation for reclaimed water (for non-potable, unrestricted urban reuse in Lisbon LL), on top of advanced hydraulics simulation capabilities.
Deployment of the tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tool #24's model is self-contained and as such may be used on its own to fulfil its primary purpose. However, in the context of the project, it aims at being used in conjunction with tool #25 to qualifying the supply/demand alternatives developed there, from the viewpoint of assessing the risks incurred in transport and distribution of the reclaimed water, in the Lisbon LL case, for non-potable, unrestricted urban reuse.

Table 44: Setup process and application: tool #25

T3.5 tool	#25 Water-Energy-Phosphorus balance planning
T2.4 subtask	T2.4.3a Urban W-E-P balance
Data inputs and model initialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tool allows for the specification of the key parameters: geolocation of water demands and water supplies, metrics (e.g., costs, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content), alternative descriptors. The tool allows the import of time series from a dedicated Excel® format for the following data: water volumes (availability/supply and consumption/demand), water price (supply), phosphorus content in water (supply), phosphorus fertilization (demand). These data series consist of the user's forecast for the evolution of the values of these variables over the planning period. When the tool is started, the user is asked to register potential sources, with corresponding time series of available volumes taking place in the same time window, though not necessarily spanning its entirety. The user is then asked to combine the available sources to make up the required monthly volumes, while complying with the energy and nutrients contents as desired. Such combinations are called 'alternatives' and are characterized by the degree to which they satisfy the required volumes over time, as well as by their energy consumption, nutrients contents, and cost. One or more alternatives will be designed to solve the demand problem at stake.
Parameters and assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The supply and demand alternative combinations are assessed and matched through a range of user-selected metrics (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content) over a targeted period.
Temporal and spatial scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monthly, annual. Urban facility (e.g., public park), neighbourhood, city, region (the software allows for full geographic representation of the sources and demands).
Design of scenarios	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> When the tool #25 is started, it displays the available analyses as well as the option to create a new one (top right). An analysis contains one or more matchmaking alternatives for a given supply/demand application case, as well as a set of metrics and a range of analysis timesteps.

Deployment of the tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tool #25 is autonomous and may be deployed on its own or in conjunction with tools #17 and #27. The tool is applicable to any demand-driven matchmaking problem without requiring modification.
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Table 45: Setup process and application: tool #27

T3.5 tool	#27 Risk assessment for urban water reuse
T2.4 subtasks	T2.4.3b Risk management - health component T2.4.3c Risk management - groundwater component
Data inputs and model initialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In each alternative, each urban facility (e.g., public park) with water demand satisfied with reclaimed water is tested for human health and for environmental risks. Tool #27 provides a structured analysis of the water reuse system. In the menu “Configuration”, the user is asked to describe the following groups of information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Components” organized in 5 subgroups: “Hazards”, “Exposure routes”, “Exposure sites”, “Activities”, and “Population or environment at risk”. The user must fill in the fields “Category” and “Name” of every component. “Barriers”, including the indication of “Name”, “Expected Log removal value”, “Number of barriers”, and “Reference” of this information. “Preventive measures”. For each one, the user must fill in the field “Name” of every measure. “Hazardous events”. The user must fill in the field “Name” of every hazardous event. The data input in the configuration menu provides the necessary information for the risk assessment process, which is organised in the following steps: risk identification, risk analysis and risk treatment. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The risk analysis is carried out in the “Analysis” menu, scenario by scenario. After selecting the demand (i.e., a green area irrigated with reclaimed water), the user describes the scenarios together with the respective risk assessment using the menu “Create scenario”. This menu sequentially presents a set of fields that are filled in with information provided in the "configuration" menu or require rating a of the likelihood of exposure to hazards or the potential damage to the population or environment at risk.
Parameters and assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The risk analysis is done for every defined exposure scenario, assigning to each scenario a rating for the likelihood of exposure to the hazards, as well as a rating of the harm that might result to the recipient (persons and environment). The levels used for the classification of likelihood and harm are predefined (i.e., not available for configuration by the user). The risk assessment ends with the comparison of the results of the risk analysis with the established criteria to determine whether the residual risk is tolerable, using a risk matrix.
Temporal and spatial scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Annual. Urban facility (e.g., public park).

Design of scenarios	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool #27 is a standardized means for building hazard exposure scenarios and assessing the risk related to each scenario. • Exposure scenarios set out how and under what circumstances people and the environment may be exposed to hazards. To facilitate the construction of exposure scenarios to hazards, a structured methodology was developed based on three questions: "what?", "why?", and "how?" (Ribeiro and Rosa, 2022). In the first moment ("what"), an analysis of the water reuse system is made to identify the constituent elements, those that may be at the basis of the risk. Next ("why"), the link between the elements of the system is identified. Finally ("how"), credible combinations between system elements are described that correspond to normal situations of system use that may, through the influence of hazardous events, result in a risk to the recipients. This methodology is embedded in tool #27.
Deployment of the tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The tool #27 is autonomous and may be deployed on its own or in conjunction with tools #17 and #25. The tool is applicable to human health and environmental risk assessment related with water reuse in irrigation and other non-potable urban uses, aligning with principles established in European and Portuguese legislation (Reg. (EU) 741/2020 and Decree-Law 119/2019, respectively), as well as with relevant ISO standards (e.g., ISO 16075-2:2020 and ISO 20426:2018).

Table 46: Setup process and application: tool #33

T3.5 tool	#33 Climate readiness certification
T2.4 subtask	T2.4.4 Water-smart for climate ready certificates
Data inputs and model initialisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The methodology has closed questions that can be answered by a single option, multiple options or percentages. Each criterion has an associated score and the answers are ordered by descending score. The answer with the most points is always the first option. In the case of a criteria that does not apply and as such is not evaluated, the auditor can exclude it and its score is proportionally distributed to the other methodology criteria.
Parameters and assumptions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The CRC methodology encompasses three dimensions: water efficiency, water-energy nexus and climate adaptation. Overall, it has 96 evaluation criteria: 53 criteria in the water efficiency dimension, 23 criteria in the water energy nexus, and 20 in the climate adaptation. • All these criteria are evaluated on three different scales of applicability: household, building and neighbourhood, though some of the criteria are not applicable to the household and outdoor space analyses.
Temporal and spatial scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NA • Household, building and neighbourhood.
Design of scenarios	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NA
Deployment of the tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Once the web tool is operational (October 2023), the auditors will be able to select the building typology to be certified, fill out the CRC methodology directly in the web tool and the platform will calculate the class of each dimension, the overall class and issue the CRC certificate.

8.2.5 Results

Having in mind the **Lisbon LL ambition** (section 8.1), the following results can be drawn at this moment for tools #25, #24, #27, and #17 (coherently with the outputs illustrated in Figure 117) and for tools #20 and #33:

1. Improving water supply-demand management

- **Tool #25 W-E-P balance planning** was successfully developed and as planned, is a matchmaking environment that enables the design of supply solutions driven by the demand(s) to be satisfied and translated as time series of required monthly volumes over a pre-specified period – “alternatives”. An “alternative” consists of the combination of the available water sources to make up the required monthly volumes in a predefined group of water demand points (e.g., green areas), while complying with the energy and nutrient contents as desired. Such combinations are characterized by the degree to which they satisfy the required volumes over time, as well as by their energy consumption, nutrient content, and cost. By facilitating the linking of water consumption locations (geographic representation) with various information related to those water demand points, tool #25 can function as a design planning tool since it allows the testing of different water management solutions, which are easily translated by the alternatives.
- **Tool #25** was designed to function both as an information repository and as a communication channel between different stakeholders – critical issues during planning and developing water-smart projects. The information to be provided to the software consists of a time series of required monthly values of water volumes, water price or P consumption over a pre-specified period, and unit values with the estimation of some variables. The full geographic representation of the sources and demands helps planners and decision-makers in urban management, municipal, and water utility contexts define water supply solutions. Finally, the software allows the introduction of text to justify the information as well as the design of alternatives. It is considered that this aspect (i.e., introduction of text) is of great use, both in a revisit of the planning exercise, and in its consultation and discussion by different decision makers.
- The energy consumption associated with each alternative results from two factors: the energy consumption associated with water production (which naturally depends on the origin of the water), and the energy consumption associated with water distribution, i.e., placing the water at that point of consumption. This information, which results from the planner’s concrete knowledge of the locations of water consumption and available sources, is introduced in **Tool #25** through the description menu of each alternative. Tool #25 also includes information on water losses and carbon footprint related to each water source. In this way, it is possible to identify the contribution of the improved water supply-demand management to strategies implemented at the municipal level, through a water losses management plan or a climate action plan.
- **Tool #17 Environment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action** is completed and enables users to select the best water source combinations to satisfy specific non-potable uses and enables prioritizing strategic and tactical planning options on the management of water sources and water uses in an urban setting. The supply/demand alternative combinations are assessed through a range of standardized, user-selected performance, risk, and cost metrics, complementing those employed to qualify the initial

selection in Tool #25 (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content). To ensure the alignment of decisions for improving water supply/demand management with the Lisbon LL Strategic Agenda, the metrics correspond as much as possible to metrics integrated in the BWS Evaluation Framework (Tool #34) or else contribute to their calculation.

- **Tool #20 Urban Water Cycle Observatory** was upgraded as foreseen. Its public access component provides visually appealing information on the urban water cycle (including the consumption of drinking water, the treatment of wastewater and the production and use of reclaimed water) as a means of increasing citizens' water literacy, hoping to make them more willing to be active agents in managing water demand in the city. In 2022, there were 8500 visits to the website and until 22/06/2022, 7200 visits were registered. Its private access component can help those responsible for large water consumption (municipalities and private institutions of public interest) to be more efficient in managing water use in those facilities. Processing raw data from smart meters by type of use provides useful information.

2. Testing the use of alternative water sources – the case of water reuse

- **Tool #27 Risk assessment for urban water reuse** was successfully developed. It provides a user-friendly solution for carrying out human health and environmental risk assessments, requiring a basic knowledge of risk management and of the legislation applicable to water reuse. For this purpose, a methodology for hazard exposure scenario building was developed from scratch and a process for human health and environmental risk assessment based on ISO standards and the EU Regulation 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse was defined (Ribeiro and Rosa, 2022).
- **Tool #24 Reclaimed water quality model in the distribution network** is completed and tested in three pilots (distribution networks). It simulates the advection, mixing, and transformation of waterborne parameters in reclaimed water (Costa et al., 2021). It aims primarily at mapping and quantifying risk in reclaimed water distribution networks. In the case of Lisbon, where the strategy for water reuse is being decided, Tool #24 has significant potential for supporting the design and monitoring of a public reclaimed water distribution network.
- **Tool #25 W-E-P balance planning** allows the integration of phosphorus circularity in a more comprehensive decision-making process regarding the management of water supply/demand in municipal (and other) green areas. It conducts a phosphorus balance in water consumption sites (gardens and other green areas) by comparing the P fertilisation needs throughout the year with what can be supplied through reclaimed water. The assessment of the fertilisation potential from the reclaimed water use is aligned with the need to improve resource efficiency and support the circularity of phosphorus – phosphate rock and specific form of P4 are currently on the EU Critical Raw Material List.

3. Promoting climate adaptation in buildings

- “3” is the number to consider for the promotion of climate ready housing, as there are three aspects to consider: the evaluated dimensions (water efficiency, water-energy nexus and climate adaptation), the scale of analysis (household, building and neighbourhood) and the moment of certification (design phase, in construction and in use). This was the basis for the

development of the **Tool #33 Climate readiness certification**, which has been tested at the abovementioned scales of analysis.

This section will be completed with final results and reported through Milestone 32 at month 45 (which is suggested to be added).

8.3 Lessons extracted

Having in mind the **Lisbon LL ambition**, the following lessons can be drawn at this moment:

1. Improving water supply-demand management

Pros

- Since the goal is to optimise the use of water in the city for non-potable uses, the decision-making process should be demand driven, i.e., with a fit-for-purpose quality to satisfy an efficient water use, as developed (tools #25 and #17). The decision-making process must also ensure alignment between strategic and tactical planning (namely aligning T1.4 and T2.4 outputs).
- The integration of the energy component associated with water allows the management of the water supply/demand to contribute to other city objectives, such as energy neutrality and climate action (tools #25, #17, #33).

Challenges

- Compiling information about water demand for non-potable uses in the city and available water sources can be difficult. Applying tools that function as data repository (e.g., tools #25, #20) catalyses proper data management.
- Exploiting the full potential of a smart-water allocation in Lisbon requires the existence of a public reclaimed water distribution network (nowadays available only in some areas), with sound asset management.

2. Testing the use of alternative water sources – the case of water reuse

Pros

- Decision-making tools must provide structured, user-friendly methodologies for human health and environmental risk assessment, making expert-knowledge available for risk managers and stakeholders responsible for non-potable water uses in the city, as in tool #27.
- It is important to predict the evolution of water quality along the reclaimed water distribution network and, when necessary, the irrigation network, as developed in tool #24. This simulation allows one to assess the need for disinfection and chlorine residual supply in the design of distribution networks or, in the case of already constructed networks, to evaluate the efficiency of the disinfection process to introduce adjustments if necessary.

Challenges

- The simulation of the evolution of reclaimed water quality in distribution networks, namely in irrigation networks, requires a temporal and spatial granularity of the base data that may be difficult to achieve. The state of conservation of the water distribution network can affect its

hydraulic performance. These two aspects constrain the calibration of mathematical models, thus affecting the quality of simulation results.

- The results naturally depend on the quantity and quality of the information available for the calibration and use of the hydraulic and water quality models (as in tool #24). The effort required to obtain this information is largely compensated by the benefits that the control of the disinfection process of reclaimed water has on the risk management associated to water reuse, as well as on the investment and operational cost of the reuse system.
- The decision on at what point of a WWTP the treated wastewater should be subject to further treatment depends on the evolution of European regulations, particularly, the Directive 91/271/EEC concerning urban waste-water treatment, and it is important to recognise this uncertainty when planning on a strategic level. For example, for phosphorus, the likely more stringent limit values in effluent discharge to receiving waters may be avoided by promoting phosphorus circularity via water reuse for irrigation. This challenge on water discharge can turn into an opportunity for water reuse.

3. Promoting climate adaptation in buildings

Pros

- There is interest in the housing market in providing information on environmental aspects of buildings.

Challenges

- The major bottleneck found so far was the lack of technical documentation from the projects (household, building and neighbourhood) to be certified.

8.4 Summary table of the LL

Table 47: Template table for LL Lisbon

Title	Methods, algorithms and software for a smart allocation of the water quality (fit-for-purpose) and quantity (water efficiency) in Lisbon. The ambition is to (i) improve the water supply / demand management and ultimately the city's water-energy-phosphorus (WEP) footprint while increasing the green areas, (ii) promote the safe use of alternative sources (e.g., reclaimed water), and (iii) promote climate-ready (water-energy efficient, climate-change proof) housing.
Description	<p>Making Lisbon a water-smarter city implies the involvement of different stakeholders in the provision and use of water. The following approaches were considered for the desired transformation into a water-smarter society:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ To increase the citizens' awareness about the local context regarding the water use in the city via the provision of appellative information and to inform individual entities about their water consumption, in case of smart water metering (Tool #20). ▪ To support the decision-making process of water demand planners and managers in urban, municipal and water utility contexts, by delivering an overview of the current water supply and water demand in the city to enable prioritizing strategic and tactical planning options (Tools #17, #24, #25, and #27). ▪ To guide or assess the promotion of climate adaptation in housing via a certification process used by housing owners and planners (Tool #33).
Reference point	https://earth.google.com/web/@38.73328057,-9.14002902,76.18325293a,14074.25418275d,35y,0h,0t,0r

Location	Lisboa, Portugal
Country (-ies)	Portugal
URL	NA
Project	BWS
Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Water Scarcity, ▪ High drinking water demand due to dense or growing resident population and economy, ▪ Dependent on distant freshwater resources, ▪ Untapped efficiency potential of water resources, ▪ Need for safe water reuse schemes, including building and managing a dedicated, reclaimed water distribution system.
Tools/Product/Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environment for decision support and selection of alternative courses of action (#17) ▪ UWC observatory (#20) ▪ Reclaimed water quality model in the distribution network (#24) ▪ Water-energy-phosphorous balance planning (#25) ▪ Risk assessment for urban water reuse (#27) ▪ Climate-readiness certification tool (#33)
Technologies	1 ozone oxidation/reverse osmosis (O3/RO) pilot installed at Beirolas water resource recovery facility (WRRF) for demonstration of water reuse in the food industry, namely, in artisanal craft beer production (direct potable reuse, DPR)
Scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Tool #20: city level ▪ Tools #17, #24, #25, and #27: urban facility (e.g., public park), neighbourhood, city, region ▪ Tool #33: household, building and neighbourhood
Legislation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ National (Portuguese) legislation: Decree-Law 119/2019 on water reuse. ▪ European regulations: Reg. (EU) 741/2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse in agricultural irrigation and Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (recast) (new proposal under approval).
Synergistic benefits	To be reported in MS32.
Facts of the applied technologies	To be reported in MS32.
Key Performance Indicators	To be reported in MS32.
Requirements and conditions	To be reported in MS32.

Key lessons	<p>A selection of key lessons</p> <p>Pros:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Since the goal is to optimise the use of water in the city for non-potable uses, the decision-making process should be demand driven, i.e., with a fit-for-purpose quality to satisfy an efficient water use. ▪ Decision-making tools must provide structured, user-friendly methodologies for human health and environmental risk assessment, making expert-knowledge available for risk managers and stakeholders responsible for non-potable water uses in the city. ▪ There is interest in the housing market in providing information on environmental aspects of buildings. <p>Challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Compiling information about water demand for non-potable uses in the city and available water sources can be difficult. Applying tools that function as data repository catalyses a proper data management. ▪ The results naturally depend on the quantity and quality of the information available for the calibration and use of the hydraulic and water quality models. The effort required to obtain this information is largely compensated by the benefits that the control of the disinfection process of reclaimed water has on the risk management associated to water reuse, as well as on the investment and operational cost of the reuse system. ▪ Exploiting the full potential of a smart-water allocation in Lisbon requires the existence of a public reclaimed water distribution network (nowadays available only in some areas), with sound asset management.
Lessons learned from technology operation	To be reported in MS32 (suggested to be added in M45).
Technology performance and best practices	To be reported in MS32 (suggested to be added in M45).
Outcome of assessments	To be reported in MS32 (suggested to be added in M45).
Organisations	<p>The Lisbon LL gathers six partners:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ CML (Lisbon Municipality), with a linked third-party – LEN (Lisboa E-Nova). ▪ LNEC (Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil) ▪ ADTA (Águas do Tejo Atlântico) ▪ ADENE (Agência para a Energia) ▪ ICS-UL (Instituto de Ciências Sociais da Universidade de Lisboa)
Contact persons	<p>Maria João Rosa, mjrosa@lnec.pt, LNEC (LL mentor)</p> <p>Rita Ribeiro, ribeiro@lnec.pt, LNEC (LL deputy-mentor)</p> <p>Pedro Teixeira, pedro.teixeira@cm-lisboa.pt, CML (LL owner)</p>
Data Manager	Not available at this stage.
Costs	Not available at this stage.
Tags	#reuse #water #multicriteria #supply #demand
Publications/Reference	<p>Costa, J., Mesquita, E., Ferreira, F., Rosa, M. J., and Viegas, R. M. (2021). Identification and modelling of chlorine decay mechanisms in reclaimed water containing ammonia. <i>Sustainability</i>, 13(24), 13548.</p> <p>Ribeiro, R., Rosa, M.J. (2022). Avaliação do risco para a saúde humana associado à reutilização de água: construção de cenários de exposição. 20.º ENASB, Cascais, 24-26 November 2022, 5 p. (communication in a conference)</p>

9 Conclusions

The aim of BWS is to accelerate the transformation to water-smart economies and societies in coastal Europe and beyond. Among other results that the project delivers to achieve this objective, different smart data applications have been released to support more efficient and safe allocation and use of resources.

D3.5 reports the final release of 8 such applications (developed in tasks T3.2 – T3.7 in collaboration with the Living Labs) as part of the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit. The 8 tools have been applied and tested in 3 LLs. Those are Flanders, East Frisia and Lisbon. Summary and concluding remarks on the 8 tools of D3.5 are provided below. These are considered to be preliminary conclusions, as the tools will continuously be applied (and optimised where necessary) throughout the project duration:

UWOT (tool #22) is a tool which can be used for the simulation of the urban water cycle by modelling individual water uses and technologies and aggregating their combined effects at any scale e.g., regional. With regard to the Flanders case, the primary goal of its application was to assess the demonstrations in their regional context with regard to their impact on water availability and resilience of the water system in support of the two cases (a) exploring aspects of the storage basin and water production system in the city of Woumen, (b) modelling an upscaling of the stormwater retention pond in the area of Mechelen. UWOT has also been applied in the East Frisia LL where the goal was to simulate the water flows (water demand and supply points) in a test case and to investigate alternative scenarios based on different climatic and demand change conditions or with the implementation of partially decentralised technologies. One of the primary lessons learned from the tool's application in both cases was that the tool can be used to model the expected effectiveness of measures with regards to water quantity under different scenarios. However, results can be limited by data availability, and results should be validated together with stakeholders.

The regional demand-supply matching GIS tool (tool #23), as tested in the East Frisia case, is a QGIS plugin for data visualization and processing with the scope to match demand-supply at a regional level e.g., the user can see all available water sources with an emphasis on the distance by querying the location in GIS. Within BWS, it has been used to identify i) possible consumption hotspots and areas of water shortage, ii) alternative water resources or areas with available water sources and iii) water drain from one region to another region. Thus, it assists in creating awareness regarding the regional limitations of water availability in quantity and quality. From its application, it was proven that it has the potential to become a key monitoring and decision-making tool for sustainable water resources and water demand management in the region. However, its acceptance and usefulness very much depend on the input data available. The highest benefits from the tool can be derived if data sets are regularly updated and enriched by new information collected from stakeholders.

The short-term demand forecasting tool (tool #28) is another tool applied in the East Frisia LL. It is a tool which generates water demand forecasts for the next (or current) day, which can be used a) to identify high peak loads in certain regions that require actions by the water utility, b) to train machine learning models and use them to generate and visualize demand forecasts and c) to enable aggregations of forecasts for multiple smart meters to achieve the desired spatial resolution. The results of the case study application prove the usefulness of the tool for predicting future load profiles of municipal water demand in the districts under investigation. Nevertheless, it was realised that the accuracy of the prognosis very much depends on the positioning of smart meters in the network and

the demographic information available on this section of the supply network. For future studies, a large-scale implementation of smart meters would be desirable instead of summarized measurements of small city districts in order to enhance the prognoses' quality.

For the case of East Frisia, UWOT and the Short-term demand forecasting tool are based on a small-scale analysis, while the regional demand supply matching tool is used for large scale analyses. The data flow between the tools can therefore be described in the same way that UWOT and STDFT are producing water demand scenarios that can be included in the RDSMG for future-oriented scenarios.

QMRA+ (tool #26), applied and tested in the Flanders case, is a tool that helps users estimate the microbial health risk of using various water sources, including reuse of wastewater, to assess the exposure of humans to this product water and the pathogens it may contain after being treated. The tool has been used within BWS to evaluate various design and treatment options for the Flanders drinking water case regarding the microbial safety risks. In the Woumen case, QMRA+ was used to help design the effluent reuse demonstration system by comparing the safety of various treatment options and enhancing certain points of the existing drinking water system. Its application to the case study revealed that QMRA is a new and complex topic for most water professionals and other stakeholders. The QMRA+ tool proved to be very accessible, and users quickly learned the principles of QMRA through the tool and were at the same time able to apply these principles to the project. It also provided a common ground for discussions, thus avoiding discussions about the safety of various scenarios. A point of attention for interpreting the tool results is a lack of expert knowledge by the user. Insufficient understanding can lead to misinterpretation of results. The tool provides the best estimate of water safety based on typical systems elsewhere. However, all input variables show large differences between individual systems. Therefore, it rather assesses the potential of a system. Verification of local water quality and treatment performance is essential to draw conclusions about safety of the actual system. Therefore, in most cases it is recommended to use the tool with consultancy support. Note that the tool only focuses on microbial risks and does not consider costs, chemical parameters etc. Therefore, it is not suitable for complete optimization of e.g., a wastewater reuse plant.

SuTRa (tool #31) is a Python package to calculate the advective removal of microbial organisms (also called 'pathogens') from source to endpoint and it calculates the subsurface removal and concentration of the microbial organism over distance and with time. For the Flanders case, the SuTRa tool builds on the microbial risk assessment of QMRA+ to specifically model (plant) pathogen removal during subsurface passage of managed aquifer recharge and infiltration schemes. This helps determine the minimum design parameters and residence time required for pathogen removal. The outputs from SuTRa may support the regional analysis or similar studies in related projects by providing input parameters on subsurface passage if these are included in the conceptual design. From its application it was proven that the tool can be used to help determine the minimum transport time and/or distance for subsurface infiltration and storage solutions required to remove pathogens.

Flanders' work and outcomes suggested that the applied tools can be used in a synergistic way. QMRA+ and Sutra can also help inform the water system modelling done with UWOT and the Regional Analysis tool as they can give an indication of the microbial water quality. UWOT and the Regional Analysis tool can only model water quantities. However, considering water quality and safety requirements is essential for the successful implementation of water reuse. SuTRa can be used to help determine the minimum transport time and/or distance for subsurface infiltration and storage

solutions required to remove pathogens. These design parameters inform the boundary conditions for water system modelling.

The stormwater reuse management system (tool #21) which is documented in D3.4, is a management tool to control water level in the basin and optimize distribution to the irrigation system based on water level, water demand, and weather prediction of precipitation/storm events (for flood protection too). The tool is used in the Flanders case to control the outflow from the basin and the water distribution for irrigation to optimize the functioning of the basin for flood prevention and availability of water for irrigation during dry periods. The tool is intended to be used to control the basin inlet and outlet and distribute irrigation water to fields based on water availability and demand. Tool #21 is based on the specific design parameters and local situation of the stormwater management system and has a local scale. Nevertheless, the interplay of these two objectives (flood volume retention vis-à-vis coverage of agriculture needs) can be explored using water systems modelling.

The reclaimed water distribution network water quality model (tool #24) is one of the tools applied in the Lisbon LL and is suggested to be used integrally with tools #17, #25, and #27 (with tool #17 being reported in D3.4). It is a complete hydraulic and water quality extended-period simulation model for pressure flow networks, designed to simulate the advection, mixing and transformation of waterborne parameters in reused water. Within the project, it aims at being used in conjunction with tool #25 to qualify the supply/demand alternatives developed from the viewpoint of assessing the risks incurred in transport and distribution of the reclaimed water, in Lisbon LL case, for non-potable, unrestricted urban reuse. It complements Tool #25 in assessing the additional cost, risk and performance changes that may be required for the supply/demand combinations chosen to make use of existing or new distribution networks. From the application to the Lisbon case, where the strategy for water reuse is being decided, tool #24 has significant potential for supporting the design and monitoring of a public reclaimed water distribution network.

The water-energy-phosphorous balance planning module (tool #25), which is one more tool of the interconnected ones in the Lisbon LL, is a matchmaking environment where sources and demand points are combined to enable the design of supply solutions for a set of potential users of reused water. The supply and demand alternative combinations are assessed and matched through a range of user-selected metrics (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content) over a targeted period. For the Lisbon case it has been used for the matchmaking of water sources (potential supplies) and water demands to enable the design of supply chain solutions (the shorter and more circular the better) for a set of potential users of non-potable water, namely, reclaimed water and other water sources alternative to those currently in use (e.g., groundwater). The supply/demand alternative combinations (matches) over a target period are assessed through a range of performance and cost metrics, for supporting strategic and tactical (aligned) planning (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content). Tool #25 is autonomous and may be deployed on its own or in conjunction with tools #17 and #27. It is applicable to any demand-driven matchmaking problem without requiring modification. Further, it conducts a phosphorus balance in water consumption sites (gardens and other green areas) by comparing the P fertilisation needs throughout the year with what can be supplied through reclaimed water. The application of the tool to the Lisbon LL proved that it facilitates the linking of water consumption locations (geographic representation) with various information related to those water demand points. Thus, it can function as a design planning tool that allows to test different water management solutions, which are easily translated by the alternatives (i.e., combination of the available water sources to make up the required monthly volumes in a predefined group of water demand points (e.g., green areas), while complying

on the energy and nutrients contents as desired). Tool #25 was designed to function both as an information repository and as a communication channel between different stakeholders – critical issues during planning and water-smart projects. It also allows the integration of phosphorus circularity in a more comprehensive decision-making process regarding the management of water supply/demand in municipal (and other) green areas.

The **risk assessment for urban water reuse module (tool #27)** is a risk assessment framework that evaluates human and environmental risks incurred by the supply/demand combinations developed in Tool #25, based on a range of current risk standards and regulations. It is a module which is considered essential for the implementation of alternative water sources, especially in case of reclaimed water use (in irrigation and other non-potable urban uses) since it assists in the assessment of alternatives that are aligned with principles established in European and Portuguese legislation. Tool #27 works as a risk-based gatekeeper that must be cleared for any supply/demand combination to be considered for assessment in Tool #17. Depending on the risk level targeted for completion, the alternative examined will be rejected (eventually go back to tool #25 for redesign), or otherwise cleared and move on to Tool #17. The strength of this tool is that it can provide a user-friendly solution for carrying out human health and environmental risk assessments, requiring a basic knowledge of risk management and of the legislation applicable to water reuse.

As noted, tools #17, #24, #25, and #27 can be used separately. Nevertheless, the integrated use can support urban management authorities and water utilities in making smart and climate-resilient water decisions for an efficient water-energy-nutrient balance in the city including safe water reuse, by enabling direct comparison of alternatives for matching water supply and water demand to satisfy specific non-potable uses.

Further to the above tools documented in detail in D3.5, 10 more software solutions are reported in D3.4, as part of the final release of the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit. The two deliverables have been prepared in parallel to ensure alignment and consistency among the approaches and contents and in order to highlight the toolkits' complementarity. Such complementarity is defined by a high-level process described in detail in Chapter 4 and summarized in Table 48, which is a reference procedural framework for using the toolkits through the fundamental steps that have to be followed by people who aim at improving the water smartness of their systems. While the monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit aims at improving water smartness by supporting the steps of context awareness, decision making, management and monitoring and certification, the toolkit presented in this deliverable (D3.5) is focused on advanced analytics for providing detailed evidence in support of the decision-making step. This is achieved by providing the tools to conduct simulations, predictions, demand/supply match-making and other analyses (Table 48). Additionally, the two toolkits aim at providing solutions to assist in coping with the water related challenges (Figure 118) and to support each step of the urban water cycle while complementing each other, as depicted in Figure 119 and Figure 120.

Table 48: Overview of toolkits' solutions and apps used in the LLs.

	Alicante (Spain)	Bodø (Norway)	East Frisia (Germany)	Flanders (Belgium)	Lisbon (Portugal)	Venice (Italy)
Context awareness		(#30) Environmental Dashboard ¹			(#20) UWC observatory ¹	(#16) Water reuse strategic platform, enabled by Digital Enabler (#32) ¹
						(#19) Sludge management platform), enabled by Digital Enabler (#32) ¹
Advanced analysis			(#22) UWOT ²	(#22) UWOT ²	(#25) Water-energy-phosphorous balance planning module ²	
			(#23) Regional demand supply matching GIS tool ²	(#26) QMRA+ for water reuse and agriculture ²	(#24) Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model ²	
			(#28) Short-term demand forecasting tool ²	(#31) SuTRa ²	(#27) Risk assessment for urban water reuse module ²	
Decision making	(#18) Re-Actor ¹				(#17) Environment for decision support and alternative course selection ¹	
Management/ monitoring		(#29) Nessie system ¹		(# 21) Stormwater reuse management system ¹		
Certification					(#33) Climate-readiness certification toolkit ¹	

¹. *The monitoring, negotiation and decision support solutions toolkit*

². *The water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit*

Figure 118: 18 solutions of the 2 toolkits related to the urban water challenges.

Figure 119: Tools of the water cycle modelling and assessment solutions toolkit supporting each step of the urban water cycle.

Figure 120: 18 solutions of the 2 toolkits related to the urban water cycle steps.

Beyond complementarity of the two toolkits, replicability of the digital tools in other cities/regions is ensured by different actions and results that T3.8 is pursuing, by interacting with the rest of the project. In particular, D3.1 has delivered at M20 the BWS FIWARE approach with its interoperability guidelines (implementation guidelines, FIWARE and interoperability maturity levels) that aim to help developers conceive and realize tools that are easily integrated with third party systems through the use of open and standard APIs, thus boosting replicability. T3.8 and the corresponding deliverables D3.4 / D3.5 make reference to the results of D3.1 and in particular to the “interoperability maturity levels” to document the readiness of each tool to be integrated with other systems and its (potential for) FIWARE compatibility.

More than 1/3 of WP3 applications are FIWARE compatible. More in detail, WP3 delivers 19 applications (18 from T3.2-T3.7 - reported in the toolkits’ deliverables D3.4/D3.5 and 1 from T3.9) out of which 7 are FIWARE compliant. The tools that have been developed in T3.2-T3.7 and are FIWARE compatible are the following: 1. Water-reuse strategic platform (#16), 2. Sludge management platform (#19), 3. Short-term demand forecasting tool (#28), 4. Nessie System (#29), 5. Environmental Dashboard (#30) and 6. Digital Enabler (#32). Most of them are described in detail in D3.4, whereas the short-term demand forecasting tool (#28) can be found under section 5.7 of the current report.

Moreover, beyond investigating the need for conducting tactical joint meetings for WP3, WP2, WP1 and WP7 to better align efforts, replicability is supported by several synergies with such WPs that have been activated and will be further enhanced by:

- Intensifying discussion and exchange among the technology/tool developers in joint WP2/WP3 meetings and conducting additional ones upon demand,
- Allocating efforts for continuous collaboration with WP1 in developing training material and conducting training activities (possibly inviting also CoP members and not only project’s colleagues). Most of the training activities are planned for the last year of the project when developments of tools are mature.

- Using recordings of training actions on tools and disseminating them through the colleagues' networks and WP7 (website, social media and Marketplace). Training activities have already taken place and the produced material is available in the WE Marketplace under the detailed page of each tool (<https://mp.watereurope.eu/l/Product/>) and the project's website (<https://b-watersmart.eu/>).
- Highlighting replicability aspects and opportunities in the LLs work and communicating reports to a broader audience via WP7 (website, social media and WE Marketplace, e.g., information available in the case study section documenting lessons learned from tools' applications, etc.).

As next steps, contents related to results and lessons extracted for each LL after an extended application of the BWS digital tools will be updated through the new MS32 which is suggested to be added at month 45.

10 References

- Antzoulatos, G., Mourtziou, C., Stournara, P., Kouloglou, I.-O., Papadimitriou, N. Spyrou, D., Mentis, A., Nikolaidis, E., Karakostas, A., Kourtesis, D., Vrochidis, S., and Kompatsiaris, I. (2020). Making urban water smart: the SMART-WATER solution. *Water Science & Technology*. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2020.391>
- Arsiso, B. K., Tsidu, G. M., Stoffberg, G. H., and Tadesse, T. (2017). Climate change and population growth impacts on surface water supply and demand of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. *Climate Risk Management*, 18, 21-33.
- Bouziotas, D., Nikolopoulos, D., Monokrousou, K., Frijns, J., and Makropoulos, C. (2020). Design and simulation of circular water systems: the UWOT model.
- Bouziotas, D., van Duuren, D., van Alphen, H. J., Frijns, J., Nikolopoulos, D., and Makropoulos, C. (2019a). Towards circular water neighborhoods: Simulation-based decision support for integrated decentralized urban water systems. *Water (Switzerland)*, 11(6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/w11061227>
- Brown, T. C., Mahat, V., and Ramirez, J. A. (2019). Adaptation to future water shortages in the United States caused by population growth and climate change. *Earth's Future*, 7(3), 219-234.
- Butler, D., Memon, F.A., Makropoulos, C., Southall, A. and Clarke, L. (2010). *WaND – Guidance on water cycle management for new developments*. C690 CIRIA, London.
- Costa, J., Mesquita, E., Ferreira, F., Rosa, M. J., and Viegas, R. M. (2021). Identification and modelling of chlorine decay mechanisms in reclaimed water containing ammonia. *Sustainability*, 13(24), 13548.
- Decreto-Lei n.º 119/2019, de 21 de agosto / Decree-Law Water Reuse, Retrieved from <https://diariodarepublica.pt/dr/detalhe/decreto-lei/119-2019-124097549>
- DESSIN, Demonstrating Ecosystem Services Enabling Innovation in the Water Sector, EU FP7 project, 2014 – 2017, <https://dessin-project.eu/>.
- EEA (2010). *The European environment — state and outlook 2010 (SOER 2010): Thematic assessment — Water resources: quantity and flows*. European Environment Agency, Copenhagen.
- Ellen, H., and Jay, L. (2008). *Adapting California’s Water Management to Climate Change*. Published by PPIC (Public Policy institute of California) study, *Preparing California for a Changing Climate*, 46.
- Eriyagama, N., Smakhtin, V., Chandrapala, L., and Fernando, K. (2010). Impacts of climate change on water resources and agriculture in Sri Lanka: a review and preliminary vulnerability mapping.

Fiware4Water, FIWARE for the Next Generation Internet Services for the WATER sector, Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020), 2019 – 2022, <https://www.fiware4water.eu/>

Foti, R., Ramirez, J. A., and Brown, T. C. (2012). Vulnerability of US water supply to shortage: a technical document supporting the Forest Service 2010 RPA Assessment. Gen. Tech. Rep. RMRS-GTR-295. Fort Collins, CO: US Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Rocky Mountain Research Station. 147 p., 295.

Gerin, O., Bleys, B., and De Cuyper, K. (2014). Seasonal variation of hot and cold-water consumption in apartment buildings. In Proceedings of CIB W (Vol. 62, pp. 1-9).

Govindan, K., and Hasanagic, M. (2018). A systematic review on drivers, barriers, and practices towards circular economy: a supply chain perspective. 56(1–2), 278–311. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2017.1402141>

Guerra-Rodríguez, S., Oulego, P., Rodríguez, E., Singh, D. N., and Rodríguez-Chueca, J. (2020). Towards the Implementation of Circular Economy in the Wastewater Sector: Challenges and Opportunities. Water 2020, Vol. 12, Page 1431, 12(5), 1431. <https://doi.org/10.3390/W12051431>

Haasnoot, M., Kwakkel, J. H., Walker, W. E., and ter Maat, J. (2013). Dynamic adaptive policy pathways: A method for crafting robust decisions for a deeply uncertain world. Global Environmental Change, 23(2), 485–498. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GLOENVCHA.2012.12.006>

iWIDGET, Improved water efficiency through ICT technologies for integrated supply-demand side management, EU FP7 project, 2012 – 2015, <http://www.i-widget.eu/>.

Iyer, M., Doshi, S., Mishra, G., and Kumar, S. (2022). Smart Planning and Management of Urban Water Systems: The Case of Bhuj, India. Advances in 21st Century Human Settlements, 133–176. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-2386-9_3/FIGURES/22

Kirsten, J. H., Mark, S. (2011). J. and Stewart, J.C. (2011). Future Water Supply and Demand in the Okanagan Basin, British Columbia: A Scenario-Based Analysis of Multiple, Interacting Stressors. Published by Water Resource Management Journal.

Kossieris, P., Kozanis, S., Hashmi, A., Katsiri, E., Vamvakeridou-Lyroudia, L.S., Farmani, R., Makropoulos, C., Savic, D., 2014. A Web-based Platform for Water Efficient Households. Procedia Engineering, 89, 1128–1135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2014.11.234>.

Kossieris, P., Panayiotakis, A., Tzouka, K., Gerakopoulou, P., Rozos, E., Makropoulos, C., 2014. An eLearning Approach for Improving Household Water Efficiency. Procedia Engineering, 89, 1113–1119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2014.11.232>.

Kossieris, P., Pantazis, C., Makropoulos, C., 2021. Data-models for FIWARE-enabled smart applications for raw-water supply system modelling, management and operation. *Advances in Hydroinformatics: SIMHYDRO 2021, SimHydro 6th International Conference*, June 16 – 18 2021 (in press).

Lee, S. W., Sarp, S., Jeon, D. J., and Kim, J. H. (2015). Smart water grid: the future water management platform. *Desalination and Water Treatment*, 55(2), 339-346.

Liakopoulou, A., Makropoulos, C., Nikolopoulos, D., Monokrousou, K., and Karakatsanis, G. (2020). An urban water simulation model for the design, testing and economic viability assessment of distributed water management systems for a circular economy. *Environmental Sciences Proceedings*, 2(1), 14.

Makarigakis, A. K., and Jimenez-Cisneros, B. E. (2019). UNESCO's Contribution to Face Global Water Challenges. *Water* 2019, Vol. 11, Page 388, 11(2), 388. <https://doi.org/10.3390/W11020388>

Makropoulos, C. (2017). Thinking platforms for smarter urban water systems: fusing technical and socio-economic models and tools. *Geological Society, London, Special Publications*, 408(1), 201–219. <https://doi.org/10.1144/SP408.4>

Makropoulos, C. K., Natsis, K., Liu, S., Mittas, K., and Butler, D. (2008). Decision support for sustainable option selection in integrated urban water management. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 23(12), 1448–1460.

Makropoulos, C., Kossieris, P., Kozanis, S., Katsiri, E., Vamvakeridou-Lyroudia, L., 2014. From smart meters to smart decisions: web-based support for the water efficient household. *11th International Conference on Hydroinformatics, Proceedings HIC2014*, 17-21 August 2014, New York, USA, 2014.

Makropoulos, C., Nikolopoulos, D., Palmen, L., Kools, S., Segrave, A., Vries, D., Koop, S., van Alphen, H.J., Vonk, E., van Thienen, P., Rozos, E. and Medema, G. (2018). A resilience assessment method for urban water systems. *Urban Water Journal*. [Online]. 15 (4). p.pp. 316–328. Available from: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1573062X.2018.1457166>.

Makropoulos, C., Rozos, E., Tsoukalas, I., Plevri, A., Karakatsanis, G., Karagiannidis, L., Makri, E., Lioumis, C., Noutsopoulos, C., Mamais, D., Rippis, C. and Lytras, E. (2018b). Sewer-mining: A water reuse option supporting circular economy, public service provision and entrepreneurship. *Journal of Environmental Management*. [Online]. 216. p.pp. 285–298. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0301479717306928>.

Mandy Mbavarira, T., and Grimm, C. (2021). A Systemic View on Circular Economy in the Water Industry: Learnings from a Belgian and Dutch Case. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13063313>

Marsalek, J., Jiménez-Cisneros, B., Karamouz, M., Malmquist, P. A., Goldenfum, J., and Chocat, B. (2014). Urban water cycle processes and interactions: Urban water series - UNESCO-IHP. *Urban Water Cycle Processes and Interactions: Urban Water Series - UNESCO-IHP*, 78, 1–131.

Morseletto, P., Mooren, C. E., and Munaretto, S. (2022). Circular Economy of Water: Definition, Strategies and Challenges. *Circular Economy and Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43615-022-00165-x>

Okello, C., Tomasello, B., Greggio, N., Wambiji, N., and Antonellini, M. (2015). Impact of population growth and climate change on the freshwater resources of Lamu Island, Kenya. *Water*, 7(3), 1264–1290.

Plevri, A., Lytras, E., Samios, S., Lioumis, C., Monokrousou, K., and Makropoulos, C. (2020). Sewer Mining as A Basis for Technological, Business and Governance Solutions for Water in the Circular Economy: The NextGen Athens Demo. *The 4th EWaS International Conference: Valuing the Water, Carbon, Ecological Footprints of Human Activities*, 54. <https://doi.org/10.3390/environsciproc2020002054>

Plevri, A., Samios, S., Lytras, E., Papadopoulos, K., Lioumis, C., Lazari, A., Tazes, N., Monokrousou, K., and Makropoulos, C. (2019). Installation of a Sewer Mining Unit in the Athens Urban Tree Nursery. *16th International Conference on Environmental Science and Technology*.

Plevri, A.; Monokrousou, K.; Makropoulos, C.; Lioumis, C.; Tazes, N.; Lytras, E.; Samios, S.; Katsouras, G.; Tsalas, N. Sewer Mining as a Distributed Intervention for Water-Energy-Materials in the Circular Economy Suitable for Dense Urban Environments: A Real-World Demonstration in the City of Athens. *Water* 2021, 13, 2764. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13192764>

Pronk, G. J., Stofberg, S. F., Van Dooren, T. C. G. W., Dingemans, M. M. L., Frijns, J., Koeman-Stein, N. E., Smeets, P. W. M. H., and Bartholomeus, R. P. (2021). Increasing Water System Robustness in the Netherlands: Potential of Cross-Sectoral Water Reuse. *Water Resources Management*, 35(11), 3721–3735. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-021-02912-5>

Proposal for a revised Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (recast). Retrieved from https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/proposal-revised-urban-wastewater-treatment-directive_en

Raskin, P., Hansen, E., Zhu, Z., and Stavisky, D. (1992). Simulation of water supply and demand in the Aral Sea Region. *Water International*, 17(2), 55-67.

Regulation Water Reuse Agricultural Irrigation, Reg (EU) 2020/741 of 25 May 2020 on minimum requirements for water reuse. Retrieved from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32020R0741&from=EN>

Ribeiro, R., Rosa, M.J. (2022). Avaliação do risco para a saúde humana associado à reutilização de água: construção de cenários de exposição. 20.º ENASB, Cascais, 24-26 novembro 2022, 5 p. (communication in a conference)

Rochdane, S., Reichert, B., Messouli, M., Babqiqi, A., and Khebiza, M. Y. (2012). Climate change impacts on water supply and demand in Rheraya Watershed (Morocco), with potential adaptation strategies. *Water*, 4(1), 28-44.

Rozos, E. and Makropoulos, C. (2013). Source to tap urban water cycle modelling. *Environmental Modelling & Software*. [Online]. 41. p.pp. 139–150. Available from: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364815212002861>. [Accessed: 1 February 2013].

Rozos, E., and C. Makropoulos (2012). Assessing the combined benefits of water recycling technologies by modelling the total urban water cycle, *Urban Water Journal*, 9 (1), doi:10.1080/1573062X.2011.630096.

Rozos, E., and C. Makropoulos (2013). Source to tap urban water cycle modelling, *Environmental Modelling and Software*, 41, 139-150, doi:10.1016/j.envsoft.2012.11.015, Elsevier.

Rozos, E., C. Makropoulos, and C. Maksimovic (2013). Rethinking urban areas: an example of an integrated blue-green approach, *Water Science and Technology: Water Supply*, 13 (6), 1534-1542, doi:10.2166/ws.2013.140.

Rozos, E., C. Makropoulos, and D. Butler (2010). Design robustness of local water-recycling schemes, *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management - ASCE*, 136 (5), 531-538, doi:/10.1061/(ASCE)WR.19.

Smeets, P. W. M. H., and Miehe, U. (2019, 16 – 20 June). AquaNES QMRA tool: a webtool for quantitative microbial risk assessment of water reuse applications. Paper presented at the Workshop 12th IWA International Conference on Water Reclamation and Reuse, Berlin, Germany.

Smol, M., Adam, C., and Preisner, M. (2020). Circular economy model framework in the European water and wastewater sector. *Journal of Material Cycles and Waste Management*, 22(3), 682–697. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10163-019-00960-z>

Stewart, G., and Rout, R. S. (2007). Reasonable Stock Water Requirements: Guidelines for Resource Consent Applications. Horizons Regional Council.

SUBSOL, bringing coastal SUBsurface water SOLutions to the market, Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020), 2015 – 2018, <http://www.subsol.org/about-subsol/>.

Thomas, J. S., and Durham, B. (2003). Integrated water resource management: looking at the whole picture. *Desalination*, 156(1-3), 21-28.

Wackerbauer, J. (2017) A Forecast of Industrial and Commercial Drinking Water Consumption in Hamburg. *Open Access Library Journal*, 4: e3425. <https://doi.org/10.4236/oalib.1103425>

Walker, W. E., Haasnoot, M., and Kwakkel, J. H. (2013). Adapt or perish: A review of planning approaches for adaptation under deep uncertainty. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 5(3), 955–979. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su5030955>

Zisopoulou, K., and Panagoulia, D. (2021). An in-depth analysis of physical blue and green water scarcity in agriculture in terms of causes and events and perceived amenability to economic interpretation. *Water*, 13(12), 1693.

Zisopoulou, K., and Panagoulia, D. (2021). An in-depth analysis of physical blue and green water scarcity in agriculture in terms of causes and events and perceived amenability to economic interpretation. *Water*, 13(12), 1693.

11 Online references

BASEFORM (2022, May 2022). Products. <https://baseform.com/np4/product/>

http://lisboaenova.org/images/stories/Lisboaenova/Ebook_Agua/mobile/index.html#p=1

<http://www.select4cities.eu>

<https://baseform.com/np4/product/>

<https://lisboaenova.org/lancamento-da-nova-versao-da-plataforma-observatorios-lisboa/>

<https://lisboaenova.org/relancamento-dos-observatorios-lisboa/>

<https://www.adene.pt/camara-municipal-de-lisboa-distingue-adene-pela-cooperacao-no-portal-observatorios-lisboa/>

<https://www.eng.it/resources/platform/digital-enabler/doc/city-enabler-brochure.pdf>

<https://www.lisboa.pt/capital-verde-2020/noticias/detalhe/relancamento-dos-observatorios-de-lisboa>

<https://www.lisboa.pt/cidade/ambiente/qualidade-ambiental/agua>

12 Annex A: Technology Readiness Level

Where a topic description refers to a TRL, the following definitions apply, unless otherwise specified.

Table 49: Technology readiness levels.

Level	Description
Level 1 - Basic Research: basic principles are observed and reported	Lowest level of technology readiness. Scientific research begins to be translated into applied research and development. Examples might include fundamental investigations and paper studies.
Level 2 – Applied Research: technology concept and/or application formulated	Once basic principles are observed, practical applications can be formulated. Examples are limited to analytic studies and experimentation.
Level 3 – Critical function, proof of concept established	Active research and development are initiated. Laboratory studies aim to validate analytical predictions of separate components of the technology. Examples include components that are not yet integrated or representative.
Level 4 – Laboratory testing of prototype component or process	Design, development and lab testing of technological components are performed. Here, basic technological components are integrated to establish that they will work together. This is a relatively “low fidelity” prototype in comparison with the eventual system.
Level 5 – Laboratory testing of integrated system	The basic technological components are integrated together with realistic supporting elements to be tested in a simulated environment. This is a “high fidelity” prototype compared to the eventual system.
Level 6 – Prototype system verified	The prototype, which is well beyond that of level 5, is tested in a relevant environment. The system or process demonstration is carried out in an operational environment.
Level 7 – Integrated pilot system demonstrated	Prototype is near, or at, planned operational system level. The final design is virtually complete. The goal of this stage is to remove engineering and manufacturing risk.
Level 8 – System incorporated in commercial design	Technology has been proven to work in its final form under the expected conditions. In most cases, this level represents the end of true system development.
Level 9 – System ready for full scale deployment	Here, the technology in its final form is ready for commercial deployment.
Level beyond 9 - Market introduction	The product, process or service is launched commercially, marketed to and adopted by a group of customers (including public authorities).

13 Annex B: Template tables

Below there are the template tables that have been used in previous sections for the description of tools and their application to the different cases studies. Instructions of anticipated information are included in each field. It is noted that the definition of those tables and their fields has been done in collaboration with WP7. The collected information is used to populate the Water Europe Marketplace (aka. the Knowledge Portal of WP7, Task 7.1).

Table 50: Template table for tool's attributes and description.

Tool's attribute	Description
Type of product	<p>Select which of the following statements describe best your product. You may choose more than one statement.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A software supporting the Circular Economy • A hardware product or a technological device around the Circular Economy • A service, offered as part of a Circular Economy enabling portfolio • A methodology or a process related with the Circular Economy
Name	Name of the tool/product.
Description	General information on the product, its components and the scope of application
Abbreviation	The acronym/abbreviation of the tool/product (if available)
URL	Related URL, providing further information on the product/tool, if available
Costs	If applicable, describe the costs and conditions for purchasing the product, obtaining a license or providing the service
Target audience	Profile of users who would find the tool/product useful or/and are qualified to use it.
Actors, roles and interactions	Actors involved (e.g., water utilities, industries, technology providers, end-users), their roles and their interactions.
Unique selling points /Added Value/Innovation	Description of the unique selling points, added value and innovation elements of the tool, product or service
TRL	The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) giving an estimate of the technology maturity of the related tool, product or service.
Technical requirements	Technical requirements to obtain, install or run the tool, product or service
Environment	Operating environment in which the tool/application runs e.g., Microsoft Windows (if applicable)
Version	Current stable version number or version code of the tool, product or service (if applicable)
Initial release	Year of the initial release of the tool (if applicable)
License type	General license type (free or commercial) (if applicable)

Programming language/technologies used	<i>The programming languages or/and major technologies which are used to implement the tool/application (if applicable).</i>
Open interface	<i>Describe the different integrations options, if any, which are supported by the tool/product e.g., web service, libraries, etc. (if applicable)</i>
Graphical User Interface / Headless software	<i>Describe if the tool can be executed in headless mode, batch mode, if it is command line executed and/or if it has GUI, etc. (if applicable)</i>
Supported spatial scales	<i>Different spatial scales that can be supported by the tool and applied e.g., household, neighbourhood, city, region, etc. (if applicable)</i>
Supported temporal scales	<i>Different temporal scales that can be supported by the tool and applied e.g., daily, annual, etc. (if applicable)</i>
Water Use Types	<i>Indicate the water use types with which the tool is related e.g., urban, industrial, rural and agriculture</i>
Compatibility with FIWARE	<i>Indicate whether the tool is compatible with FIWARE or not.</i>
Organisations	<i>Organisation(-s) that own the tool, product or service.</i>
Contact details	<i>Contact details of the person related to the tool, product or service. Needs to include at least first name, last name and email.</i>
Data Manager	<i>Indicate the persons who will be responsible to monitor and update the information about the tool/product/service in the Water Europe Marketplace (https://mp.watereurope.eu/l/Product/). Include the contact details by providing at least first name, last name and email.</i>
Technologies	<i>Circular economy technologies related with the tool, product or service. You may examine the Overview of Technologies available in the Water Europe Marketplace (https://mp.watereurope.eu/technologies/) and select among them or add new technologies in order to be included.</i>
Tags	<i>Tags related with the tool, product or service.</i>
Images	<i>Characteristic images or schematic representations of the tool. In cases where the file is provided as a separate file, all known formats up to a certain size which are supported by web browsers are accepted (e.g., jpeg, png). The file must not exceed the size of 5MB.</i>
Caption/Source	<i>Caption needs to be provided for each illustration in textual format, as well as its reference/source that should be included.</i>
Publications	<i>Publications related with the tool, product or service</i>

Table 51: Template table for the application of tools/technologies to case studies and LL.

Indicative application of the tool	
Title	<i>Title of the case study where the tool/product/service is applied.</i>
Description	<i>Brief description of the application of the tool/product/service to the case study/Living Lab.</i>

Reference point	Indicate a point location that best represents the application of the tool to the Case Study/Living Lab by sharing a Google's maps location link.
Location	The name of the city /area/geographical location which best represents the application of the tool to the Case Study/Living Lab.
Country (-ies)	Countries hosting the case study/Living Lab where the tool has been applied.
URL	Related URL, providing further information on the application of product/tool to the Case Study/Living Lab, if available
Project	Related project where the application of tools to the Case Study/Living Lab has been applied (if applicable)
Challenges	<p>Select the challenges that are addressed through the application of tools and/or technologies. Multiple selection can be made:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Scarcity, • Limitations to water reuse due to high salinity/nitrates, • Limitations to water reuse and recovery due to low acceptance, • High drinking water demand due to dense or growing resident population and economy, • Untapped efficiency potential of water resources, • High or increasing irrigation water demand for agriculture, • Groundwater overexploitation, • Water quality deterioration, • Dependent on distant freshwater resources, • Increasing water demand by growing industrial sectors, • Need for reuse and recovery schemes for wastewater & sludge, • Other
Tools/Product/Services	Tools/Product/Services that have been applied in the case study/Living Lab.
Technologies	Circular economy technologies related with the tool, product or service. You may examine the Overview of Technologies available in the Water Europe Marketplace (https://mp.watereurope.eu/technologies/) and select among them or add new technologies in order to be included.
Scales	<p>Typical operational scales of this case study/Living Lab related to the application of tool(-s)/technology(-ies), i.e., the scales at which the solutions/technologies are implemented and have an impact.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local (e.g., single treatment plant, industrial site or city quarter), • City (whole city level), • Metropolitan (extending beyond the city e.g., into neighbouring cities or peri-urban fringe area), • Regional (across several municipalities and/or administrative borders, incl. rural areas), • National (relating to a whole country), • Other
Legislation	EU/National/Regional/Local regulations that are related to the application of tools/technologies to the LLs e.g., limits of quality parameters of reused water, etc (if applicable).
Synergistic benefits	Description of the synergistic benefits that came along from the application of the tool/product/services to the case study and its combination with other tool(s) and/or related technologies.
Facts of the applied technologies	Capacity, production rate or yield, energy consumption, CAPEX, OPEX. (If applicable, related to the technologies and the WP2 work).

Key Performance Indicators	<i>KPIs for every technology and comparison to the situation before its implementation (if applicable, related to the technologies and the WP2 work).</i>
Requirements and conditions	<i>Requirements, conditions or constraints that might have been encountered for the application of the tool/product/service in the case study.</i>
Key lessons	<i>Brief textual description of the key lessons learned from the application of tools to the case study and the potential combined used of technologies/tools.</i>
Lessons learned from technology operation	<i>Required competence, maintenance, technological risk (downtimes and its avoidance). If applicable, related to the technologies and the WP2 work.</i>
Best practices	<i>Best practice guidelines to construct and operate the applied technologies (if applicable, related to the technologies and the WP2 work).</i>
Outcome of assessments	<i>LCA, LCC, QMRA, QCRA, Technical RA, etc. (if applicable, related to the technologies and the WP2 work)</i>
Organisations	<i>Entities which are involved in the case study/Living Lab.</i>
Contact persons	<i>Contact persons for this case study where the tool/product has been applied. Needs to include at least first name, last name, email and organisation.</i>
Data Manager	<i>Indicate the persons who will be responsible to monitor and update the information about the application of the tool/product/service to the specific case study/LL in the Water Europe Marketplace (https://mp.watereurope.eu/CaseStudy). Include the contact details by providing at least first name, last name and email.</i>
Costs	<i>Approximate costs for tool/technology implementation including e.g., purchase, setup, etc.</i>
Tags	<i>Keywords that capture knowledge about the specific case study/Living Lab and the application of the tool.</i>
Publications/Reference	<i>Issued publications that refer to the application of tool/technology to the case study/Living Lab.</i>
Images	<i>Characteristic images or schematic representations of the tools' applications to the Case Study/Living Lab. In case provided as a separate file, all known formats up to a certain size which are supported by web browsers are accepted (e.g., jpeg, png). The file must not exceed 5MB in size.</i>
Caption/Source	<i>Caption needs to be provided for each illustration in textual format, as well as its reference.</i>

14 Annex C: Summary table of the tools documented in D3.4/D3.5

#No.	Tool name (leading partners)	Living Lab using the tool	Deliverable
16	Water reuse strategic platform (VERI/ENG)	Venice	D3.4
17	Environment for decision support and alternative course selection (BASEFORM)	Lisbon	D3.4
18	Re-Actor (CET, AMA)	Alicante	D3.4
19	Sludge management platform (VERI/ENG)	Venice	D3.4
20	UWC observatory (Lisboa E-Nova, third party linked to CML)	Lisbon	D3.4
21	Stormwater reuse management system (AQUAFIN/VITO)	Flanders	D3.4
22	UWOT (ICCS/KWR)	Flanders/East Frisia	D3.5
23	Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS tool (IWW)	East Frisia	D3.5
24	Reclaimed water distribution network water quality model (BASEFORM)	Lisbon	D3.5
25	Water-energy-P balance planning module (BASEFORM)	Lisbon	D3.5
26	QMRA+ (KWR)	Flanders	D3.5
27	RA-Reuse (BASEFORM)	Lisbon	D3.5
28	Short-Term Demand Forecasting Tool (IWW)	East Frisia	D3.5
29	Nessie System (ICCS/NTUA)	Bodø	D3.4
30	Environmental Dashboard (Nordkontakt AS)	Bodø	D3.4
31	SuTRa (KWR) (former ASR-pro tool)	Flanders	D3.5
32	Digital Enabler (ENG)	Venice	D3.4
33	Climate-readiness certification tool (ADENE)	Lisbon	D3.4

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